

IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM): Exploring the dimensions and attributes of a maturity model for IT Infrastructure Automation

A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements
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Declaration of Authorship

I, Henk-Jan Hopman, declare that this thesis titled, 'IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM): Exploring the dimensions and attributes of a maturity model for IT Infrastructure automation' and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- This work was done wholly or mainly during candidature for a research degree at this University.
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- Where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
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- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.
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"The first rule of any technology used in a business is that automation applied to an efficient operation will magnify the efficiency. The second is that automation applied to an inefficient operation will magnify the inefficiency."

Bill Gates

"Automation is good, so long as you know exactly where to put the machine."

Eliyahu Goldratt

"Technology, through automation and artificial intelligence, is definitely one of the most disruptive sources."

Alain Dehaze

"Complexity shall increase with new technologies, and we have to simplify management of Complex IT Infrastructure in the Future."

Amar Prusty

Abstract

Faculty Enterprise Engineering
Executive Master Enterprise IT Architecture

Master of Enterprise IT Architecture (MSc)

IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM): Exploring the dimensions and attributes of a maturity model for IT Infrastructure automation.

by ing. Henk-Jan Hopman BSc

Digital-centric businesses use IT infrastructure to create business value. Today, an IT infrastructure is made up of different parts. These parts are on-premises, cloud, and legacy IT infrastructure. As a result, the IT complexity is tremendously increased. By automating IT infrastructure management, organizations can reduce overall complexity. An automation maturity model helps define a clear roadmap and steps to implement and bring an IT infrastructure to a certain desired maturity level. This research aims to explore whether it is feasible to develop a maturity model for IT infrastructure automation. Design science research is used together with the Delphi method for the iterative development of the maturity model. A new definition and model of the IT infrastructure and IT infrastructure automation are created to understand the environment in which the maturity model operates. The developed maturity model has five levels, allowing automation of the IT infrastructure management to evolve from a stand-alone technology to a fully integrated cross-technological domain environment. Intending to enhance quality and productivity, strengthen a business's competitive advantage, and reduces IT complexity. The maturity model defines three dimensions: People, Processes, and Technology. The people dimension addresses the knowledge and skills needed to understand and implement different levels of automation per maturity level. The technology dimension covers the technical aspects required to operate and maintain an automated IT infrastructure platform. The process dimension concerns the structured and documented workflows guiding IT infrastructure management. Conclusively we can state that this research provides a maturity model for organizations to assess their current IT infrastructure automation level and identify areas for improvement, ultimately strengthening their digital transformation efforts and being better prepared to adopt industry trends. Future research aims to develop and validate the IT infrastructure model and should focus on exploring the "how" aspect of automation and conducting practical validation. Another research topic would be to explore whether reaching maturity level five is possible. With the IT infrastructure automation maturity model, this thesis contributed to both the body of knowledge and the practitioners that can immediately apply the developed maturity model.

Keywords: IT infrastructure, Automation, IT infrastructure automation, Maturity Model, IT infrastructure management, IT infrastructure automation maturity model

Executive Summary

Digital-centric businesses use IT infrastructure to create business value. IT infrastructure refers to the physical and virtual components that enable a business to build and run its applications. Today, an IT infrastructure is made up of different parts. These parts are on-premises, cloud, and legacy IT infrastructure. As a result, IT complexity is increased enormously. This led to the following problem statement:

By automating the IT infrastructure, organizations can reduce overall complexity. An automation maturity model helps to define a clear roadmap and necessary steps to implement and bring it to a certain maturity level, aligning with the business's goals and reducing IT complexity. It also allows people to understand the required capabilities per maturity level since automation is not only about technology.

This research aims to explore whether it is feasible to develop an **IT infrastructure automation maturity model**. The following main research question is formulated to guide this research:

MRQ: What dimensions and attributes constitute an IT infrastructure automation maturity model?

Design science research is used for the iterative development of the maturity model. This method is a systematic and transparent approach to problem-solving, while rigor ensures that the solutions created are scientifically sound. The Delphi method is used together with design science research to incorporate practical knowledge from subject matter experts in a structured and iterative way.

The scientific body lacks recent definitions of IT infrastructure and IT infrastructure automation. These definitions are necessary for the environment in which the maturity model operates. This thesis presents the following new definition of IT infrastructure in the cloud age:

An IT infrastructure platform is a shared foundation consisting of self-service APIs, tools, services, and knowledge. This foundation enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data. The platform comprises both virtual resources and supporting physical technology, which work together in an automated way to provide the necessary services and a managed environment.

Definition 6-2 IT Infrastructure (created by the researcher)

IT Infrastructure automation is defined as follows:

Automation of the IT infrastructure platform consists of the use of software tools and technologies to automatically provision, configure, deploy, and manage physical and virtual resources such as servers, storage, and networking. It involves using automation tools, scripts, and workflows to perform provisioning, patching, and scaling tasks.

Definition 6-2 Automation for the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher)

The thesis suggests a maturity model for the automation of IT infrastructure management. The proposed maturity model answers the main research question by defining three dimensions: People, Processes, and Technology. The people dimension addresses the knowledge and skills needed to understand and implement different levels of automation. The technology dimension covers the technical aspects required to operate and maintain an automated IT infrastructure platform. The process dimension concerns the structured and documented workflows guiding IT infrastructure management.

The developed maturity model consists of five levels for providing a roadmap for automation to develop, see Figure 1. The first level concerns manually managing the IT infrastructure without any automation. For level two, some of the management tasks are automated. At level three, automation is the cornerstone of infrastructure management. At level four, automation is widespread, and policies and access management are handled per technology domain. At level five, the highest maturity level, IT infrastructure management becomes entirely policy driven. Increasing automation maturity enhances quality and productivity, strengthens a company's competitive advantage, and reduces IT complexity.

Figure 1 High-level overview of the maturity model for automation of the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher)

By establishing an IT infrastructure automation maturity model, this research provides a framework for organizations to assess their current IT infrastructure automation level and identify areas for improvement, ultimately strengthening their digital transformation efforts and being better prepared to adopt industry trends.

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1 Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the research topic by introducing the research problem, the problem statement, and the associated research questions. In the remaining part of the chapter, the applied research methodology is briefly described, followed by a discussion of the practical and scientific impact and relevance of this research. The chapter closes with the structure of this thesis.

1.1 Introducing the Research Problem

In today's IT landscape, technologies are changing rapidly, and the landscape is shifting towards a more hybrid environment where it is hard to differentiate between the IT infrastructure and applications (Sinclair & Keane, 2019). The IT infrastructure enables an organization to build and run the applications that underlie its business and helps to achieve cost optimizations, flexibility, and efficiency (Rimol, 2022). Over the past few decades, the IT infrastructure has undergone a significant shift from the "iron age" to the "cloud age" (Morris, 2020). Several technological advances, such as virtualization, software-defined networking, and the widespread availability of the high-speed Internet, have driven this shift. The shift towards cloud-based infrastructure has transformed the way organizations operate. An organization must change its operating model and move towards a digital-centric business to remain competitive (Bhandari, 2021). Digital-centric businesses use technology to create new business value. Generally speaking, the role of IT within organizations is changing due to this shift toward the "cloud age," which affects the function of IT infrastructure.

Unfortunately, with this shift comes an increase in complexity (Help_Net_Security, 2022; Nallappan, 2022; Saunderson, 2021). This complexity is enhanced because IT infrastructures often rely on legacy IT systems. These legacy systems introduce what is called technical debt. Technical debt is a term that describes the accumulation of inefficiencies and limitations in an organization's IT landscape (Ashok Vasa, 2023). Outdated software, hardware, skills, processes, or practices can cause technical debt. Many organizations have a tremendous amount of technical debt due to an extensive patchwork of different technologies and processes that are often not optimized, lean, connected, consistent, or explicit. On top of that, technical debt makes it difficult to modernize your business and adapt to changing markets because it diverts resources away from meaningful investments. As a result of the shift towards the "cloud age" and the presence of technical debt, the complexity of IT infrastructure is tremendously increased (Atchison, 2022).

To overcome the complexity of IT in an organization, it is essential to have a clear understanding of the business objectives and IT requirements. Adopting an agile approach, simplifying processes, and investing in modern technologies, such as automation, can also help reduce complexity and improve organizational efficiency (Atchison, 2022).

1.2 The Problem Statement

The traditional IT infrastructure and its applications are operated and maintained manually. As a result, organizations waste money, time, and talent, sacrifice quality, and are exposed to significant security risks (Rimol, 2022). For organizations to overcome their technical debt challenge and quickly adopt new technologies in their environment, automation of the IT infrastructure is needed (Stephen, 2020). Automation refers to the use of technology and software to perform tasks or processes that would otherwise require human intervention (Ninja, 2021). Automation aims to improve processes' efficiency, accuracy, and speed while reducing potential errors or variations. In addition, organizations are increasingly using automation to automate IT infrastructure deployment, configuration, monitoring, and management.

When the IT infrastructure is not properly managed, it affects business performance and reduces revenue (Serrano & Pereira, 2020). By automating the IT infrastructure, organizations can reduce overall complexity and increase security with fewer resources and operational costs while simultaneously providing faster and more flexible services and keeping up with the competition (Bigelow, 2019; Maxima_Consulting, 2021). Furthermore, by implementing automation, organizations can reduce human error and increase efficiency by eliminating manual human actions (McHugh, 2022).

Furthermore, the automation of IT infrastructure is not a one-time thing. It needs continuous attention. Implementing automation and bringing it to a certain maturity level takes time, requires planning and coordination, and is probably done in different steps (Rimol, 2022). However, implementing automation is not achieved overnight and can be complex.

A framework offers a structured way to support an organization that implements processes and products, such as automation (Chrissis, Konrad, & Shrum, 2011). A maturity model provides this framework by defining a clear roadmap for the organization, describing the necessary steps to achieve the goals, and providing a means to measure progress (Becker, Knackstedt, & Pöppelbuß, 2009). The roadmap to implement automation and bring it to a preferred maturity level requires the right resources, skills, tools, and a focused plan that aligns with the goals of the enterprise organization. In Figure 2 Characteristics of Automation Maturity (source: Gartner's leadership vision for 2022 (H. Chris, 2021)) an example of characteristics of a maturity roadmap is presented.

Source: Gartner

Figure 2 Characteristics of Automation Maturity (source: Gartner's leadership vision for 2022 (H. Chris, 2021))

Maturity models allow an organization to assess its current state and guide it toward its preferred end state (Becker et al., 2009). Therefore, an automation maturity model for the IT infrastructure can help organizations overcome their IT complexity. It allows an organization to assess its current automation maturity level and identify gaps in its automation capabilities by performing a maturity assessment.

1.3 Research Question

This research aims to explore whether it is feasible to develop an **IT infrastructure automation maturity model**. This maturity model must be a practical framework with a scientific foundation for implementing automation. The following main research question is formulated to provide guidance to this research:

MRQ: Which dimensions and attributes constitute an IT infrastructure automation maturity model?

IT infrastructure refers to the physical and virtual components required to support an organization's information technology services to deliver storage, processing, and security (Haris, 2010). As mentioned above, there is a shift toward a cloud-based IT infrastructure, which supports computing that relies on a network of remote servers hosted on the Internet to store, manage, and process data instead of relying on local servers or personal computers (Dijk, 2017). This research needs a clear definition of this cloud-based IT infrastructure. Hence, the first sub-question is to define a clear description of an IT infrastructure.

RQ01: What is an IT infrastructure?

The second sub-question is about automation, to define and scope the role and place in the context of an IT infrastructure. Automation is a broad concept within information technology. Automation in IT infrastructure management involves the use of software tools to manage and optimize IT infrastructure, such as automating server provisioning and configuration management. In contrast, application automation typically requires software tools to streamline the development process, such as automated testing and deployment tasks (Humble & Farley, 2011).

RQ02: What is IT infrastructure automation?

The following research question investigates the availability and current state of maturity models for automation of the IT infrastructure and identifies if already existing models could be re-used as a starting point.

RQ03: What models of IT infrastructure automation maturity are available in the current scientific literature?

A maturity model framework (Poeppelbuss, Niehaves, Simons, & Becker, 2011) usually includes maturity levels, dimensions, and attributes. The model defines a set of maturity levels through which an organization can progress. Each level represents a higher degree of

maturity. The model also identifies the key dimension that an organization must develop to move to a higher maturity level. Attributes are defined to measure and assess the progress of dimensions (Lasrado, Vatrapu, & Andersen, 2015). The following sub-questions aim to identify these dimensions, attributes, and how they can be placed within a maturity model.

RQ04: What are the useful dimensions along which the maturity of IT infrastructure can be assessed?

RQ05: What are the useful attributes of each of these dimensions?

1.4 Research Methodology at a Glance

Design science research is a problem-solving approach that involves creating and evaluating artifacts in real-world settings (Hevner & Chatterjee, 2010; Recker, 2021). Design science research aims to develop innovative solutions to practical problems by leveraging knowledge from various fields, such as academic research and practical information. This information refers to the knowledge gained from stakeholders, users, and other relevant parties.

One of the key characteristics of design science research is the use of rigorous methods to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of their artifacts. The research methodology used for this research is design science research due to the combination of rigor and practical information, which leads to the creation of innovative solutions that meet academic and practical needs. This research only uses the different phases of design science research to develop the artifact. The phases for evaluation are not part of this research.

Design science research provides a systematic and transparent approach to problem-solving, while rigor ensures that the solutions created are scientifically sound. Most importantly, practical information ensures that the artifact created is practical and usable in the problem context. The iterative framework used within design science research (Vom Brocke, Hevner, & Maedche, 2020) and adapted to the research of this thesis is presented in Figure 3 The research approach of this thesis (created by the researcher)

Figure 3 The research approach of this thesis (created by the researcher)

The Delphi method (Alarabiat & Ramos, 2019; Turoff & Linstone, 2002) is used as a structured, organized, and iterative process to gather data. The strength of the Delphi method is to create consensus with opinions from a panel or individual experts. The Delphi method conceives data in a setting with incomplete knowledge of the 'research problem.' The Delphi method is combined with design science research to incorporate practical knowledge fully.

The research approach is visualized in the middle part of the above figure. This research aims to explore and define these different steps during the following phases.

1. With scientific rigor and practical knowledge from subject matter experts, find and define ingredients for the automation of an IT infrastructure.
2. These ingredients are the basis for a prototype artifact that a panel of experts can validate.
3. Based on the panel's outcome, a prototype artifact (Maturity model (Poepelbuss et al., 2011)) is designed to evaluate and implement automation initiatives in steps.

1.5 Impact and Relevance

Automation has become a crucial component in the IT infrastructure of organizations (Josh Chessman, 2020; Saunderson, 2021), and a maturity model framework can be used to assess an organization's level of automation in its IT infrastructure. This model can provide practical benefits and relevance to organizations to overcome their IT complexity. As a result, efficiency increases, costs reduce, and quality improves.

Maturity models have a clear relation with the IT processes of an organization. This relation is described by Nedzalskay et al. (Nedzalskay, Moiseyev, Bikineeva, & Bulakina, 2020); see Figure 4 Relations between business objectives and how maturity models contribute

(adapted from (Nedzelskay et al., 2020)). For the evaluation of IT processes, there are three approaches. The first is efficiency, and the second is results; both can be measured with performance indicators. The third is maturity, which is measured with maturity models. In addition, they point out that technical competence is needed for infrastructure management.

This research is about a maturity model in a technical environment. The following sections discuss the potential practical impact and scientific relevance of an automated IT infrastructure maturity model.

Figure 4 Relations between business objectives and how maturity models contribute (adapted from (Nedzelskay et al., 2020))

1.5.1 Practical Impact

The practical impact of an IT infrastructure maturity model for automation is significant for organizations seeking to overcome their IT complexity. By providing a framework for assessing the level of automation in an organization's IT infrastructure, the model can help organizations identify areas for improvement and guide automation efforts. This is also stated by K. Morris (Morris, 2020). He describes that for organizations to be successful in their digital transformation and operation, automation is essential for the high-quality delivery of IT infrastructure services.

A survey conducted by the consulting firm Gartner in 2021 revealed that 70% of information and operations leaders view IT Infrastructure automation as a strategic topic for the next four years, and 50% of these leaders plan to develop skills in IT Infrastructure automation (Rimol, 2022). The IT automation trends for 2022 indicate that automation is rapidly increasing due to a rise in data volume and data diversity, driving enterprise organizations toward new IT infrastructure technologies (McHugh, 2022). Furthermore, the network

vendor Cisco presents in their trend paper “Network Automation Trends and Strategy” that it is also relevant for an organization to have an automation strategy (Pinto & Lacunza, 2021). A white paper from the VMware Infrastructure Virtualization Vendor (VMWare, 2022) presents the same conclusion.

1.5.2 Theoretical Impact

The question arises: Is a maturity model already available in the scientific body of knowledge? This research explores the development of a new maturity model. A study of the body of knowledge conducted during this research shows that different researchers report that there are different maturity models available. The research of Wendlers (Wendler, 2012) maps a total of two hundred and thirty-seven scientific papers about maturity models to twenty different domains, mainly the domains in computer science and information science. Researchers Proença and Borbinha (Proença & Borbinha, 2016) researched the current practice of the maturity model in the available scientific literature. They found twenty-two maturity models with the same number of domains. A study by Poepelbuss et al. (Poepelbuss et al., 2011) found 76 relevant articles about maturity models in different science fields. The findings of Poepelbuss et al. and Wendlers are also mentioned in the related work part of the research of Monteiro et al. (Monteiro & Maciel, 2020). This recent research from around 2020 found more than 600 academic papers about maturity models. As can be said, the scientific body of knowledge contains many maturity models that cover many domains. Only one maturity model is found that covers the IT infrastructure; This is a model from Ferry Haris called 'IT Infrastructure Maturity Model' (Haris, 2010). Another observation is that limited information about the IT landscape's technological part (IT infrastructure and automation) is available in the body of knowledge.

In addition to the scientific body of knowledge, practical information, such as white papers and technical journals, is available in the information and technology industry. Several maturity models can be found within the industry body of knowledge, but all address a specific technology or product range. As an example, a network automation maturity model developed by NetBrain (Netbrain, 2022), a network automation maturity model developed by Cisco (Howell, 2022), and a more general IT automation model from EMA (Drogseth & Twing, May 2020). The consultancy firm Gartner has developed a more generic maturity model for the IT infrastructure (Scott, Pultz, T, Bittman, & McGuckin, 2007).

Answering the question at the beginning of this section, this research contributes to the scientific body of knowledge by adding a new maturity model. Additionally, it adds a new maturity model for the automation of the entire IT infrastructure instead of one of the different technology-based constituent parts.

1.6 Thesis Structure

The thesis is organized into four parts (see Figure 5 Outline of the thesis (created by researcher)). Part 1 of this thesis presents background information on the main concepts and research approach, covering both theoretical and practical aspects. Chapter 2 delves into the theoretical concepts of IT infrastructure, automation, and maturity models. Moving on to Chapter 3, the research approach is described, including the research methods used and the literature review conducted.

Part 2 will cover the exploration phase of the thesis. In this phase, the artifact's creation, namely a maturity model for IT infrastructure automation, is described in detail. Chapter 4 begins by examining the three core concepts of IT infrastructure, automation, and maturity models. Followed by the development of the preliminary maturity model in Chapter 5.

Figure 5 Outline of the thesis (created by researcher)

The development of the artifact, the IT infrastructure automation maturity model, and the definitions of IT infrastructure and automation are presented and described in Chapter 6, which is Part 3.

Part 4 is about critically looking back and forward. Chapter 7 reflects on and discusses the research process and results. Chapter 8 answers the research questions, and conclusions, limitations, and recommendations for future work are presented.

2 Theoretical Foundation

This chapter describes the theoretical foundation that is relevant to this research. The theoretical foundation is the context in which this research takes place and provides the pertinent theory to be analyzed to answer the research questions. For a good foundation, the different theoretical concepts are described from a rather generic perspective to a more specific one. The first concept described is the IT infrastructure, followed by the concept of automation. The next concept is IT infrastructure automation, a compound of the first two concepts. Another key topic that is described is maturity models. The central concept behind a maturity model is introduced and explained. At the end of the chapter, an overview of the available maturity model related to IT infrastructure automation is provided.

2.1 Introduction

The theoretical framework for this thesis is constructed using the following iterative steps: finding many studies and understanding relationships and theory. These steps result in the theoretical framework (Chumney, 2016) (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 Process of creating a theoretical framework (adapted from (Chumney, 2016)).

The iterative way of working on creating this theoretical framework is described in more detail in Section 3.3, Literature Review Strategy. The theoretical framework consists of three primary sources: scientific literature, industry publications, and books.

1.1 IT Infrastructure

Information technology (IT) infrastructure is a strategic capability for organizations to perform their business (Broadbent, Weill, & Neo, 1999). The purpose of an IT infrastructure is to support different business processes. These processes are supported not only by the IT infrastructure but also by applications. Applications are the technology that directly supports the business environment, and the IT infrastructure supports applications. This relationship and alignment are also captured in the Guidelines Regarding Architecture Alignment (GRAAL) (van Eck, Blanken, & Wieringa, 2004), which defines how different service layers can support business processes; see Figure 7.

Figure 7 Service of GRAAL framework (adapted from (van Eck et al., 2004))

A more formal definition of the business IT alignment is provided by Santana Tapia (Santana Tapia, 2009), which is:

The process of making the services offered by IT support the requirements of the business – whether such services are offered individually by one participant in the collaborative networked organization or collaboratively by the entire network – so that value is created for the participating organizations of the collaborative networked organization.

Definition 2-1 Business-IT alignment according to (Santana Tapia, 2009)

The definition of Santana Tapia makes clear that IT services can support the business processes of your organization and those of others. The essence of this definition was already captured in a model by Broadbent et al. (Broadbent et al., 1999) see Figure 8. This model perfectly shows the IT infrastructure's supporting function to the business processes.

Figure 8 The elements of IT infrastructure (adapted from Broadband et al. (Broadbent et al., 1999))

Broadbent et al. state that the IT infrastructure capability comprises three aspects: service, human, and technical. These aspects stand for:

- *Shared Information Services.* Refers to the infrastructure as services users can understand, draw upon, and share to support conducting businesses.

- *Human Information Technology Infrastructure*. Refers to knowledge, skills, standards, and experience required to operate and manage IT components.
- *Information Technology Components*. Refers to the IT components, the technology commodities readily available in the market, such as computers, routers, printers, database software packages, operating systems, etc.

Bryd and Truner's (Byrd & Turner, 2015) research supports this view. They also see that the IT infrastructure is not only a technical IT infrastructure but also contains the human aspects of the IT infrastructure. According to them, the definition of IT infrastructure is as follows:

The IT infrastructure is the shared IT resources consisting of a technical, physical base of hardware, software, communications technologies, data, and core applications and a human component of skills, expertise, competencies, commitments, values, norms, and knowledge that combine to create IT services that are typically unique to an organization. These IT services provide a foundation for communication interchange across the organization and for developing and implementing current and future business applications.

Definition 2-2 IT infrastructure according to (Byrd & Turner, 2015)

On the other hand, Santana Tapia points out that the IT infrastructure is based on the following two IT entities, which are based on the GRAAL framework (van Eck et al., 2004):

- *The software infrastructure* consists of the collection of standard general-purpose software needed to run all information system services. It ranges from operating systems, middleware, and network software to database management software.
- *Physical infrastructure* consists of computers, cables, wireless access points, printers, and user interface devices to support software running in an organization.

In the research of Geert Haerens (Haerens, 2016), he defines the IT infrastructure as follows:

'Infrastructure = Physical Infrastructure (according to GRAAL) + Software Infrastructure (according to GRAAL)'

Definition 2-3 IT infrastructure according to (Haerens, 2016)

An almost similar definition of the IT infrastructure is presented by Gartner (Gartner, 2022):

The IT infrastructure is the system of hardware and software installations and service components that support the delivery of business systems and IT-enabled processes.

Definition 2-4 IT infrastructure according to (Gartner, 2022)

Based on the different definitions mentioned above, the IT infrastructure can be described as a physical infrastructure with software components that provide services to the business. Generally speaking, based on all these different definitions, a general statement can be made that the IT infrastructure supports and facilitates the business.

Figure 9 Views on IT infrastructure (adapted from (Laan, 2017))

Although all these different definitions suggest that it is clear how an IT infrastructure can be defined, it still isn't. It is still a bit 'vague' how an IT infrastructure can be seen. This vagueness is also highlighted by Sjaak Laan ((Laan, 2017). He describes that it depends on your perspective on how a person or organization sees or defines an IT infrastructure and visualizes the different perspectives, see Figure 9.

Sjaak Laan presents the most comprehensive model for describing an IT infrastructure in his book IT Infrastructure Architecture (Laan, 2017); see Figure 10. Although this model is a simplified representation, it contains all the essential building blocks to build an infrastructure.

Figure 10 The IT infrastructure model (adapted from (Laan, 2017))

In addition, this model combines more or less the mentioned definitions and incorporates the relationship with the processes, which connects to the business. Business IT alignment is not fully covered in this model because it lacks the business environment defined by the GRAAL framework. However, because it contains the essential building block for infrastructure, this model is the basis for the perspective of how the IT infrastructure is seen in this thesis.

In the introduction to this thesis's problem statement, the IT infrastructure change in the last decade is already mentioned. This change is called the shift from the 'iron age' to the 'cloud age' (Morris, 2020). The IT infrastructure model (Figure 10) represents the 'iron age' IT infrastructure. Due to the introduction of the Cloud, the IT infrastructure has changed. Table 1 provides a summary of these changes. The most significant change is the introduction of virtualization technology (virtualized resources in the table).

Iron Age	Cloud Age
Physical Hardware	Virtualized resource
Provisioning takes weeks	Provisioning takes minutes
Manual Processes	Automated Processes

Table 1 IT infrastructure changes through time (adapted from (Morris, 2020))

Like the IT infrastructure model, the cloud IT infrastructure can be represented by building blocks (Musse & Alamro, 2016); see Figure 11. The adaption of the Cloud shifts the traditional IT infrastructure landscape, based on personal computers and enterprise computing in its own data centers (on-premises), towards an IT infrastructure based on virtual and distributed computing. With distributed computing, the necessary infrastructure components are in other data centers than in the on-premises data center of an organization.

Figure 11 Building blocks of a cloud IT infrastructure (adopted from (Musse & Alamro, 2016))

Within Cloud, services and how they are delivered are separated, where the service model supports the application and business needs. The Cloud does not change how applications support the business and conforms to the models and definitions of GRAAL (van Eck et al., 2004), Broadbent et al. (Broadbent et al., 1999) and Santana Tapia (Santana Tapia, 2009). Cloud service models and delivery models are illustrated in Figure 12 Cloud service models and delivery models (adapted from (Dijk, 2017)). These models are essential for grasping the essence of the research, as they provide the theoretical background.

Figure 12 Cloud service models and delivery models (adapted from (Dijk, 2017))

The service models for a cloud IT infrastructure are software-as-a-service (SaaS), platform-as-a-service (PaaS), and infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS).

1. *Software-as-a-Service (SaaS)*: With SaaS, a provider offers its (proprietary) software products in a cloud model. Consumers can access the software through a thin client interface (e.g., a web interface) or a program interface. In this model, the customer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but only has limited available customization options built into the software (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016).
2. *Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS)*: PaaS is one step further down in its level of abstraction, allowing the customer to deploy their applications on the cloud architecture (be it consumer-created or acquired). The cloud provider manages the underlying cloud architecture, where the consumer controls the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the hosting environment (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016).
3. *Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS)*: With IaaS, the service provider offers an environment where the consumer can deploy and run software, ranging from operating systems to applications. The cloud provider manages the cloud infrastructure, but the consumer controls all functionalities, such as operating systems, storage, and deployed applications (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016).

A delivery model for cloud computing refers to how cloud service models are provided to customers. It outlines the methods by which cloud service models are deployed, managed, and accessed. The main delivery models for cloud computing include public, private, community, hybrid, and virtual private Cloud.

- *Public Cloud*: Public Cloud is a type of cloud computing delivery model where a third-party service provider offers computing resources and services, such as virtual machines, storage, and applications, over the internet to a broad range of users. This model allows organizations to rent computing resources on demand and pay only for what they use without investing in and maintaining their own infrastructure (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016).
- *Private Cloud*: Private Cloud is a type of cloud computing where the computing resources, including servers, storage, and networking, are dedicated to a single organization or user. It is a cloud delivery model that offers the same benefits as the

public cloud, such as scalability and on-demand resources, but with added security and control. Private Cloud can be deployed on-premises or hosted by a third-party provider (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016).

- Community Cloud: A community cloud is a cloud computing deployment model in which a group of organizations with common interests shares a cloud infrastructure to meet their specific needs. The community cloud model allows organizations to achieve cost savings and economies of scale by sharing resources while maintaining a level of control and privacy that is impossible in public cloud deployments. The community cloud model can facilitate collaboration and information sharing among member organizations (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016).
- Hybrid Cloud: A hybrid cloud is a delivery model that combines two or more different cloud deployment models, typically a combination of public and private cloud environments. It allows organizations to take advantage of both models while addressing specific needs and requirements, such as data security and compliance regulations. The hybrid cloud model can also provide greater flexibility, scalability, and cost-effectiveness than a single deployment model (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016).
- Virtual Private Cloud: Refers to a cloud computing model that provides a private cloud environment using public cloud infrastructure. It enables users to create isolated virtual networks within a public cloud provider's network, allowing organizations greater control over their resources and security. With a virtual private cloud, users can configure and manage virtual servers, storage, and networking resources as if using an on-premises infrastructure (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016).

At the beginning of this section, the IT infrastructure capability is described as containing three aspects (service, human, and technical). In addition, this capability is essential to support the development of information technology within the business. As pointed out by Anwar et al. (Anwar & Masrek, 2014), Seppo Sirkemaa (Sirkemaa), and Byrd and Turner (Byrd & Turner, 2015) to have an organization that profits from information technology development, the business needs to be flexible. Additionally, the IT infrastructure must be flexible to support this.

Anwar et al. (Anwar & Masrek, 2014) developed a framework for the IT infrastructure that positively influences the flexibility needed in a business. This framework comprises three aspects: process, human, and technology. The framework is shown in Figure 13 IT infrastructure flexibility (adapted from (Anwar & Masrek, 2014)). This flexibility is needed due to changes in markets or applications (Anwar & Masrek, 2014; Byrd & Turner, 2015). This flexibility requires an IT infrastructure that is built to meet the standards. These standards make it possible to be compatible and easily accommodate the change in the existing IT infrastructure.

In addition to the influence of technology and the human aspect on the IT infrastructure, it is crucial to note that the process aspect is the most important. Serrano et al. also describe this essential point (Serrano & Pereira, 2020). They have found that processes are essential to be implemented to manage the whole IT infrastructure. In addition, IT infrastructure is a

complex universe consisting of different building blocks with various technologies. And due to the Cloud, there are also different service and delivery models.

Figure 13 IT infrastructure flexibility (adapted from (Anwar & Masrek, 2014))

The different resources of the cloud service and delivery models must be managed; this can be time-consuming. Automation is the solution for an organization’s IT department to manage its IT infrastructure seamlessly on-premises and in the cloud (the combination is known as hybrid) (Nedzelskay et al., 2020). In the next section, the concept of automation will be explained in more detail.

2.2 Automation

To understand why automation helps to manage IT infrastructure, it is essential to understand the concept of automation. Automation is mentioned in the previous section as a methodology to manage IT infrastructures. In essence, automation can be defined as (Ghazizadeh, Lee, & Boyle, 2012; Parasuraman, Sheridan, & Wickens, 2000; Vagia, Transeth, & Fjerdingen, 2016; Wickens, Li, Santamaria, Sebok, & Sarter, 2010):

Automation is the use of technology to execute a function that was previously performed by humans.

Definition 2-5 Automation (adapted from (Ghazizadeh et al., 2012))

This definition shows that automation can be used in many different ways. It also implies that automation is not all or none. The use of automation can vary across a continuum of levels, from the lowest to the highest level of full automation (Parasuraman et al., 2000; Vagia et al., 2016). Research by Vagia et al. (Vagia et al., 2016) shows that different models describe levels of automation. These levels define that a human only executes the function at the lowest level; at the highest level, a computer performs all functions autonomously. Sheridan and Verplank already described in their research the first levels of automation in

1978 (Sheridan & Verplank, 1978), where they represent the shift of the role of an operator in the industry from manual to supervisory control; see Figure 14.

Level of autonomy	Description	Explanation
Level 1	Fully manual control	The computer offers no assistance.
Level 2	The computer offers a complete set of decision/action alternatives	Several options are provided to the human who decides.
Level 3	The computer narrows the selection down to a few	Human still has to decide.
Level 4	The computer suggests one alternative	Human decides amongst suggestions.
Level 5	The computer executes that suggestion if the human approves	Human approval needed for execution.
Level 6	The computer allows the human a restricted time to veto before automatic execution	Limited time for veto given to the human.
Level 7	The computer executes automatically, then necessarily informs the human	No human interference, just information at the end.
Level 8	The computer informs the human only if asked	Human gets information only if asks.
Level 9	The computer informs the human only if it decides to	Computer decides whether to give information.
Level 10	Fully autonomous Control	The computer decides everything and acts autonomously, ignoring the human.

Figure 14 Levels of automation (adapted from (Sheridan & Verplank, 1978))

In a research conducted by Vagia et al. (Vagia et al., 2016), they investigated different models of levels of automation. After comparing these models, they proposed an eight-level model that fits better within modern information technology; see Figure 15.

Level of autonomy	Description	Description
Level 1	Manual control	Computer offers no assistance
Level 2	Decision proposal stage	The computer offers some decisions to the operator. The operator is responsible to decide and execute.
Level 3	Human decision select stage	The human selects one decision and the computer executes.
Level 4	Computer decision select stage	The computer selects one decision and executes with human approval
Level 5	Computer execution and human information stage	The computer executes the selected decision and informs the human
Level 6	Computer execution and on call human information stage	The computer executes the selected decision and informs the human only if asked
Level 7	Computer execution and voluntarily information stage	The computer executes the selected decision and informs the human only if it decides to
Level 8	Autonomous control stage	The computer does everything without human notification, except if an error that is not into the specifications arrives. In that case the computer needs to inform the operator.

Figure 15 Level of automation (adapted from (Vagia et al., 2016))

Organizations face a challenge when levels of automation increase. This challenge is called the *automation problem* (Endsley, 2018):

The more automation is added to a system, and the more reliable and robust that automation is, the less likely human operators overseeing the automation will be aware of critical information and able to take over manual control when needed. More automation refers to automation used for more functions, longer durations, higher automation levels, and automation that encompasses longer task sequences.

Definition 2-6 Automation problem (adapted from (Endsley, 2018))

Hancock (Hancock, 2014) discusses in his paper ‘Automation: How much is too much?’ the loss of level of control for humans. Endsley and Hancock conclude that organizations need to adopt technology and the use of automation to remain accurate in their business. However, organizations must be very aware of when and if they want to lose control. The most important message that both researchers give is that human operators of automated systems must always be informed and able to interact effectively and safely with the system.

2.2.1 IT automation

In the previous section, the purpose of automation was explained. The definition of automation can be explicitly defined for information technology. Within information technology, automation can be defined as follows (Bigelow, 2019; Ninja, 2021; Stephen, 2020):

IT Automation can be defined as the use of software and scripts to execute repeatable tasks and reduce human interaction with IT systems.

Definition 2-7 IT automation (created by the researcher)

IT automation ranges from a scope of single on-off tasks to more routine repeatable tasks and ultimately to tasks that are executed autonomously. Software tools and application frameworks with minimum human intervention perform these tasks. Before these tools or applications can be released in a production environment, they must be tested. The different steps involved are named a deployment pipeline or workflow. A deployment pipeline is, in essence, an automated implementation of the application build, deploy, test, and release process (Humble & Farley, 2011); see Figure 16.

Figure 16 Deployment pipeline (adapted from (Humble & Farley, 2011))

This deployment pipeline is the main driver for delivering and deploying software in an automated and continuous way, as described by Humble et al. (Humble & Farley, 2011; Humble, Kim, & Forsgren, 2018). The pipeline releases software (applications) quickly and with a repeatable process. The application platform includes these pipelines for these applications' continuous integration (CI) and continuous deployment (CD). The application runs after deployment on the resources of the IT infrastructure. Both building blocks are depicted in Figure 10 The IT infrastructure model (adapted from (Laan, 2017)). The combined interaction between these layers is responsible for the delivery of software as an automated process. Therefore, automation is a key successor to application delivery.

Automatization between the application platform and the infrastructure is about the provisioning of virtual (and sometimes physical) resources. The main difference between automation for applications and automation for infrastructure resource provisions is the following. Automation for application source code is used to build and deploy an application, and automation for the infrastructure is used to provision components with configuration parameters (Humble & Farley, 2011; Morris, 2020). The similarity is that the same automation application workflow (pipeline) mechanism can be used and that the configuration parameters are handled just like the source code. The automated way to provision the infrastructure is called Infrastructure as Code (IaC) (Morris, 2020). With infrastructure as code, infrastructure resources can repeatedly recreate the same application environment.

Infrastructure as code is what is called a cloud-age approach. This approach embraces the continuous change of the application and provides higher reliability and quality. It also reduces errors and makes governance, security, and compliance control visible (Morris, 2020).

2.2.2 IT Infrastructure Automation

IT infrastructure automation is the automation to operate and manage the infrastructure (Maxima_Consulting, 2021). As seen in the IT infrastructure model (Figure 10), the infrastructure is a compound of different building blocks. Based on this context, IT infrastructure automation can be defined as follows:

Infrastructure automation uses technology to manage and operate physical and virtual resources, such as computer hardware and operating systems, networking components, and data storage systems, to deliver IT services and solutions.

Definition 2-8 IT infrastructure automation (created by the researcher)

Within the IT infrastructure, two types of infrastructure can be defined that need to be managed and operated (Maxima_Consulting, 2021); these are:

- *Traditional infrastructure*: refers to all physical components, such as computer hardware and operating systems, networking components, data storage systems, and other equipment owned and managed by the business within its facilities and data centers. This type of infrastructure is usually quite expensive to manage and operate. (Haris, 2010; Maxima_Consulting, 2021; Morris, 2020)
- *Cloud infrastructure*: refers to all components and resources related to cloud computing, and the service model for cloud infrastructure is only Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) and supports all the delivery models (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Maxima_Consulting, 2021; Musse & Alamro, 2016; Redhat, 2019).

However, there is a significant difference between the way of working with these two types. These differences are shown in Table 2.

Traditional infrastructure	Cloud Infrastructure
The cost of change is high.	The cost of change is low.
Change has a high impact on stability.	Changes have a low impact on stability.
Reduce the opportunities to fail.	Maximize the speed of improvement.
Deliver in large batches, test at the end	Deliver small changes, and test continuously.
Long release cycles.	Short release cycles.
Monolithic architecture (fewer, larger moving parts).	Microservices architecture (more, smaller parts).
GUI-driven or physical configuration.	Configuration as Code.

Table 2 Difference in the way of working for infrastructure types (adapted from (Morris, 2020))

Another aspect within the realm of IT infrastructure automation is life cycle management. Life cycle management involves several stages: planning, design, implementation, operation, and maintenance. These stages can be described as day-n operations (Codiline, 2023; Rami, 2015), which are:

1. Day-0 involves designing and implementing the infrastructure based on the organization's requirements.
2. Day-1 focuses on configuring and operating the infrastructure to ensure it functions efficiently and effectively.
3. Day-2 or Day-N involves periodic upgrades and modifications of the infrastructure to keep up with the changing needs.

Based on these insights, IT infrastructure automation can be defined as:

IT infrastructure automation supports processes of the different lifecycle phases to have a predictable and repeatable interaction with the different IT infrastructure building blocks of a traditional and cloud infrastructure.

Definition 2-9 IT Infrastructure Automation (created by the researcher)

This definition directly highlights the challenge of IT infrastructure automation. On the one hand, it must be able to deal with traditional IT infrastructure building blocks and, on the other hand, with cloud-based IT infrastructure building blocks. Managing and operating both types of IT infrastructure at once increases the complexity of IT (Atchison, 2022; Sinclair & Keane, 2019). This complexity is exacerbated because IT infrastructures often rely on legacy IT systems. These legacy systems introduce what is called technical debt. Technical debt is a term that describes the accumulation of inefficiencies and limitations in an organization's IT landscape (Ashok Vasa, 2023; Atchison, 2022). Although technical debt sounds like a traditional 'thing,' only technical debt covers the building blocks that are often outdated and do not support the automated way of working. In contrast, traditional is about on-premises IT infrastructure with updated building blocks.

IT infrastructure automation must deal with three different aspects to be successful, namely:

- Traditional IT Infrastructure Building Blocks
- Cloud IT Infrastructure Building Blocks
- Legacy IT Infrastructure Building Blocks

2.3 Maturity Models

For the management of software and systems within information technology, organizations constantly seek ways to improve quality, increase efficiency, and reduce costs (Becker et al., 2009; Nedzelskay et al., 2020; Serrano & Pereira, 2020). Information technology management's primary goal is to improve IT performance continuously (Becker et al., 2009). A maturity model provides a roadmap for the organization, describing the necessary steps to achieve this goal and providing a means to measure progress (Becker et al., 2009). The concept of a maturity model is defined by Becker J et al. (Becker et al., 2009) as follows:

A maturity model consists of a sequence of maturity levels for a class of objects. It represents an anticipated, desired, or typical evolution path of these objects shaped as discrete stages.

Definition 2-10 Maturity Model (adapted from (Becker et al., 2009))

Based on this definition, we can state that a maturity model can be used as a "tool" to define the current maturity level and the corresponding gap to reach the next maturity level (Proença & Borbinha, 2016). As stated by Santana Tapia (Santana Tapia, 2009), the maturity model also gives a path to evolve toward a higher level over time.

In their research on IT infrastructure management, Serrano and Pereira (Serrano & Pereira, 2020) describe the concepts of a maturity model. This concept comprises three elements: maturity, capability, and maturity levels. These descriptions are shown in Table 3 Maturity Model Concepts (adapted from (Serrano & Pereira, 2020)).

Concepts	Description
Maturity	The maturity concept has been described as a 'state in which an organization is perfectly able to achieve the goals it sets itself.' This concept is recognized as a measure to assess the organization's capabilities. The “component” of maturity may be an object, a system, or a person.
Capability	Capability is characterized as the ability of an organization to produce value. Organizations strategically use their capabilities to improve their 'abilities' to another efficient and effective level.
Maturity Levels	Maturity levels or stages are a sequential path, not just to give an improvement path to the organization but also to “situate” organization capabilities at a hierarchal level. There are often five maturity levels, each with procedures to implement to achieve that level.

Table 3 Maturity Model Concepts (adapted from (Serrano & Pereira, 2020))

The most well-known maturity model in the information technology field is the Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI) (Chrissis et al., 2011). CMMI is a framework that contains the knowledge and experience of many experts. In addition, this model is the basis for most maturity models used today due to basic principles and concepts (Santana Tapia, 2009; Serrano & Pereira, 2020). A CMMI model can be categorized into two types, namely, staged and continuous (Chrissis et al., 2011; Santana Tapia, 2009). Both types use the same concepts but are organized in different ways. Where levels describe maturity objectives, these types describe the improvement path only in different ways. The description of both is given in Table 4 Types of improvement paths (adapted from (Serrano & Pereira, 2020)).

Paths	Description
Staged	The staged model helps an organization improve its capabilities as a whole. Organizational capabilities must comply with those characteristics of that level to achieve a certain maturity level. This model helps organizations characterize the overall state of organizational capabilities.
Continuous	In a continuous path is the description of the procedures to improve/evaluate in-divided each capability of a domain to improve. Each capability can be at a different maturity level. This helps the organization develop and characterize the state of its individual capabilities and abilities.

Table 4 Types of improvement paths (adapted from (Serrano & Pereira, 2020))

The definition of a staged maturity model and continuous maturity model are described in more detail by Pereira and Silva (de Sousa Pereira & da Silva, 2010). A CMMI model typically has five maturity levels (Chrissis et al., 2011; Santana Tapia, 2009). These five levels have the following characteristics:

- *Level 1* is described as 'initial' processes that are still unpredictable, poorly controlled, and reactive processes.
- *Level 2* is described as 'managed'; processes are focused on projects and are often reactive.
- *Level 3* is described as 'defined.' The organization now characterizes processes and is not reactive but proactive.
- *Level 4* is described as 'quantitatively managed' in which processes are measured and controlled.
- *Level 5* is described as 'optimizing,' focusing on process improvement.

The relationship of these levels is visualized in Figure 17 Characteristics of CMMI maturity models (adapted from (Chrissis et al., 2011)).

Figure 17 Characteristics of CMMI maturity models (adapted from (Chrissis et al., 2011))

An example of a continuous maturity model with five maturity levels for IT infrastructure management looks like this (de Sousa Pereira & da Silva, 2010):

- *Level 1:* Ad-hoc, success depends on individual effort and heroics.
- *Level 2:* Resources and training are provided. Responsibilities and roles are assigned. The process is executed according to a plan and a policy. The process is controlled and monitored.
- *Level 3:* The process is documented, and all documents become assets of the organization in order to institutionalize the process so that it becomes a standard process of the organization.
- *Level 4:* Measurements, audits, reviews, and reports are provided, managed, and controlled. Quantitative objectives for quality and process performance are established and used as criteria for process management.
- *Level 5:* Continuous process improvement is enabled by quantitative feedback from processes and the pilot of innovative ideas and technology.

And an example of a staged maturity model for IT infrastructure management with five levels looks like this (de Sousa Pereira & da Silva, 2010):

- *Level 1:* Ad-hoc, success depends on individual effort and heroics.
- *Level 2:* Projects establish the foundations for an organization to become an effective service provider. This enables organizations to understand what they provide, with/for whom, and how they provide it. The focus is on customer satisfaction and organizational training.
- *Level 3:* IT service processes are documented, standardized, and integrated into standard service processes. Critical organizational processes that allow for high-performance levels in IT management are included.
- *Level 4:* Manage and control the information. Both service processes and delivery services are quantitatively understood and controlled.
- *Level 5:* Continuous process improvement is enabled by quantitative feedback from processes and the pilot of innovative ideas and technology.

The purpose of a maturity model is to provide information about an organization on how it can improve. The scientific literature defines three specific purposes for a maturity model (Serrano & Pereira, 2020). The descriptions of these three purposes are presented in Table 5 *Specific purposes of the maturity model* (adapted from (Serrano & Pereira, 2020)).

Purpose	Description
Descriptive	A maturity model can be used for an as-is situation of an organization, easing a basic assessment of the organization's capabilities. For descriptive purposes, the maturity model is used as a 'diagnostic tool.'
Prescriptive	A maturity model has a prescriptive purpose when it gives an improvement path to a higher maturity level, providing guidelines and measures to an organization.
Comparative	Comparative purpose allows an organization to benchmark its capabilities externally and internally, using a large number of historical data from the assessments of another organization.

Table 5 Specific purposes of the maturity model (adapted from (Serrano & Pereira, 2020))

In his dissertation, Santana Tapia (Santana Tapia, 2009) argues that maturity models are descriptive because they describe, in a sense, the characteristics or processes that distinguish an organization at a specific maturity level. He also stated that the maturity model is not prescriptive because it does not tell an organization how to improve. The purpose of a maturity model is to define the 'What' and not the 'How.'

According to Lasrado et al. (Lasrado et al., 2015), most maturity models in information technology can be described by a generic structure. This generic structure is visualized in Figure 18 General representation of a maturity model structure (adapted from (Lasrado et al., 2015)). This generic model shows that a maturity model consists not only of levels but also of dimensions. A dimension or sub-dimensions in the model represents a specific aspect of maturity. These dimensions provide a structured framework for organizations to assess their current capabilities and identify areas for improvement. Organizations can better

understand their strengths and weaknesses by evaluating their capabilities in these dimensions and developing a roadmap to improve their maturity level (Proença & Borbinha, 2016). This thesis uses the term dimensions because a dimension represents the same purpose as a capability: to improve a specific aspect of maturity.

Figure 18 General representation of a maturity model structure (adapted from (Lasrado et al., 2015))

2.4 Overview of the Maturity Model Related to IT Infrastructure Automation

This section provides an overview of the maturity models related to IT infrastructure automation. These models are selected during the literature review. The methodology for conducting the literature review is described in detail in Section 3.3. In Table 6 an overview of the related maturity models is presented.

Maturity Model	Reference	Number of Maturity Levels
IT Infrastructure Maturity Model (ITI-MM)	(Haris, 2010)	1 - 5
Maturity Model for IT Management	(Becker et al., 2009)	0 - 5
Gartner IT Infrastructure and Operations Maturity Model	(Scott et al., 2007)	1 – 6
The Gartner Infrastructure Maturity Model.	(Hidas, 2006)	1 - 6
Maturity Model for Implementing ITIL v3	(de Sousa Pereira & da Silva, 2010)	1 – 5
Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model	(Greene, Parker, & Perry, 2017)	1 - 5
Cisco Network Automation Maturity	(Pinto & Lacunza, 2021)	1 - 5
Cloud Maturity Model	(Dijk, 2017)	1 – 5
DevOps Maturity Model	(Radstaak, 2019)	1 - 5
Open Group Service Integration Maturity Model	(Group, 2009)	1 – 7
Netbrain Network Automation Maturity Model	(Netbrain, 2022)	0 - 4
Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model	(Quali, 2021)	1 – 5

Table 6 Overview-related maturity models (created by the researcher)

For a maturity model to be related, the characteristics of the model must meet at least two or more of the following requirements:

- *IT Infrastructure*, the maturity model describes an improvement path for IT infrastructure building blocks.
- *Cloud Infrastructure*, the maturity model, describes an improvement path for cloud services and delivery models.
- *Software development approach*, the maturity model describes an improvement path for automated software/application delivery and deployment workflows.
- *IT management*, the maturity model describes an improvement path for IT management. The improvement path includes at least a dimension of processes, humans, or technology.
- *IT (infrastructure) Automation*, the maturity model describes an improvement path for automation. This improvement path includes at least a dimension on manual or automated tasks.

In Table 7 an overview of the related maturity models and the requirements they fulfill is presented.

Maturity Model	Infrastructure	Cloud	Software Development	IT management	Automation
IT Infrastructure Maturity Model (ITI-MM)	✓			✓	✓
Maturity Model for IT Management				✓	✓
Gartner IT Infrastructure and Operations Maturity Model	✓			✓	
The Gartner Infrastructure Maturity Model.	✓			✓	✓
Maturity Model for Implementing ITIL v3	✓			✓	
Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model	✓			✓	✓
Cisco Network Automation Maturity	✓	✓		✓	✓
Cloud Maturity Model	✓	✓			✓
DevOps Maturity Model		✓	✓		✓
Open Group Service Integration Maturity Model	✓			✓	
Netbrain Network Automation Maturity Model	✓		✓		✓
Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 7 Related maturity model and the requirements they fulfill (created by the researcher)

In the following subsections, these maturity models are briefly described.

2.4.1 IT Infrastructure Maturity Model (ITI-MM)

The IT infrastructure maturity model (ITI-MM) (Haris, 2010) describes a step-by-step roadmap to mature a flexible IT infrastructure. It is a vendor-agnostic roadmap. The focus of this roadmap is on technology and human aspects. The model covers five levels, from basic to innovative, and twelve dimensions. A descriptive overview of all levels is given in Figure 19 IT Infrastructure Maturity Model (ITI-MM) (adapted from (Haris, 2010)). The ITI-MM model is used in a real-life context and is easily understood by several experts. For time reference, the model is developed for a more traditional IT infrastructure. Although the introduction of the cloud infrastructure started, it did not incorporate the cloud service and delivery models.

Dimensions are described in more detail Table 8 Dimensions of ITI-MM (adapted from (Haris, 2010)). However, the ITI-MM model lacks quantitative key performance indicators for every dimension. This lack prevents the use of this model to assess an IT infrastructure better.

Domains	Descriptions
Infrastructure Management	This <i>domain</i> describes the overall or general IT infrastructure management style and directions being performed.
Knowledge	This <i>domain</i> represents the level of knowledge sharing and management on IT infrastructure and its respective processes.
Infrastructure Provisioning	This <i>domain</i> describes how IT infrastructure is provisioned, both by business and IT organizations.
Service Management	This <i>domain</i> represents the service management level of an IT organization.
Solution Driver	This <i>domain</i> describes the drivers that trigger an infrastructure being provisioned in the first place.
Management Focus	This <i>domain</i> represents the focus of the IT infrastructure management team.
Organization	This <i>domain</i> represents IT infrastructure’s managing organization or ownership.
Agility	This <i>domain</i> represents how quick IT infrastructure can adapt to changes.
Pricing Scheme	This <i>domain</i> describes the scheme of pricing structure offered by the IT infrastructure service provider.
Business Interface	This <i>domain</i> describes the Service Level Agreement (SLA) offered by IT infrastructure service provider related to the Quality of Service (QoS) promised.
Utilization	This <i>domain</i> represents the extend level of how IT infrastructure resources is being utilized.
Automation and Process Management	This <i>domain</i> represents the level of automation and process management within an IT organization.

Table 8 Dimensions of ITI-MM (adapted from (Haris, 2010))

Figure 19 IT Infrastructure Maturity Model (ITI-MM) (adapted from (Haris, 2010))

2.4.2 Maturity Model for IT Management

The Maturity Model for IT management (Becker et al., 2009) is based on other maturity models. The maturity model presented in Figure 20 is developed with the research procedures of Becker et al. This model provides an improvement path for measuring IT performance in the field of IT management. The model contains six levels, from nonexistent performance measurement to fully automated and integrated performance management. The models cover three dimensions, namely contents, organization, and technology. Each dimension can be assessed by five criteria, in which the dimension contents describe the relevant measures to be applied for IT management. The dimension organization looks at the IT management integration in the organization, and the dimension technology examines the supporting components.

Master Thesis - IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM)

Figure 20 The IT management maturity model (adapted from (Becker et al., 2009))

2.4.3 Gartner IT Infrastructure and Operations Maturity Model

The IT infrastructure and Operations Maturity Model from consulting firm Gartner (Scott et al., 2007) aim to improve the Business IT alignment over time. The model describes five levels, from little to no focus on IT infrastructure and operations to a trusted partner for business to increase value. For many organizations, the level required to reach is level four. Level four has a maturity level that supports a business IT alignment that supports business priorities and competitive IT services. With the increase of every maturity level, there is a substantially higher business value. A descriptive overview of this model is given in Figure 21. The model incorporates four dimensions to assess maturity: people, process, technology, and business management. Every dimension can be measured with the performance of several sub-dimensions; see Table 9 Overview of dimensions and sub-dimensions (adapted from (Scott et al., 2007)). The model is developed at a moment in time when the cloud infrastructure does not exist. Therefore, the model lacks the support to assess cloud services and delivery models.

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions
People	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization • Roles • Culture • Training • Metrics
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus • Standards • Integration • Metrics
Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard • Efficiency

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agility • Service Quality • Tools
Business Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning • Financial Management • Metrics • Governance • Sourcing • Project Management

Table 9 Overview of dimensions and sub-dimensions (adapted from (Scott et al., 2007))

	Survival	Awareness	Committed	Proactive	Service-Aligned	Business Partnership
People	No organizational focus on IT infrastructure and operations	Defined, technology-centric organization for IT infrastructure and operations	Technology-centric organization; investment in IT service desk function and staff	Process-centric organization, defined governance structure	Customer- and business-focused, IT service and delivery centric organization, formal governance	Business optimization and entrepreneurial focused culture
Process	No formal IT processes for IT infrastructure and operations	Ad hoc, but aware that processes are necessary; dependent on tools to implement de facto processes	Defined processes for IT service support and project management	Repeatable and individually automated; focus on IT service delivery-related IT processes	Integrated, automated and extended beyond I&O; focus on all service and business management processes	Dynamic optimization of IT services, implement processes fostering business innovation
Technology	No formal strategy or execution on technology investments	Basic management tools; no formal infrastructure hardware or software standards	IT support and project-related management tools; desktop hardware/software standards defined; begin infrastructure standardization/rationalization	Formal infrastructure standards and policies; process and domain-centric management tools; virtualization foundation in place	Formal IT management process/tools architecture; shared services; aggregated capacity management	Proactively promoting new technologies and impact to business; real-time infrastructure
Business Management	No formal IT business management functions	Very little outside of budgeting	Project management office	Financial management, formal key performance indicators	IT service cost metrics, competitiveness	Business contribution metrics
Level:	0	1	2	3	4	5

Figure 21 The levels of Gartner's I&O Maturity Model (adapted from (Scott et al., 2007))

2.4.4 The Gartner Infrastructure Maturity Model.

The Infrastructure Maturity Model of the consulting firm Gartner (Hidas, 2006) aims to improve the maturity of the IT infrastructure building blocks toward a real-time IT infrastructure. A real-time IT infrastructure is, according to Gartner, an infrastructure that provides shared services to the business. Business policies drive these services and automatically configure the IT infrastructure. This description of an IT infrastructure looks like the description of a cloud infrastructure. This model is also developed at a moment in time when the cloud infrastructure does not exist, but it already incorporates the ideas behind the cloud. The model consists of six levels and seven dimensions; see Figure 22.

	Basic <i>Uncoordinated infrastructure</i>	Standardized <i>Standard resources, configurations</i>	Rationalized <i>Consolidate to fewer</i>	Virtualized <i>Infrastructure resources pooled</i>	Service-Based <i>Services managed holistically</i>	Policy/Value-Based <i>Dynamic optimization to meet SLAs</i>
Objective	React	Reduce complexity	Economies of scale	Flexibility, reduce costs	Service-level delivery	Business agility
Ability to Change	Months to weeks	Weeks	Weeks to days	Weeks to minutes	Minutes	Minutes to seconds
Pricing Scheme	None, ad hoc	Fixed costs	Reduced, fixed costs	Fixed shared costs	Variable usage costs	Variable business costs
Business Interface	No SLAs	Class-of-service SLAs	Class-of-service SLAs	Flexible SLAs	End-to-end SLAs	Business SLAs
Resource Utilization	Unknown	Known	Rationalized	Shared pools	Service-based pools	Policy-based sharing
Organization	None	Central control	Consolidated	Pooled ownership	Service-oriented	Business-oriented
IT Management Processes	Chaotic — Reactive Ad hoc	Reactive — Proactive Life cycle management	Proactive Mature problem management	Proactive Prediction, dynamic capacity	Service End-to-end service management	Value Policy management

Figure 22 The Gartner Infrastructure maturity model (adapted from (Hidas, 2006))

The model describes a roadmap from a basic IT infrastructure, which is very ad hoc and reactive, via a virtualized infrastructure where the IT management is proactive toward a real-time infrastructure. The aspects in the model are derived from the Gartner IT infrastructure and Operations Maturity Mode (see Section 2.6.3). To achieve the different maturity levels, the model uses the dimensions of people, processes, and technologies. How these dimensions support the roadmap for improvement is per dimension described in Table 9.

	<i>People</i>	<i>Process</i>	<i>Technology</i>
Standardized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IT owns assets Processes, tools are shared 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Infrastructure life cycle standards Basic SLAs Event management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standard configurations Tools to monitor assets
Rationalized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organization structure and ownership rationalized across IT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mature and integrated systems management processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated systems management tools Consolidated assets
Virtualized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organization aligned to pooled asset usage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Holistic capacity management Flexible chargeback 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Servers, storage, network capacity is virtualized
Service-Based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IT organization aligned to service delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measure, report, guarantee end-to-end services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service management tools manage end-to-end
Real-Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IT proactively influences use of technology to drive business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End-to-end services are centrally managed and balanced 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The business has direct interface to service prioritization

Figure 23 Gartner Infrastructure Mature through People, Process, and Technology (adapted from (Hidas, 2006))

2.4.5 Maturity Model for Implementing ITIL v3

The Maturity Model for ITIL¹ v3 (de Sousa Pereira & da Silva, 2010) describes an improvement path for ITIL processes. Examples of ITIL processes are incident management, configuration management, problem management, change management, security management, service level management, and more. The model contains four levels and fourteen dimensions; see Figure 24.

ITIL processes	Stage Model Maturity Level	Continuous Model Maturity Levels			
		Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Service Catalogue Management	2				
Service Level Management					
Supplier Management					
Service Asset & Configuration Management					
Event Management					
Incident Management					
Request Fulfillment					
Monitoring & Control					
Service Desk					
Technical Management					
Service Generation	3				
Demand Management					
IT Financial Management					
Service Portfolio Management					
Capacity Management					
Availability Management					
IT Service Continuity Management					
Transition Plan & Support					
Change Management					
Release & Deployment Management					
Service Validation & Testing					
Problem Management					
Access Management					
Application Management					
Information Security Management	4				
Evaluation					
Knowledge Management					
Service Report					
Service Measurement	5				
Service Improvement					

Figure 24 Maturity model for implementing ITL v3 (adapted from (de Sousa Pereira & da Silva, 2010))

The dimensions are all the management processes as defined by ITIL v3. Details of the different ITIL processes are needed for a good assessment of an organization. Therefore, a good understanding of ITIL is required to use this model. The model is built around the two types of improvement paths for a maturity model. Organizations that do not know how to implement the different ITIL processes can use the staged improvement path. If an organization already has some processes in place, then the continuous improvement path can be used.

2.4.6 Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model

The Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model (Greene et al., 2017) provides an improvement path from traditional to digital-ready networks. A network is one of the building blocks of an IT infrastructure that provides communication and data transport. In Figure 25 the characteristics of the traditional network and the digital ready network are shown.

¹ Information Technology Infrastructure Library is a framework for managing IT services. (<https://www.itlibrary.org/>)

Figure 25 Transformation from a traditional network to a digital-ready network (adapted from (Montanez, 2020))

The model contains five levels from best effort towards self-driving. Self-driving stands for continuously and automatically adapting the changes needed for the business. The model is shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26 Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model (adapted from (Greene et al., 2017))

The five dimensions of this model contribute to readiness at every level. The dimension architecture defines the approaches to enhancing the network architecture, life cycle, governance, and compliance. Automation is the ability to reduce manual tasks. When the security dimension improves, the risk is reduced, and the compliance requirements are met. Therefore, a security policy must be defined. Service assurance is the ability to continuously align with the application's growth, supporting the business's demands. The fifth-dimension analytics provides the necessary information for valuable insight into the network's operation and management. The lack of this model is due to the lack of descriptions for levels two, three, and four. Therefore, assessing a network with the help of this model is challenging.

2.4.7 Cisco Network Automation Maturity

The Cisco Network Automation Maturity model (Pinto & Lacunza, 2021) describes a roadmap for automated deployment, configuration, and testing/validation of network components. The automated processes of this network automation maturity model involve both types of IT infrastructure. Network automation also includes the day-n life cycle management of components. This maturity model contains five levels, from manual

configuration to automatic provisioning, and has only one dimension, the automation dimension. The levels are:

1. *Manual device configuration.* The network still relies on manual provisioning and configuration.
2. *Basic configuration automation.* There are some basic configuration automation and advanced service provisioning.
3. *Automated provisioning based on the controller per domain.* There is controller-based automation in one or more network domains that allow secure, scalable, and consistent day 0 and day 1 provisioning.
4. *Controller-based, network-wide automated provisioning.* There is already controller-based automation across the network for policy-based day 0 and day 1 provisioning and configuration, delivered consistently by the cloud delivery models.
5. *Automated provisioning of devices in a self-organized, self-diagnosing, and dynamically updated network.* The network has advanced self-optimization capabilities.

2.4.8 Cloud Maturity Model

The Cloud Maturity Model (Dijk, 2017) provides an improvement roadmap for cloud service models. The roadmap of this model describes the evolution of cloud infrastructure from an on-premises deployment to a fully optimized cloud (native) infrastructure for the three cloud service models, IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS. These three are the dimensions of the model. The model contains five levels and is visualized in Figure 27. Behind these three dimensions are fourteen so-called focus areas; these focus areas are called sub-dimension in this thesis. The focus areas and their origination are presented in Table 10 Consolidation of capabilities into dimensions (adapted from (Dijk, 2017)). The maturity model offers an improvement path across all levels for every focus area (dimensions).

Cloud Domain	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Infrastructure	Legacy apps on dedicated infrastructure	IaaS replacing on premise		Cloud-native infrastructure	Cloud-optimized infrastructure
Platform			PaaS development Application stack on PaaS	Redesigned applications for PaaS	Cloud-optimized PaaS
Software		Mature cloud solutions SaaS Point solutions	Secondary processes SaaS	Primary processes SaaS	Hybrid SaaS

Figure 27 Cloud maturity model (adapted from (Dijk, 2017))

Old capability areas	Literature elements	New focus area
Business Process Management	Process management	Business Process Management
Strategy; Organisational understanding		Cloud strategy
Compliance	Compliance	Compliance
Data management; Service integration and management	Integration	Data management
Cost management; Program management	Financial management	Financial
Governance	Governance	Governance
(On-premise) infrastructure; Change management; Portfolio management	Cloud service models	Infrastructure
Enterprise architecture; Program management; Service integration and management	Integration	IT architecture
Operations; Program management; Project management; Portfolio management		Operations
Change management; Service integration and management; Portfolio management	Cloud service models	Platform
Security management; Risk management	Security	Security
Change management; Service integration and management; Portfolio management	Cloud service models	Software
Software development; Agile		Software Development
Vendor management	SLA management	Vendor management

Table 10 Consolidation of capabilities into dimensions (adapted from (Dijk, 2017))

2.4.9 DevOps Maturity Model

The DevOps Maturity Model (Radstaak, 2019) provides an improvement path for software development. With the infrastructure model (see Figure 10), the software development is placed in the development block of the application platform. The term DevOps stands for development and operations. This maturity model contains five levels, which are based on CMMI; the levels are:

- *Initial*, software development teams are isolated and organized around one specific skill set. There is no automation for software delivery. Documentation and configuration are saved per project and are not consistent.
- *Managed*, software development teams are still independent and structured to short-term deliverables. Software delivery processes are scheduled, and the support

environment is partially automated. The deployment is partially automated. Documentation and configuration are up-to-date.

- *Define*, the software development team. The teams are structured around projects and their processes to facilitate collaboration between teams. The delivery process is standardized and automated. There is a basic deployment through a pipeline. Documentation and configuration are regularly validated.
- *Measured*, software teams are structured around whole products. Software delivery and deployment are automated. The documentation is updated with the gathered experience and quality requirements.
- *Optimized*, the software teams are cross-functional and interdisciplinary. The software delivery and deployment are optimized for a maximum throughput of releases. Documentation and configuration are automated and generated.

There are five dimensions in the DevOps maturity model: communication and collaboration, measurement, monitoring, automation, and culture. These dimensions represent how DevOps is achieved. Each dimension has several sub-dimensions. Figure 28 presents a high-level overview of this model.

Figure 28 High-level DevOps maturity model (adapted from (Radstaak, 2019))

2.4.10 Open Group Service Integration Maturity Model

The Open Group Service Integration Maturity Model (OSIMM) (Group, 2009) provides an improvement path for service integration levels for an organization, IT systems, and business applications. This model consists of seven levels, which are as follows:

1. *Silo*, Individual parts of the organization are developing their own software independently, without integrating data, processes, standards, or technologies.
2. *Integrated*, technologies have been put in place to communicate between the silos and to integrate the data and interconnections. Constructing an IT system that integrates across different parts of the organization is possible.
3. *Componentized*, the IT systems in the silos have been analyzed and broken down into component parts, with a framework in which they can be developed into new

configurations and systems. Although components interact through defined interfaces, they are not loosely coupled, which limits agility and interoperability between different segments of the organization.

4. *Service*, composite applications are built from loosely-coupled services. Services run on an IT infrastructure supported by appropriate protocols, security mechanisms, data transformation, and service management capabilities. The way in which services may be invoked is based on open standards and is independent of the underlying application technology.
5. *Composite Services*, at this level of service maturity, it is now possible to construct a business process for a set of interacting services, not just by bespoke development but by using a composition or business process modeling language of information and control through the individual services. Composite services include static, process, and activity-based services.
6. *Virtualized services*, business, and IT services are now provided through a façade – a level of indirection. The service consumer does not invoke the service directly but rather by invoking a 'virtual service.' The virtual service becomes loosely coupled with the infrastructure on which it is running, allowing more opportunities for the composition of services.
7. *Dynamically Re-Configurable Services*, prior to this level, the business process assembly, although agile, is performed at design time by developers (under the guidance of business analysis and product managers) using suitable tooling. Now this assembly may be performed at runtime, either assisted by the business analysts via suitable tooling or by the system itself.

These maturity levels can be assessed by the following dimensions, business, organization and governance, method, application, architecture, information, and infrastructure and services. The dimensions of infrastructure and services are relevant to this thesis. Because it addresses the IT infrastructure, service management, IT operations, IT management, and service level agreements. An overview of the model is shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29 Open Group Service Integration Maturity Model (adapted from (Group, 2009))

2.4.11 Netbrain Network Automation Maturity Model

The Netbrain Network Automation Maturity Model (Netbrain, 2022) provides an improvement path process of automated deployment, configuration, and testing/validation. The maturity model shows that the operational overhead decreases as automation increases. A measure of automation maturity, according to Netbrain, is the Mean-Time-To-Repair (MTTR). In Figure 30 Network Automation Maturity Model (adapted from (Netbrain, 2022)), the positive advantage of automation is the difference between the two curves.

Figure 30 Network Automation Maturity Model (adapted from (Netbrain, 2022))

The maturity model addresses only dimension automation, with five maturity levels.

2.4.12 Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model

The Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (Quali, 2021) is an improvement path for the IT infrastructure created by a vendor. The main driver behind this model is the adaptation of the DevOps approach in the IT infrastructure. The maturity model is designed around the infrastructure management lifecycle, see Figure 31. The lifetime of an IT infrastructure is influenced by several factors for the business to provide several business deliverables.

Figure 31 IT infrastructure automation lifecycle (adapted from (Quali, 2021))

The maturity model has four dimensions: culture, people, process, and technology. Each dimension has an improvement path of five levels, from ad-hoc to self-defining. The levels can be briefly described as follows:

1. *Ad-hoc*, the IT infrastructure is a mix of old and new technology. IT teams are highly siloed with skills focused on domains. Provisioning is accomplished by using multiple methods. Changes take time.
2. *Automated*, the IT infrastructure remains a mix of old and new technology. However, the cloud infrastructure has been adopted. DevOps is emerging with the IT infrastructure.
3. *Frictionless*, optimization is the key initiative. There is a need to standardize, reduce complexity, and create insight to understand DevOps activities. There are still challenges to the management of the IT infrastructure. The IT infrastructure is still too complex and is managed with too many tools.
4. *Lifecycle*, the IT infrastructure is managed holistically and end-to-end and entirely according to the DevOps approach. In addition, governance, security, and change control practices are in place.
5. *Self-defining*, IT infrastructure management is a high-scale, end-to-end environment actively supported and enhanced by software delivery.

The description of the different levels and dimensions is shown in Figure 32.

	Infrastructure Level 1 AD-HOC	Infrastructure Level 2 AUTOMATED	Infrastructure Level 3 FRICITIONLESS
CULTURE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Uncommunicated objectives · Infrastructure assumed · Blind to complexity and cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Reduce complexity · Reduce execution time · Remove manual activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Self-service without risk · Increasing workloads · Change instances managed
PROCESS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Skilled practitioners · Domain/function focus · Measured against activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Highly-skilled practitioners · Teams with broader functions · Measured against throughput 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Skills focused where needed · Skills optimized and leveraged · Measured against productivity
PEOPLE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Project to product · Manual activities · Manual create & configure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · DevOps/shift-left established · Mixed/Hybrid Clouds · Silo process activity delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · DevOps scaled and optimized · Full stack process managed · End-to-end process visibility
TECHNOLOGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Script-based tooling · Manual activities · Non-integrated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Sophisticated/custom · Team automation & Integration · Tools choice freedom 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Low/no touch requirement · Infrastructure agnostic at scale · Intuitive simple UX
	Infrastructure Level 4 LIFECYCLE		Infrastructure Level 5 SELF-DEFINING
CULTURE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Governance required · Accountability measured · End-to-end change managed 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Costs managed · Business outcome measured · Complete observability
PROCESS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Cross-team prioritization · Cross-team optimization · Measured against outputs 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Business-driven contribution · Cross-team business priorities · Measured against outcomes
PEOPLE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · DevSec Ops & Dev Value Streams · End-to-end execution & visibility · Infra. & DevOps infra. lifecycle mgt. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Business Value Streams · End-to-end value context · Seamless DevOps/infra process
TECHNOLOGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · End-to-end management platform · Integrated/automated change · End-to-end change & risk mgd. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Dynamic lifecycle · Intelligent predictive change · Single source of truth

Figure 32 IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (adapted from (Quali, 2021))

2.5 Summary

The theoretical framework of this thesis consists of three concepts. The first concept introduced is IT infrastructure, where the two types of infrastructure are explained. The first type is traditional infrastructure, and the second is cloud infrastructure. The positive influence of humans, processes, and technology is introduced for operations and management.

The next concept is automation. Automation is a broad concept. This thesis defines automation as using software and scripts to execute repeatable tasks and reduce human interaction.

The latest concept introduced is about maturity models, which provides a roadmap for organizations to describe the necessary steps to achieve a more mature improvement and means to measure progress. An overview of the twelve maturity models related to IT infrastructure automation is provided.

3 Research Design and Approach

This chapter discusses the overall design of the research and provides an overview of the reasoning behind the selection of the research methods. It also provides information on the research methods used and explains the conceptual framework, scope of the research, the research method, and the research approach. Furthermore, the structure of the literature research is described.

3.1 Research Design and Approach

The research design consists of two research paradigms: Design Science Research and the Delphi Method. This section will introduce both methods and explain why these paradigms were chosen.

3.1.1 Design Science Research

Design Science Research (DSR) is a research paradigm that aims to create and validate innovative and effective solutions to practical problems (Alarabiat & Ramos, 2019; Massaroli, Martini, Lino, Spenassato, & Massaroli, 2018; Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004). DSR involves a systematic approach to designing, developing, and evaluating artifacts, such as software applications, information systems, and processes. DSR is also a research paradigm that combines rigor and practical information to create innovative and effective solutions to practical problems. As mentioned in the books, 'Scientific Research in Information Systems' (Recker, 2021) and 'Design Research in Information Systems' (Hevner & Chatterjee, 2010), the main paradigm behind DSR is understanding a design problem in their environment and finding the solution while creating the artifact. This research approach emphasizes the importance of combining rigor and practical knowledge to ensure the relevance and usefulness of the artifacts created (Vom Brocke et al., 2020).

DSR follows a cyclical process that includes three main cycles: the relevance cycle, the design cycle, and the rigor cycle (Vom Brocke et al., 2020). The relevance cycle aims to identify and understand a practical problem and determine its relevance to research. The design cycle involves creating and testing a prototype artifact that is iteratively refined based on subject matter expert feedback. Finally, the rigor cycle evaluates the effectiveness of the artifact and refines the design principles used.

The three cycles of DSR are crucial to creating and validating artifacts. The conceptual DSR framework, presented in Figure 33 Design Research Framework (adapted from (Hevner & Chatterjee, 2010)), shows the three cycles and their relations. This conceptual framework combines the real world, called the environment, and the practice and scientific theory, called the knowledge base. The environment consists of the problem space in which the research problem is defined. The knowledge base provides the foundational theories, frameworks, methods, and constructs to build the theoretical base for the research.

The motivation to use DSR as a research method is based on the following factors:

- The main goal of this research is to attempt to create a new practical artifact for a real-world problem using a scientific approach. The DSR research paradigm supports this goal.
- For the creation of this artifact, knowledge is needed from best practices, scientific theory, practitioner experience, and knowledgeable experts. The key feature of DSR is the combination of rigor and practical information, which supports this functional requirement.
- The process of creating this artifact is not linear but iterative. It requires solid design techniques and interaction with professionals and experts, and it is a creative process. DSR is a cyclical process and supports the iterative approach needed for the development of the artifact.

The environment and the knowledge base are bridged together with two cycles, these are:

1. The **Relevance Cycle** ensures the 'research problem' is clearly and precisely defined. This cycle bridged the environment context with the iterative design science research steps.
2. The **Rigor Cycle** connects the knowledge base with the design science research steps. In this way, there is an iterative coupling during the research with the scientific literature, best practices, experiences, and expertise used during the research. This research study conducts a literature study to ensure the theoretical basis for creating the artifact described in Section 3.3, Literature Review.

Figure 33 Design Research Framework (adapted from (Hevner & Chatterjee, 2010))

The framework contains a third cycle, the **Design Cycle**. The design cycle is a crucial part of DSR, enabling researchers to create a prototype artifact that can be iteratively refined based on feedback from subject matter experts. The Design Cycle is executed in collaboration with the Delphi method (Turoff & Linstone, 2002) to ensure the creation of an artifact based on rigor and practical information. The Delphi method is a structured communication technique that involves multiple rounds of expert feedback and consensus building. This method is particularly suited to DSR, as it supports the creation of artifacts that are

grounded in best practices and validated by experts in the field. The Delphi method is explained in more detail in the next section.

3.1.2 Delphi Method

The Delphi method is a structured communication technique that is widely used in various fields, including social sciences, business, and engineering (Turoff & Linstone, 2002). This method involves multiple rounds of expert feedback and consensus building to identify best practices in a particular field. The Delphi method is particularly useful when dealing with complex and uncertain problems, where experts' opinions can provide valuable insights and perspectives (Hsu & Sandford, 2007).

The Delphi method typically involves several rounds to get a consensus about a topic, with each round providing participant feedback and insights. The results of each round are analyzed and summarized. Participants, who generally are subject matter experts in the field, remain anonymous throughout the process, which helps to eliminate bias and promote honest feedback. The selection of the subject matter experts is an essential step in the method. Subject matter experts can be involved in the next round to have the opportunity to review their earlier responses and provide feedback. The process continues until a consensus is reached or a predetermined endpoint is reached (Alarabiat & Ramos, 2019; Hsu & Sandford, 2007).

The Delphi method offers several strengths that make it a valuable research technique. One of its primary strengths is its ability to gather subject matter expert opinions and insights while minimizing bias and groupthink. By allowing experts to remain anonymous and providing multiple rounds of feedback, the Delphi method enables experts to provide honest and independent assessments, which can be critical for decision-making and problem-solving (Avella, 2016; Hsu & Sandford, 2007; Turoff & Linstone, 2002).

Another strength of the Delphi method is its flexibility and adaptability to different research contexts. The method can be used in various fields, from healthcare and education to technology and business. Its iterative and collaborative approach allows researchers to adjust their research questions or objectives based on feedback received in each round, making it an effective method for exploring complex and uncertain problems (Avella, 2016; Hsu & Sandford, 2007; Turoff & Linstone, 2002).

The Delphi method also offers a cost-effective and efficient approach to data collection, as it can be carried out remotely and does not require face-to-face meetings or extensive travel. This makes it a practical method for collecting data from experts who are located in different regions or countries (Avella, 2016; Belton, MacDonald, Wright, & Hamlin, 2019; Turoff & Linstone, 2002).

Finally, the Delphi method provides a systematic approach to gathering and analyzing data, enhancing research findings' rigor and validity. The structured and iterative nature of the method ensures that data are collected and analyzed consistently and reliably, reducing the potential for errors or biases (Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004; Turoff & Linstone, 2002).

The mentioned strengths are the motivation to choose the Delphi method in the Design Cycle of DSR. Additionally, using the Delphi method in the Design Cycle enables the creation of artifacts based on rigor and practices validated by field experts.

3.2 Research Approach

To carry out design science research, vom Brocke et al. (Vom Brocke et al., 2020) created a research process model. This process model consists of six steps: problem identification and motivation, the definition of the objectives for a solution, design and development, demonstration, evaluation, and communication; and four possible entry points: problem-centered initiation, objective-centered solution, design, and development-centered initiation, and client/context initiation; see Figure 34 DSR methodology process model (adapted from (Vom Brocke et al., 2020)).

As a starting point for this research, the Design & Development process is chosen. By starting at this process, all relevant rigor and practice necessary is collected during the iterations in the artifact's creation. The main activities of this study are around the creation of an artifact. But to create the artifact, according to Hevner et al. (Hevner & Chatterjee, 2010), all of the ingredients are needed to be in place. Therefore, the processes 'Identify Problem & Motivation' and 'Define Objective of a Solution' are part of this research. The other processes are not part of this research because they do not provide the necessary ingredients. The three processes are outlined in the different chapters:

- The "Identify Problem & Motivation" process defines the research problem, and the justification of the solution's value is determined; see Chapter 1.
- The "Define Objective of a Solution" process is where an objective of a solution can be inferred from the available knowledge and explored of what is possible and feasible; see Chapter 4 and Chapter 5.
- And the "Design & Development" process is where the artifact is created; see Chapter 6.

Figure 34 DSR methodology process model (adapted from (Vom Brocke et al., 2020))

3.2.1 Mapping Research Questions to Research Methods

As mentioned above, DSR is an iterative method with different iterative cycles. As a result, the research method can differ during DSR activities. The different research questions are mapped to the appropriate research method to answer each question. Table 11 Mapping the research questions to the research shows the methods used to try to answer them.

	Research Question	Research Methods	Data Collection Method
RQ01	<i>What is an IT infrastructure?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the literature • Delphi together with qualitative analysis methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Literature Review • Expert Panel – Interview • Digital Survey
RQ02	<i>What is IT infrastructure automation?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the literature • Delphi together with qualitative analysis methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Literature Review • Expert Panel – Interview • Digital Survey
RQ03	<i>What models of IT infrastructure automation maturity are available in the current scientific literature?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the literature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Literature Review
RQ04	<i>How can these attributes be ordered over different maturity stages as part of a maturity model for IT Infrastructure automation?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design Science Research Combined with • Delphi Method and Qualitative Analyses Methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Literature Review • Expert Panel – Interview • Digital Survey
RQ05	<i>What are the useful attributes for each of these dimensions?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design Science Research Combined with • Delphi Method and Qualitative Analyses Methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Literature Review • Expert Panel – Interview • Digital Survey

Table 11 Mapping the research questions to the research methods (created by the researcher)

3.2.2 Conceptual Model

Conceptual models are a vital component of research design, providing a theoretical framework for understanding and analyzing complex phenomena. According to Recker (Recker, 2021), a conceptual model is a simplified representation of a complex reality that captures the essential elements and relationships among them. One of the key concepts in conceptual modeling is abstraction, which involves simplifying complex phenomena by focusing on the essential elements and the relationships among them. This abstraction enables researchers to develop a clear and concise representation of the phenomenon under study.

The conceptual model for this research is shown in Figure 35 Overall Conceptual Framework. The conceptual model is based on a conceptual framework of the flexibility of the IT infrastructure (Anwar & Masrek, 2014). That model defines which concepts influence an IT infrastructure. The conceptual model for this research explains that three relationships influence the IT infrastructure. IT infrastructure is defined as an independent variable. The dependent variable is the maturity level; this variable needs to be observed to determine the effect of the independent variable. Automation is the moderator variable influencing the relationship between independent and dependent variables. In this case, it influences the maturity of the IT infrastructure.

Figure 35 Overall Conceptual Framework (created by the researcher)

One of the key concepts in conceptual modeling is abstraction, which involves simplifying complex phenomena by focusing on the essential elements and the relationships among them. This abstraction enables researchers to develop a clear and concise representation of the phenomenon under study. Based on this overall conceptual framework, a more abstract model can be defined; see Figure 36 Conceptual Framework. In this more abstract model, the maturity of the IT infrastructure is seen as one concept and is the dependent variable. Automation, on the other hand, is the independent variable; the way automation is present or implemented says something about maturity. This conceptual model shows that this research investigates only the relation or influence of automation on the maturity of an IT infrastructure. In general, the research study concerns the maturity of automation in IT infrastructure.

Figure 36 Conceptual Framework (created by the researcher)

Additionally, experts are often invited to participate in the research to refine further and test the conceptual model. Their insights and perspectives on the phenomenon are used to identify gaps in existing knowledge and highlight areas where further research is needed.

3.2.3 Research Scope

In the theoretical foundation for this research, see Chapter 2, the IT infrastructure is presented as a model that consists of different building blocks (Laan, 2017). Within the IT infrastructure model, there is a separate building block for infrastructure management. It is within this building block that automation of the IT infrastructure takes place. The maturity of the IT infrastructure is influenced by the maturity of the IT infrastructure management (Serrano & Pereira, 2020).

To limit and scope our research, the artifact created aims only at a maturity level of automation of the IT infrastructure management building block. This is visualized in Figure 37 Scope of the research in the context of the IT infrastructure.

Figure 37 Scope of the research in the context of the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher)

3.2.4 Applied Research Approach

Based on the information in the previous section, the research approach can be visualized in the conceptual research framework, shown in Figure 38 The conceptual research framework of this thesis.

Figure 38 The conceptual research framework of this thesis (created by the researcher)

In this model, the environment contains the topics that are part of this research. To create the right artifact, the environment must be clear and precise. The theoretical framework, see Chapter 2, shows that the IT infrastructure, automation, and IT infrastructure management topics are not ambiguous. Section 1.1, Introducing the Research Problem, also describes that there are challenges in understanding these topics. Therefore, part of this research focuses on defining the environment, not the artifact. The sub-research questions RQ01 and RQ02 address this research and aim at the topics of IT infrastructure and automation. Therefore, during the DSR iterations, data was collected to answer the main research questions to create the artifact, and data was gathered to define the environment to answer the sub-research questions.

The knowledge base contains the theoretical framework for this research. This framework is based on the literature review, as described in more detail in Section 3.3. As described, this framework's rigor cycle connects the different DSR iterations.

In the DSR design cycle, the artifact is developed and created, as described in Chapter 6 of this document. The design cycle is supported by sub-research questions RQ03, RQ04, and RQ05. The development and creation of the artifact is carried out through a total of two iterations. In the first iteration, a subject matter expert panel is interviewed, while a larger group of experts is invited to participate in a digital questionnaire during the second iteration. The data collected from both iterations define the exact environment and guide the artifact's creation.

To gather the necessary data during the iteration of the design cycle, Section 3.4 provides a detailed explanation of the data-gathering methods used.

3.3 Literature Review Strategy

A literature review is conducted to create the body of knowledge that is relevant to this research. The literature review uses an iterative divergent and convergent process (see Figure 39 Divergent and Convergent). This process is described in more detail by Edzo Botjes (Botjes, 2020). The process of analyzing and synthesizing the literature is repeated several times until a comprehensive understanding of the different topics is achieved. The topics are IT infrastructure, automation, and maturity models. The divergent process is used to find and discover various sources of information such as whitepapers, reports, and case studies from vendors and industry experts. The convergent process involves the selection of sources by identifying the different topics and keywords.

Figure 39 Divergent and Convergent Process (created by the researcher)

The motivation to choose this research approach is because the theoretical framework must contain information about the topics of this research (IT infrastructure, automation, and IT infrastructure management). As pointed out in Section 1.5.2, limited literature is available in the body of knowledge about IT infrastructure and automation. Therefore, the search for relevant information is extended outside the scientific body of knowledge. The diverge and converge approach used during the research period allowed the researcher to search many sources and filter only the relevant information. These sources can be categorized into books, scientific databases, and the world wide web. The different stages of the literature review are shown in Figure 40 Literature review stages.

Figure 40 Literature review stages (created by the researcher)

The search strings used to find potential information are as follows:

- "IT Infrastructure"
- "Maturity Model"
- "IT Infrastructure" and "Maturity Model"
- "IT Infrastructure" and "Maturity"
- "Automation"
- "IT Infrastructure" and "Automation"
- "IT Infrastructure" and "Automation" and "Maturity"
- "IT Infrastructure" and "Automation" and "Maturity Model"
- "Automation" and "Levels"
- "Level of Automation"
- "Infrastructure as code" or "Infrastructure-as-Code"

The inclusion criteria for building the theoretical framework are as follows:

- Publications² must be written in English.
- Publications must be available for download.
- The title, Keywords, Abstract, and Introduction of the publication make it explicit that the publication is related to "IT Infrastructure" or "Maturity Model" or "Automation" or a combination of these three.

² The term publications is used as an aggregate for papers, whitepapers, websites and blogs.

- The publications define the concept as "IT Infrastructure" or "Maturity Model" or "Automation" or a combination of these three or adapt a definition provided by another relevant study or add specific and relevant knowledge.

The following selection criteria are used per topic to filter within the initial set and drill down to a more comprehensive collection. The following criteria are used:

- For publications about "IT Infrastructure":
 - The title, keywords, abstract, or introduction of the publication make it explicit that it contains the following:
 - IT Infrastructure
 - IT Components
 - IT Services /Processes
 - Relations between each other
- For publications about "IT Infrastructure Automation":
 - The title or keywords, or abstract, or introduction of the publication make it explicit that the publication contains the following:
 - IT Infrastructure
 - IT Components
 - Automation
 - Process elimination of human actions
- For publications about the "Maturity Model":
 - The title or keywords, or abstract, or introduction of the publication make it explicit that the publication contains the following:
 - Maturity model
- For publications about the "IT Infrastructure Maturity Model":
 - The title or keywords, or abstract, or introduction of the publication make it explicit that the publication contains the following:
 - IT Infrastructure
 - IT Components
 - Maturity Model
- For publications about the "IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model":
 - The title or keywords, or abstract, or introduction of the publication make it explicit that the publication contains the following:
 - IT Infrastructure
 - IT Components
 - Automation
 - Process elimination of human actions
 - Maturity Model

In addition to the information found in the databases, books are added to the theoretical framework. These books met the selection criteria and provided extra relevant information besides the found publications. The following books are part of the theoretical framework:

- Continuous delivery: reliable software releases through build, test, and deployment automation (Humble & Farley, 2011).
- Accelerate: The science of Lean and DevOps: Building and Scaling High Performing Technology Organisations (Humble et al., 2018).

- IT Infrastructure Architecture-Infrastructure Building Blocks and Concepts Third Edition (Laan, 2017).
- Infrastructure as code (Morris, 2020).
- Team Topologies (Skelton, Pais, & Malan, 2019).
- CMMI Guidelines for Process Integration and Product Improvement (Chrissis et al., 2011).

Based on the literature review strategy and applied criteria, ninety-six publications are selected to be incorporated into the theoretical framework. The number of publications chosen per database is shown in Figure 41 Number of publications selected per database

Figure 41 Number of publications selected per database (created by the researcher)

Several publications cover the different topics; the distribution is shown in Figure 42 Number of publications per topic.

Figure 42 Number of publications per topic (created by the researcher)

3.4 Data-gathering Techniques

This section will describe the qualitative data-gathering techniques used in this research. The techniques used are based on the Delphi method and as mentioned in a previous section, are part of the design cycle. The Delphi method is introduced in Section 3.1.2. and depends on multiple rounds to obtain a consensus among the subject matter experts (Alarabiat & Ramos, 2019). The method typically consists of two to five rounds. The total number of rounds for this research is two. This number is based on studies that concluded that a two-round Delphi method is enough to obtain consensus (Fernández-Llamazares et al., 2013; Paré, Cameron, Poba-Nzaou, & Templier, 2013; Schmalz, Spinler, & Ringbeck, 2021).

The two rounds of the Delphi method are defined as follows:

1. *Round 1 – A qualitative semi-structured interview:* To get an adequate understanding of the topics of IT infrastructure, automation, and maturity modes a subject matter expert panel is interviewed.
2. *Round 2 – A Digital Survey:* The retrieved findings from the first round are validated together with the preliminary maturity model presented by a broad group of subject matter experts.

3.4.1 Semi-structured Interview

The first Delphi round is the qualitative semi-structured interview. The essence of the interview is to capture the experts' main opinions and understandings and their common points of view. Although the Delphi method provides a structured and systematic approach to gathering initial thoughts and feedback, semi-structured interviews provide a more flexible and in-depth approach to exploring the perspectives and insights of experts (Dejonckheere & Vaughn, 2019; Kallio, Pietilä, Johnson, & Kangasniemi, 2016). This flexibility is the motivation to choose the semi-structured interview. The design and execution of the interviews are based on the structure provided by Dejonckheer et al. (Dejonckheere & Vaughn, 2019); see Table 12 Steps to design and conduct semi-structured interviews (adapted from (Dejonckheere & Vaughn, 2019)).

Steps	Tasks
1	Determining the purpose and scope of the study
2	Identifying the participant
3	Considering ethical issues
4	Planning logistical aspects
5	Developing the Interview Guide
6	Establishing trust and rapport
7	Conducting the interview
8	Memorizing and reflecting
9	Analyzing the Data
10	Demonstrating the trustworthiness of the research.
11	Presenting findings in a report paper

Table 12 Steps to design and conduct semi-structured interviews (adapted from (Dejonckheere & Vaughn, 2019))

The interviews are conducted face to face, where several subject matter experts are interviewed in person and some via digital video conferencing. The interview responses are written down by hand and summarized in a meeting report. The transcripts are anonymized to take care of the privacy of the participants. All meeting reports are available in Appendix 10.

Considering that the objective of the interview is to obtain an adequate understanding, the researcher used a qualitative analysis of meeting reports with thematic analysis (Clarke, Braun, & Hayfield, 2015). This analysis method is advised by Toma and Picioreanu (Toma & Picioreanu, 2016) and was also selected because the responses collected from the interviews were not structured. Thematic analysis is a method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within unstructured qualitative data. The method tries to capture a theme about something important in relation to the research questions. In this research, the three topics are IT infrastructure, automation, and maturity models. A framework for conducting the thematic analysis is provided by Braun et al. (Braun & Clarke, 2006); see Table 13 Framework for thematic analysis (adapted from (Braun & Clarke, 2006)).

Phase	Description of the process
1. Familiarizing yourself with your data:	Transcribing data (if necessary), reading and re-reading the data, noting down initial ideas.
2. Generating initial codes:	Coding interesting features of the data in a systematic fashion across the entire data set, collating data relevant to each code.
3. Searching for themes:	Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each potential theme.
4. Reviewing themes:	Checking if the themes work in relation to the coded extracts (Level 1) and the entire data set (Level 2), generating a thematic 'map' of the analysis.
5. Defining and naming themes:	Ongoing analysis to refine the specifics of each theme, and the overall story the analysis tells, generating clear definitions and names for each theme.
6. Producing the report:	The final opportunity for analysis. Selection of vivid, compelling extract examples, final analysis of selected extracts, relating back of the analysis to the research question and literature, producing a scholarly report of the analysis.

Table 13 Framework for thematic analysis (adapted from (Braun & Clarke, 2006)).

A homogeneous panel is needed to understand the three topics well. This panel needs to have professional experience and, at the same time, many different opinions (Toma & Picioreanu, 2016). The criteria for the selection of the subject matter experts are as follows:

- The expert must have first-hand background knowledge and experience on the topics under investigation (Alarabiat & Ramos, 2019).
- The expert is willing to allocate substantial time to participate (Alarabiat & Ramos, 2019; Avella, 2016).
- The expert panel contains experts with different backgrounds to provide different perspectives (Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004; Toma & Picioreanu, 2016).

Another important aspect of the Delphi method is the size of the expert panel. Different studies have addressed this aspect (Alarabiat & Ramos, 2019; Avella, 2016; Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004; Toma & Picioreanu, 2016). Most of these studies recommend that the size of the expert panel should be between fifteen and twenty participants.

The kind of subject matter experts needed for this research are as follows:

- *IT managers* because they are an expert at overseeing the technology operations of a business or organization. They possess a combination of technical and managerial skills to manage teams, budgets, projects, and resources to ensure efficient and effective use of technology to support business objectives.
- *Enterprise architects* because they are an expert in aligning an organization's technology strategy with its overall business goals. They have a broad understanding of business processes, systems, and technologies to design and implement integrated solutions that enable an organization to operate more effectively and efficiently.
- *IT architects* are experts in designing and overseeing the implementation of information technology solutions for businesses or organizations. They fully understand the technical infrastructure, software applications, and data systems required to support complex business processes and achieve organizational goals.

In this context, the term IT architect is a very general description. This expertise can be divided into the following professionalisms:

- *IT infrastructure architects* because they are experts in designing and implementing technology solutions that support an organization's operations. They possess a deep understanding of hardware, software, networking, and storage technologies to create and manage complex IT infrastructures that are secure, efficient, and scalable and enable the organization to meet its business objectives.
- *IT cloud architects* are experts in designing and implementing cloud-based solutions for businesses or organizations. They have a deep understanding of cloud infrastructure, platforms, and software services to optimize the use of cloud resources, improve scalability, and ensure the security and compliance of cloud-based applications and data.
- *IT network architects* are experts at designing and implementing complex network infrastructures for businesses or organizations. They possess a deep understanding of network protocols, hardware, and software to develop and optimize network architectures that support the organization's needs for reliable and secure connectivity, high availability, and efficient data transmission.
- *IT cybersecurity experts* are experts in protecting an organization's digital assets and infrastructure from cyber threats. They have a deep understanding of security technologies, risk management, compliance, and incident response to develop and implement adequate security measures that protect against cyber-attacks, data breaches, and other security risks.

This Delphi round's subject matter expert panel consists of seventeen participants and fits with the recommended size. The participant works in different economic sectors; this is important for a broad perspective on the three topics. The distribution of expertise of the

subject matter expert panel participants is visualized in Figure 43, and for by economic sector in Figure 44.

Figure 43 Distribution of professions in the panel of subject matter experts (Created by the researcher)

Figure 44 Distribution of experts in sectors of the economy (created by the researcher)

3.4.2 Digital Survey

The second round is based on a digital survey. As suggested by Toma and Piciooreanu (Toma & Piciooreanu, 2016), the survey uses a seven-point Likert scale (Joshi, Kale, Chandel, & Pal, 2015) with a neutral (midpoint) option. The advantages are that a seven-point Likert scale is the most accurate of the Likert rankings, is easy to use, and better reflects the actual opinion of the expert. Per set of questions, a participant has the opportunity to give an additional explanation.

The digital survey has been conducted via through Qualtrics³. Qualtrics is an online survey software platform that provides survey creation, distribution, and analysis tools. The participants' responses were analyzed with the platform, and a report was downloaded; see Appendix 13. The participants had two weeks to complete the survey; a reminder was sent after one week.

This digital survey's subject matter expert panel is extended with twenty-three enterprise architects working in different sectors of the economy. This extension helps overcome the participant's dropout and still has enough valid responses (Belton et al., 2019). The survey was sent to a total of forty subject matter experts, and twenty-five have taken the time to complete the survey.

³ <https://uamangementschool.eu.qualtrics.com>

The professions of the subject matter experts who completed the survey are shown in a word cloud; see Figure 46 Word cloud of the participant's professions. The distribution in sectors of the economy is shown in Figure 45 Distribution of experts from the sectors of the economy for the digital survey (created by the researcher).

Figure 45 Distribution of experts from the sectors of the economy for the digital survey (created by the researcher)

Figure 46 Word cloud of the participant's professions (created by the researcher)

3.4.3 Explorative study with a single expert

In addition to the two Delphi rounds, a single expert is asked an exploratory research question. This explorative research question is an extra potentially relevant approach and contributes to the research of essential concepts in information system research, as presented by Recker (Recker, 2021). By exploring the expert's knowledge and experiences in the field, this research question can help identify key concepts and themes central to the three topics under research. In addition, it can provide new perspectives and insights that can be used to refine existing concepts or to develop new ones. The exploratory study is conducted in between the two rounds. This research question helps the researcher identify gaps in existing research and develop further research questions that can be explored in the second round. Overall, exploratory research questions with the expert are a valuable approach to advancing knowledge in the field of information systems research. This

exploratory research is conducted with Sjaak Laan, the author of the book 'IT Infrastructure Architecture-Infrastructure Building Blocks and Concepts Third Edition' (Laan, 2017) and a well-known expert in the field. The expert is explicitly asked for his opinion to validate the first models which define the environment. As mentioned earlier, having a clearly defined environment helps in creating the artifact.

3.5 Summary

This chapter presents the research design and overall approach being employed. The overarching research paradigm is design science research. Design science research is a paradigm that combines rigor and practical information to create innovative and effective solutions to practical problems. The three cycles of design science research (relevance, rigor, and design) are crucial for the creation and validation of artifacts. For this research, it is essential to have a good understanding of the topics of IT infrastructure, automation, and their relationship. On the other hand, having a theoretical framework to ground this research in rigor is essential. The strategy for the creation of this framework is described in the literature review strategy. Using the Delphi method in the design cycle enables the researcher to create the artifact based on the rigor and practices validated by field experts. In two Delphi rounds, the necessary data will be collected.

4 Exploring IT Infrastructure, Automation, and Maturity

Automation is the common driver within IT, but also a very broad term. This chapter will explore the relationship between automation and IT infrastructure with the subject matter expert panel. The exploration is based on interviews with subject matter experts and is part of the first iterations of the design cycle. The transcripts of the interviews are thematically analyzed and followed by a discussion about the implications. The preliminary maturity model developed for IT infrastructure automation is presented at the end of this chapter.

4.1 Qualitative semi-structured interview

The qualitative semi-structured interview, described in more detail in Chapter 3, is conducted following the semi-structured interview guide (Kallio et al., 2016). As the semi-structured interview guide mentioned, a comprehensive and adequate understanding of the topics is necessary. In the journey to answer the research questions, the interviews capture the knowledge of the different subject matter experts on these topics. The topics are IT infrastructure and automation. The first objective of this interview is to collect information on the subject matter experts' perspectives regarding the IT infrastructure. Due to the significant shift from the "iron age" to the "cloud age" within IT infrastructure during the last years (H. Chris, 2021; Dijk, 2017; Morris, 2020; Musse & Alamro, 2016; Rahman, Mahdavi-Hezaveh, & Williams, 2019; Rimol, 2022), an updated and common view of IT infrastructure is needed. The second objective is to obtain the opinion of experts about automation. Automation is a broad topic in IT and covers many domains. Therefore, a good understanding of the place and function of automation in the IT infrastructure is needed. This understanding is necessary to define the environment to develop the preliminary maturity model. The last part of the interview is about the exploration to develop a maturity model. For the development, the subject matter expert's way of thinking is captured, especially on how a maturity model can be used in automation concerning the IT infrastructure.

The structure of the interview is as follows:

- The interview starts with a question introducing the research topic and briefly starting the conversation.
- The first part of the interview is to collect global and practical knowledge about the IT infrastructure and the perspectives and understanding of that IT infrastructure from the expert's viewpoint.
- The middle part of the interview is about automation. This part aims to capture experts' opinions and insight about automation in relation to IT infrastructure and if there is a difference in relation to automation for applications.
- The remaining part of the interview concerns maturity models, especially the expert's understanding of that topic, his opinion on them, and what a potential maturity model 'looks like.'

The following interview questions are defined:

1. What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?
2. Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?
3. From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?
4. Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?
5. This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?
6. From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?
7. From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?

4.2 Automation in General

As mentioned earlier, automation is a broad term (Wickens, 2018) commonly used in many parts of technology. For this research, it is necessary to have a good understanding of what automation is exactly in relation to the IT infrastructure. On the other hand, knowledge of the challenges of automation in IT infrastructure is necessary. Knowing the challenges helps to build a maturity model with a growth path for automation to overcome these challenges. The first question of the interview is to capture the automation challenges as seen by the subject matter experts.

Question 1 of the interview: What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?

The transcripts of the interviews with the subject matter experts are incorporated in Appendix 10, and the results of a first thematic analysis are in Appendix 11. A refinement of the themes for the first question is shown in the first column of Table 14 Thematic analysis of interview question 1. For every theme, the essence is described in the third column.

Refinement of themes	Themes	Essence
Manual Work	Time Cost Low pace / Low speed of change Processes Skills / Knowledge	People perform manual tasks for configuration and deployment.

Refinement of themes	Themes	Essence
Consistency	State of the system (i.e., the IT infrastructure) Error-sensitive Configuration Reproducible Compliance	There is no consistency in the configuration and compliance of all components within the IT infrastructure. It is necessary to know the state of the IT infrastructure at all times, making it possible to reproduce the IT infrastructure.
Today, the IT infrastructure is too complex.	No standardization	The IT infrastructure is a combination of different technologies, and there is no standardization between them; hence, an IT infrastructure is a complex environment.
Culture	Organization culture	Automation is a way of thinking; the intention is to automate every task.
Business IT alignment	IT aligns with Business. Business aligns with IT	A good business IT alignment needs automated, standardized processes.

Table 14 Thematic analysis of interview question 1 (created by the researcher)

4.2.1 Implications for Automation

Thematic analysis confirms that the subject matter experts agree that today's IT infrastructure is complex. Additionally, many manual tasks are still performed by people working in the IT infrastructure despite the incentive of many vendors to introduce automated tasks into their products. According to subject matter experts, the IT department struggles with automation mainly due to a lack of standardization. Based on the analysis results, an important conclusion can be drawn that there is no automation standard to integrate the different technologies of the IT infrastructure.

4.3 Exploring IT Infrastructure

The term IT infrastructure is well-known within information technology, according to some definitions (Gartner, 2022; Haerens, 2016; Laan, 2017), as a combination of components of physical information technology. In the last decade, the IT infrastructure has evolved towards cloud computing (Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016). For this research, it is crucial to understand how that evolution impacted the view and understanding of an IT infrastructure. Therefore, the second question is the following:

Question 2 of the interview: Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?

The thematic analysis for the second question is presented in Table 15 Thematic analysis of interview question 2.

Theme	Essence
No Business Context	The IT infrastructure supports or enables applications to operate. Applications and the corresponding data provide real value for a business.
Technology Layer	The IT infrastructure is the most technologically advanced part of the IT landscape.
Physical IT infrastructure	IT infrastructure consists of physical hardware components such as servers, storage networks, and communication networks.
Virtual IT Infrastructure	The IT infrastructure is a collection of virtualized computing resources, such as virtual servers, virtual storage networks, and virtual communication networks.
Two parts; the dividing line is the OS.	The computer operating system level is the dividing line for applications and infrastructure.
It is all about the users.	The IT infrastructure is an environment with components that allow people to do their jobs.
Skeleton / Body of the IT Landscape	The IT infrastructure is the supporting layer of the IT landscape and must support all the other layers that build this landscape.
Hybrid	The IT infrastructure combines local on-premises IT infrastructure and cloud IT infrastructure.
Collaboration/Support Applications	Supporting applications, such as helpdesk software and collaboration applications, are part of the IT infrastructure.
It depends on your point of view	The definition of an IT infrastructure is something that can change depending on the viewpoint of people.

Table 15 Thematic analysis of interview question 2 (created by the researcher)

4.3.1 Implications for the IT Infrastructure

Based on the interviewees' responses, the IT infrastructure model presented by Sjaak Laan (Laan, 2017) could be adjusted. The transcripts also support the idea that a virtual IT infrastructure must be part of a new model. Furthermore, based on the interviewees' responses, the hybrid concept (Liu et al., 2011) is an important development and should be integrated into an IT infrastructure model. Applying the analysis results. The following adjustments can be made:

- Adding an on-premises data center and cloud provider building block to represent the hybrid IT infrastructure.
- Adding a physical infrastructure building block to both data center building blocks. This building block incorporates the existing building block for compute, storage, and networking.

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- Adding an infrastructure virtualization building block to both physical infrastructure building blocks. This building block has the function of enabling the hybrid way of working.
- Adding a generic virtualization layer, which combines both infrastructure virtualization building blocks. This building block is based on Infrastructure as a Service from the cloud computing model of Musse et al. (Musse & Alamro, 2016).
- Adding the Platform as a Service (Musse & Alamro, 2016) building block to deliver services to the application platform.
- The operating system building block is removed. This building block is now an implicit part of the IaaS building block.
- The infrastructure management building block is divided into two building blocks: a dedicated building block for managing the generic virtual infrastructure and a dedicated building block for managing the physical infrastructure.

Figure 47 New proposed IT infrastructure model version 1 (created by the researcher)

The new IT infrastructure model (version 1) is visualized in Figure 47 New proposed IT infrastructure model version 1. The added building blocks can be recognized by their gray color. The model consists of the different building blocks that make up an IT infrastructure. In this model, the process and information building blocks use the application building blocks to store and manage their data. The application building block needs the infrastructure platform building block to 'run.' The infrastructure platform building block is the accumulation of different building blocks representing different technologies and can be divided into two parts. The above part contains the building blocks of Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) and Platform as a Service (PaaS), this is called the virtual IT infrastructure, and the part below is called the physical IT infrastructure. Both parts have a separate management building block.

4.4 Exploring Automation

As described by Ghazizadeh et al. (Ghazizadeh et al., 2012) automation is not a single concept. In the context of information technology, we see that automation is used for different purposes in different layers of the IT landscape and within different technologies (Penttinen, Kasslin, & Asatiani, 2018). The IT infrastructure model (Laan, 2017) also describes that there are different management building blocks. Each management building block incorporates automation to manage and operate the corresponding building block(s). Another area of automation is the delivery of software. Humble et al. (Humble & Farley, 2011) describe the software delivery process as a deployment pipeline. The interesting question is, how do all these automation concepts and approaches fit within the IT infrastructure? The following two questions are formulated to capture the insight and are set against this background.

Question 3 of the interview: From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?

Question 4 of the interview: Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?

In the following subsection, the responses are analyzed.

4.4.1 Automation Themes

The thematic analysis of question three is presented in Table 16 Thematic analysis of interview question 3. The refinement of the themes for the third question is shown in the first column.

Refinement of themes	Theme	Essence
Defined IT environment	A standard way of configuring (Deployment is part of it) A reproducible environment Status-aware One Central Truth A Standard Way of Documentation	The IT infrastructure is fully aware of its status. Configurations are consistent with the policies, and configurations are deployed centrally.
Cloud-based Development	CI/CD Philosophy ⁴ Self-Service Based on Cloud Principles Development part of the IT infrastructure	The IT infrastructure provides and supports services for application development through pipelines.

Table 16 Thematic analysis of interview question 3 (created by the researcher)

⁴ CI/CD (Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery) is a software development philosophy where frequent code changes are integrated and tested in a shared repository, and then automatically delivered to production environments.

The result of the analysis of question three delivers two valuable conclusions about automation for an IT infrastructure. The first is that automation is necessary for an IT infrastructure to be fully aware of its status. With automation at all times, the operating or health status of the components can be recovered, and the approved configuration is known. This provides the ability to know the performance of a single component and the combination of all components, also known as the system, as a whole. The second is that an IT infrastructure enables and supports the application platform for software development and deployment. These conclusions support the finding in the theoretical framework for IT infrastructure and application development; see Sections 2.2 and 2.3.

For question four, some themes could be further refined and are shown in the first column of Table 17 Thematic analysis of interview question 4.

Theme	Essence
Fundamentally different	There is a fundamental difference between application automation and IT infrastructure. Automation for applications is about software and application development. Automation for the IT infrastructure is about configuration management and deployment of physical and virtual equipment. Both are managed by their own teams.
No difference	The IT infrastructure also contains application and software components.
Applications deliver business value.	Applications are, in essence, the "tools" to deliver business value.
Relation	With IT Infrastructure Automation, there is an interaction between the system software and the hardware. The application layer depends on the IT infrastructure layer. As a result, there are two different automation environments.
Automation at the Application Layer	Application automation is about building applications with continuous integration and deployment with continuous deployment; additional application automation is about supporting a dynamic environment where changes are fast and volatile.
Automation at the Infrastructure Layer	IT infrastructure automation is about continuously testing configurations and consistently provisioning them.

Table 17 Thematic analysis of interview question 4 (created by the researcher)

The results of the analysis of the fourth question support the results of the analysis of the third question. As mentioned above, the IT infrastructure enables the development and deployment of applications. The subject matter experts also divide automation into two entities, one for developing and deploying applications and one for configuring and provisioning. The differentiator is that application automation is about source code, and IT infrastructure automation is about parameter configuration.

4.4.2 Implications for Automation

Combining the new IT infrastructure model (Figure 47 New proposed IT infrastructure model version 1) with the information on automation from the previous section, a conceptual framework can be created with the two automation functions in the IT infrastructure. The conceptual framework has three automation layers to support two different functions.

Automation can also be defined as a pipeline for continuous integration and continuous deployment, according to Humble et al. (Humble & Farley, 2011). This approach is also valid for delivering a virtual IT infrastructure called Infrastructure as Code (de Souza, Franco, & Silva, 2022). The same principles can be applied to physical infrastructure. However, to the researcher's knowledge, there is no known approach for a continuous integration and continuous deployment pipeline for a physical IT infrastructure. The physical IT infrastructure has the same steps as a pipeline for continuous integration and continuous deployment (Pinto & Lacunza, 2021). Based on this knowledge, the conclusion can be derived that the concept of pipelines can be adapted to the physical IT infrastructure.

The two functions are as follows:

1. *Automation for software developers.*

This automation consists of two layers:

- a. Automation pipelines for software development and deployment (1).
- b. Automation pipelines are used to provision and deploy virtual IT infrastructure resources that are needed to run the application(s) (2).

2. *Automation for IT infrastructure professionals.*

This automation consists of pipelines for provisioning, deploying, and operating the physical IT infrastructure (3).

A visualization of the conceptual automation framework is shown in Figure 48 Conceptual automation framework in the new IT infrastructure model version 1. The number in the figure corresponds to the different functions mentioned above.

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Figure 48 Conceptual automation framework in the new IT infrastructure model version 1 (created by the researcher)

Based on the conceptual framework for automation and the three functions of every automation layer, a comprehensive, integrated continuous integration and continuous delivery pipeline can be created; see Figure 49 Proposed combined CI/CD pipelines. The combined continuous integration and continuous deployment pipeline model shows the relations between the three functions and how they interact.

Every layer has its responsibility and interacts with another layer. The application automation layer is the starting point. When a new application is deployed, the pipeline initiates the virtual infrastructure to allocate the necessary resources. The physical infrastructure delivers these resources. When automation of the physical infrastructure signals that the resource is available, the virtual infrastructure signals the application automation that the application can be deployed.

Figure 49 Proposed combined CI/CD pipelines (created by the researcher)

Every automation platform (Application, Virtual Infrastructure, Infrastructure) has its own speed of change. The application platform is the most volatile, and the infrastructure platform is the most stable. The pipelines can operate independently and work together.

4.5 Exploring the Maturity Model

Maturity models are widely used techniques to measure the current maturity level of a particular aspect and provide a path for systematic and logical improvement (Proença & Borbinha, 2016). As described in Chapter 2, a maturity model is a series of sequential levels to form a logical path from an initial state to a final state of maturity (Becker et al., 2009; Proença & Borbinha, 2016). The following interview question is about capturing the opinion and insights of the subject matter expert regarding the different levels of maturity models, especially in the context of IT infrastructure and automation.

Question 5 of the interview: This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? Do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?

The subject matter experts provided much insight into their maturity models for automation of the IT infrastructure and how they define a maturity model. The maturity model of subject matter experts can be found in Appendix 10. The thematic analysis of question 5 can be found in Appendix 11. The summary of the thematic analysis, which results in a maturity model for automation of the IT infrastructure, can be found in Table 19 Thematic analysis of interview question 6.

Theme	Essence
Level 0	This maturity level is all about manual tasks. These tasks are the configuration and parameterization of the components. There are no scripts and no documentation, and the state of the IT infrastructure is unknown.
Level 1	This maturity level is for scripted tasks, but the execution is done manually. The scripts manage the configuration and parameterization of one or multiple components. The state of the IT infrastructure is known at the component level.
Level 2	This maturity level is about automated scripts. The scripts manage the provisioning and deployment of the configuration and parametrization of multiple technologies and components. The state of the IT infrastructure is known across multiple components.
Level 3	This maturity level is about controller-based automation. The provisioning and deployment of configuration and parameterization are executed from a central controller. The automation solution is based on standards. The configuration and parameterization are checked and validated based on policies. These policies can include security and compliance. The state of the IT infrastructure is known across multiple components.
Level 4	This maturity level is about policy-based automation. The entire IT infrastructure is standardized. The provision and deployment of configurations and parametrization are fully policy controlled. The state of the IT infrastructure is known for the technology domain.
Level 5	This maturity level is about integrated automation. The IT infrastructure is self-learning and healing and knows the state of the IT infrastructure in different technology domains. Provisioning and deployment are fully autonomous.

Table 18 Thematic analysis of interview question 5 (created by the researcher)

The subject matter experts also provide some generic suggestions on developing a maturity model for an IT infrastructure. These are:

- *A more mature IT infrastructure can check whether it complies with company policies. The next step can be to have the automation fix the errors (automated healing).*
- *As the automation of the IT infrastructure matures, less knowledge of the IT infrastructure is required to deploy the application, as automation takes care of more tasks with increasing maturity.*

The construction of the maturity model consists not only of the levels but also of dimensions. Each dimension of the model represents a specific aspect of maturity, such as process, technology, people, or culture. For organizations to assess their current capabilities and identify areas for improvement, dimensions provide a structured framework. Organizations can better understand their strengths and weaknesses by evaluating their capabilities across these dimensions and developing a roadmap to improve their maturity level (Lasrado et al., 2015; Proença & Borbinha, 2016). The following two questions of the interview are about the dimensions and especially which ones are important for a maturity model for automation of the IT infrastructure. Where Question 6 is only about the dimensions, Question 7 is about the attributes of dimensions. These attributes are indicators that can be measured.

Question 6 of the interview: From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?

Question 7 of the interview: From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?

For the subject matter experts, the questions were challenging. They all struggled, especially with question 7, since no dimensions were presented, was naming the attributes for the experts challenging. Therefore, most experts answered these two questions at once. In the transcripts, the answers of the subject matter experts for both questions are combined; see Appendix 10. The thematic analysis is conducted on the combined answers, see Appendix 11. The analysis results only in a list of potential dimensions; see Table 19 Thematic analysis of interview question 6.

Theme	Essence
Empowerments	Leadership in the implementation of automation.
Technology	The technological aspects of automation.
Processes	Refer to a set of activities, tasks, or steps that are followed to manage, operate, maintain, and support the IT infrastructure.
People / Mindset	Refers to the mindset of people to automate repetitive tasks.
Culture	Refers to the organization's culture to automate repetitive tasks.

Theme	Essence
Skill / Knowledge	Refers to automating repetitive tasks; people must possess the knowledge and skills necessary for the task.
Deployment	Automated deployment of components.
Configuration	Automated configuration of components.
Compliance	The term refers to the fact that an IT infrastructure must comply with laws, regulations, and standards.
State (Errors /Failures)	Refers to the overall condition and performance of the IT infrastructure.
Security	Refers to the general measures that are taken to protect the IT infrastructure.
Standardization	Refers to establishing uniform guidelines, specifications, or criteria for products, services, processes, or systems to improve quality, consistency, safety, and compatibility.
Governance	Refers to the framework of policies, procedures, and processes that define how an IT infrastructure is managed, controlled, and monitored.
Operations	Refers to the ongoing management, maintenance, and support of an IT infrastructure to ensure that it functions reliably and efficiently.
Automatability	Refers to how an IT infrastructure can be automated to improve efficiency, reduce errors, and enhance performance.
Integrability	Refers to the ability of technologies within an IT infrastructure to work together seamlessly.
Hybrid (On-premises & Cloud)	Refers to an IT infrastructure environment that combines both on-premises and cloud-based resources.
Documentation	Refers to the process of recording and maintaining information about an IT infrastructure to ensure that it can be effectively managed, maintained, and supported over time.
Suppliers/Vendors/Partners	Refer to external companies or organizations that provide products, services, or solutions for an IT infrastructure.
Cost	Refers to the total amount of costs of an IT infrastructure to deploy, operate, maintain, and support technology components.
Architecture of Automation	Refers to the design and frameworks used to automate IT infrastructure.
Speed	Refers to the rate at which an IT infrastructure can adopt, integrate, and implement new technologies.

Table 19 Thematic analysis of interview question 6 (created by the researcher)

4.5.1 Development of the Preliminary Maturity Model

A maturity model is a framework that describes the stages of development and improvement of a particular process or practice. It is a tool for assessing and improving organizational processes and practices. It provides a roadmap for organizations to move from an initial, ad hoc state to a mature, optimized state. Maturity models typically consist of a set of maturity levels, each representing a different stage of development and improvement (Pereira & Serrano, 2020). Several features also characterize maturity models. First, they are hierarchical, each building on the previous level. Second, they are prescriptive, providing specific guidelines and criteria for each level. Third, they are iterative, meaning that organizations may move back and forth between levels as they learn and improve. Fourth, they are goal-oriented, with each level representing a specific goal or set of goals that organizations should aim to achieve (Becker et al., 2009; Kuriakose, Raj, Satya Murty, & Swaminathan, 2011; Proença & Borbinha, 2016).

The construction of a maturity model typically consists of a set of maturity levels and dimensions. Maturity levels represent a progression of increasing capability and are often described using a numerical scale or a descriptive name. At the same time, the dimension in the model represents a specific aspect of maturity, such as process, technology, people, or culture. The dimensions provide a structured framework for organizations to assess their current capabilities and identify areas for improvement. Organizations can better understand their strengths and weaknesses by evaluating their capabilities across these dimensions and developing a roadmap for improving their maturity level (Proença & Borbinha, 2016).

The dimensions in the preliminary maturity are based on the operational IT infrastructure capabilities. These capabilities can best be split into four domains: plan and organize, acquire and implement, provide and support, and monitor and evaluate. These four domains are derived from the COBIT framework and are an excellent practical fit for an organization to manage its IT infrastructure, according to Miranda et al. (Miranda, Rodavia, & Miranda, 2019). The Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model (Greene et al., 2017) contains a number of network areas to increase the management of an IT infrastructure. The relevant areas are automation, security, and analytics. Besides these areas, the following dimensions are selected: technology, documentation, provisioning, ability to change, and tasks. All these dimensions are also found as part of the thematic analysis, see Table 19. These dimensions are more abstract and aggregate some of the found dimensions.

Dimension provisioning is about executing the changes and incorporating the themes' configuration, deployment, and operations. Dimensional technology is selected to represent the different technologies used in IT infrastructure and exaggerate themes, hybrid, and integrability. Documentation is selected because there is always a lack; the subject matter experts also address this. The dimensions automation is about the essence of this research and needs to be addressed as a dimension; this is the same for tasks. This dimension incorporates the architecture of automation and automatability, and standardization. Here, the dimension tasks are about the manual aspects of automation. The dimension task is mentioned separately because part of the growth in maturity is to reduce manual tasks. With the help of this maturity model, an improvement path can be created to reduce

manual influence. The dimension of security incorporates the themes of governance and compliance. Analytics dimensions are about the overall insight, such as state (errors/failures) in the operation of the IT infrastructure. Although the thematic analysis also found cost and Suppliers/Vendors/Partners, these are not about the operational IT infrastructure capabilities and are not part of the preliminary maturity model. Lastly, the dimension ability to change is about the speed to execute a change. The distribution of dimensions in the four different domains is shown in Table 20.

Activities Domains	Dimensions
Plan and Organize	Technology Documentation
Acquire and Implement	Provisioning Ability to change
Deliver and Support	Automation Tasks
Monitor and Evaluate	Security Analytics

Table 20 Distribution of dimensions across IT management domains (created by the researcher)

Based on the models of CMMI (Chrissis et al., 2011), ITI-MM (Haris, 2010), Becker et al. (Becker et al., 2009), Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model (Greene et al., 2017) and the thematic analysis of the interview question 5, the levels for the preliminary maturity model are constructed; see Table 21 Maturity level of the preliminary maturity model.

Level	Description
1	<p>This level is characterized by a siloed, hardware/device-centric approach to infrastructure management. Device configurations are performed manually at this level, and policies and access management are fragmented and managed locally. Visibility into individual devices is limited, and each device is managed separately.</p> <p>There is no documentation or centralized system to manage the infrastructure, and changes to the infrastructure can take weeks to months to complete. This level of maturity is generally considered inefficient and prone to errors, as there is a high degree of manual intervention and limited visibility into the overall state of the infrastructure.</p> <p>Organizations at this level of maturity may struggle with scalability, agility, and overall efficiency. However, this level is an important starting point for organizations just beginning their journey toward automation and can serve as a baseline for improvement.</p>
2	<p>This level is characterized by an end-to-end hardware/device-centric approach to infrastructure management. There is basic automation for device configurations at this level, and policies and access management are decentralized. Basic configurations can be made, and insights into the infrastructure are only alarm-triggered and device-level. Scripts are in place for each component but are managed per device. Documentation is available for each device. Although some automation is in place, this level</p>

Level	Description
	<p>is still considered relatively inefficient and prone to errors. However, it represents a more systematic approach to managing the infrastructure and basic automation capabilities. Changes to the infrastructure can take days to weeks to complete. Organizations at this level of maturity may be able to handle larger-scale operations and respond more quickly to changes in the infrastructure. However, they may still struggle with scalability and overall efficiency.</p>
3	<p>This level is characterized by a mixed hardware-centric and software-centric approach to managing the infrastructure. At this level, controller-based automation is implemented for multiple devices, and policies and access management are centralized. Controller-based configurations are in place, providing information about the infrastructure in the technology domain. Scripts are available for multiple components, and documentation is available per technology domain. Changes to the infrastructure can take hours to days to complete.</p> <p>Organizations at this level of maturity have achieved a more systematic and centralized approach to infrastructure management. They can respond more quickly to changes with a higher level of automation and improved visibility into the infrastructure. However, organizations at this level may still have some manual processes.</p>
4	<p>This level is characterized by an end-to-end software-centric approach to managing the infrastructure. At this level, automation is in place for each technology domain, and policies and access management are managed per technology domain. Configuration is also managed per technology domain, with adaptive and preventive insight into the infrastructure. Scripts are in place per technology and multiple components, and cross-technology domain documentation is available. Organizations at this level of maturity have achieved a high level of automation and efficiency, with the ability to quickly adapt to changes and prevent problems from occurring. Changes to the infrastructure can be made in minutes to hours rather than days. However, there is still room for improvement toward higher levels of maturity. The organization may still have some manual processes in place, and there is an opportunity to achieve more comprehensive automation and integration across technology domains.</p>
5	<p>This level is characterized by an integrated software-centric approach to managing the infrastructure. At this level, there is comprehensive automation and integration across technology domains. There is also automated and predictive insight into the infrastructure, with scripts in place that are cross-technology domain and cross-components. Policies and access management are managed across technology domains, and configuration is managed across technology domains.</p> <p>Documentation is generated automatically and cross-technology domain, making it easy to keep track of changes and maintain a comprehensive understanding of the infrastructure. Changes to IT infrastructure can be made in seconds to minutes, allowing for rapid adaptation and response to changes. Organizations at this level of maturity have achieved a high</p>

Level	Description
	level of automation, integration, and efficiency. They are well-equipped to handle complex IT infrastructure and manage it in an effective and streamlined manner.

Table 21 Maturity level of the preliminary maturity model (created by the researcher)

The preliminary model is based on the structure of the generic maturity model as developed by Lasrado et al. (Lasrado et al., 2015) and presented in Table 22 A preliminary maturity model for IT infrastructure automation The model provides a path to evolve from no automation with a device-centric approach with manual configuration as the least mature level toward a fully integrated IT infrastructure with cross-technology domain automation as the most mature level.

Dimension	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Technology	Silo'd, Hardware/device-centric	End-to-End hardware/device-centric	Mixed hardware-centric and software-centric	End-to-End software-centric	Integrated software-centric
Automation	Manual device configuration	Basic configuration automation	Controller-based multiple devices Automation	Per technology domain automation	Cross-technology domain automation
Security	Fragmented (local) policy and access management	Decentralized policy and access management	Centralized policy and access management	Per technology domain policy and access management	Cross-technology domain policy and access management
Provisioning	Individual device-centric configuration	Basic configuration	Controller-based configuration	Per technology domain-based configuration	Cross-technology domain-based configuration
Analytics	Individual device visibility	Alarm-triggered and device level insight	Technology domainwide insight	Adaptive and preventative insight	Automated and predictive insight
Tasks	Manual	Script per component	Scripted to multiple components	Scripted per technology and multiple components	Scripted cross technology domain and cross components
Documentation	No documentation	Per device documentation	Per technology domain documentation	Cross technology domain documentation	Documentation is generated automatically and cross technology domain
Ability to change	Weeks to Months	Days to weeks	Hours to days	Minutes to Hours	Seconds to Minutes

Table 22 A preliminary maturity model for IT infrastructure automation (created by the researcher)

4.6 Summary

This chapter describes the first round of the design science research design cycle. The results of this cycle are a preliminary maturity model, a new model for the IT infrastructure, and a conceptual framework for automation regarding the IT infrastructure.

The first result is the preliminary maturity model developed for the automation of the IT infrastructure. The model is based on maturity models from the literature study and the analysis of the qualitative semi-structured interview. The framework of the maturity model consists of five levels and eight dimensions. The eight dimensions represent the necessary capabilities for improvement. The levels provide a path to evolve for device-centric IT infrastructure, with no automation, towards a fully integrated IT infrastructure that is fully automated.

The second result is a new IT infrastructure model developed to understand the current modern view of the IT infrastructure. The model consists of the different building blocks that make up an IT infrastructure. These building blocks have their own management building block. Because there are different management building blocks, there are different automation functions. The functions of automation for the IT infrastructure are 'Automation for users/developers' and 'Automation for IT professionals.' The first function contains the continuous integration and deployment pipeline for application development and the virtual

infrastructure pipeline. The second function contains the pipeline responsible for delivering the physical resource pools. Combining these automation functions forms a conceptual automation framework for an IT infrastructure. This conceptual framework is the third result.

5 The Preliminary Maturity Model Design

Within design science research, the development of artifacts is an iterative process. This chapter describes the second iteration. As shown in the previous chapter (Chapter 4), the results created in the first iteration are assessed through a digital survey. In the first part of this chapter, we explore the definition of an IT infrastructure by evaluating the digital survey responses, followed by proposing a refined model based on the digital survey results. The following part assesses the role of automation in IT infrastructure and refines the conceptual automation framework. The final part of this chapter evaluates the preliminary maturity model and proposes refinements.

5.1 The Digital Survey

In the context of the design cycle, it is crucial to validate the findings obtained in the initial stages of the design process. The survey was designed to validate the findings obtained from interviews conducted in the first iteration of the design cycle. An expert panel was asked to participate in a digital survey to achieve this. The survey questions were based on a Likert scale, with the option to provide feedback. The survey has three parts focusing on IT infrastructure, automation, and a maturity model for IT infrastructure automation. Appendix 12 contains the entire survey. The final report of the survey is available in Appendix 13. In the following sections, we will discuss the details of the survey and the responses provided by the expert panel.

5.2 Exploring the Definition of IT Infrastructure

The previous chapter (Chapter 3) created the first artifact for an IT infrastructure model. This section evaluates that artifact and suggests a refinement of the IT infrastructure model.

5.2.1 IT Infrastructure Model Evaluation

The first part of the digital survey, as outlined in Chapter 3, evaluates the IT infrastructure, and consists of three sub-questions. The first sub-question concerns the overall context in which the IT infrastructure operates. It depends on an individual's point of view on how the IT infrastructure can be seen. Because of that, there are many approaches to express what is an IT infrastructure. Section 4.3 has an overview of these 'ways.' The expert panel's opinion is asked to assess these 'ways' to see if there is a consensus about the 'ways' to express an IT infrastructure. The responses of the expert panel are shown in Figure 50 Results of the survey on 'way' to describe an IT infrastructure.

Analysis of the response to the statement regarding business context shows a consensus on the IT infrastructure to support the business. This consensus also supports the 'ways' of how an IT infrastructure is described in the scientific literature; see Section 2.1. As explained by Broadbent et al. (Broadbent et al., 1999) and Sirkemaa (Sirkemaa), the purpose of the IT infrastructure is to support different business processes. According to the consensus of the expert panel, this purpose is still valid in the current IT infrastructure. Broadbent et al. and Byrd et al. (Byrd & Turner, 2015) also stated that an IT infrastructure is the base fundament for supporting applications and services, supported by the survey results. The survey also

supports the scientific literature (Broadbent et al., 1999; Clive & Bigelow, 2020; Dijk, 2017; TOGAF, 2018) that the IT infrastructure is all about technology and can be seen as the lowest layer in the IT landscape. The IT infrastructure is not about users and their applications. Applications are supported and serviced by the IT infrastructure (Dijk, 2017; Laan, 2017; Musse & Alamro, 2016). This viewpoint is still valid according to the consensus of the expert panel.

Figure 50 Results of the survey on 'way' to describe an IT infrastructure (created by the researcher)

Today's IT infrastructure is a hybrid environment (Liu et al., 2011). The environment consists of different technologies, stacks, and physical areas. The second sub-question is about the IT infrastructure model version 1, see Section 4.3.1, and how these technology stacks as building blocks are positioned. The responses to the second sub-questions are presented in Figure 51. In the responses to the first two sub-questions, there is consensus that the IT infrastructure combines physical and virtual hardware. On the other hand, there is also consensus that IaaS is part of the IT infrastructure.

Most experts agree that the proposed IT infrastructure model represents the current view or understanding of the IT infrastructure as much as possible. There are a couple of minor remarks. The first one is about the building block cloud. Experts agree that the cloud building block must be part of the model but suggest using a more abstract approach. The cloud is just a service delivery model (Dijk, 2017). In addition, also the on-premises building block should be part of the model. The second remark is that a few experts do not see the

infrastructure as a platform. It is not clear why there is a more-than-average variance in the responses, except for the comment of one of the experts that there is a lack of industry definition of a platform. This lack could indicate that the experts do not have the same understanding of the term platform concerning IT infrastructure. The third remark is about users and their devices. Although users are not considered part of the infrastructure, the expert panel has a consensus that end-user devices are part of the IT infrastructure. It perfectly fits the fact that an IT infrastructure is constructed of physical technology building blocks. Some experts proposed an improvement for the end-user devices. End-user devices also need a location and physical infrastructure.

Figure 51 Results of the survey on the proposed IT infrastructure model (created by the researcher)

Another part of the second sub-question (IT infrastructure model version 1) is the management of the IT infrastructure. Experts have different opinions on the reach of the management of the IT infrastructure platform management building block. This opinion correlates with the view from most experts that IT infrastructure management cannot be divided, and that IaaS is part of the IT infrastructure. Based on this insight, the model needs to be changed. The infrastructure platform management building block should be merged with the infrastructure management building block.

The opinions of the expert panel have a significant variance about separate management for cloud and on-premises. The difference can be explained because it depends on the expert's viewpoint. Some experts only work with cloud environments and do not have an on-

premises infrastructure. For them, there will only be one cloud to manage. Other experts have an on-premises or hybrid infrastructure and need an overarching management solution.

The third sub-question concerns the relationship between the application and infrastructure platform building blocks. The different building blocks are shown in the IT infrastructure model version 1 in Section 4.3.1. The experts agreed that there is a clear difference between the application and infrastructure platforms. This also supports the current literature (Laan, 2017; TOGAF, 2018), which describes that there are different layers in the IT landscape with their own responsibility.

Experts have a slightly different opinion on the position of SaaS in the infrastructure. As described by Dijk (Dijk, 2017) and Liu (Liu et al., 2011), SaaS is about applications. Together with the consensus of experts that the IT infrastructure is not about applications and that there are different layers, it is safe to place SaaS in the application building block of the IT infrastructure building block.

An interesting observation is that according to experts, there is a difference between PaaS and the application platform. But the variance in the answer is very high; there is no consensus. The literature (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011) places PaaS in the infrastructure. But according to this outcome and the comments of some experts, PaaS nowadays can be placed in the application platform building block instead of the IT infrastructure building block.

5.2.2 IT infrastructure definition

The academic literature has various definitions of IT infrastructure, ranging from physical hardware and software components to broader network architecture; see Section 2.1. However, with the increasing shift towards cloud-based systems and services, there is a need for an updated definition that reflects this new paradigm. As organizations increasingly rely on cloud-based solutions for their IT infrastructure needs, it is essential to consider how this affects the traditional definitions and concepts of IT infrastructure (Haerens, 2016; Laan, 2017; Liu et al., 2011). Therefore, the researcher developed four concepts to define a more updated and modern definition of the IT infrastructure.

The following four concept definitions are presented via the survey to the expert panel:

- 1) The IT infrastructure is the overall shared and common foundation of virtual resources and services, which has no direct business context and enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data.
- 2) IT infrastructure is a shared platform with no direct business context, which supports and enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data. This platform consists of a virtual and supporting physical technology layer. Both layers consist of complex hard- and software components and communication technology.

- 3) IT infrastructure is a shared platform that provides a common foundation with virtual resources and service components with no direct business context to support and enable organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications.
- 4) IT infrastructure is a shared platform that provides a common foundation with virtual hardware and supporting software to provide resources and service components, with no direct business context, to support and enable organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications.

Definition number two received the most agreement from experts; see Figure 52 Survey result of IT infrastructure definitions A couple of experts write a comment to explain their score. These experts had trouble with a definition that explicitly included 'no business context.' They all stated that the IT infrastructure delivers value to the business. This is in line with the observation at the beginning of Section 5.2.1.

Figure 52 Survey result of IT infrastructure definitions (created by the researcher)

Based on the response of experts, a definition of an IT infrastructure must include the following requirements:

- The IT infrastructure supports the business in achieving its goals.
- The IT infrastructure contains a physical technology layer because there is always a physical component.
- The IT infrastructure includes a virtual resource to support cloud services.

Combining definition two with the above requirement results in a refined IT infrastructure definition.

An IT infrastructure platform is a shared foundation that enables organizations to develop, implement and operate present and future business applications and data. The platform comprises both physical and virtual resources.

Definition 5-1 IT Infrastructure (created by the researcher)

5.2.3 Explorative study with expert

The explorative study was conducted with the author of the book "IT Infrastructure Architecture" (Laan, 2017). The author was not a member of the expert panel and was consulted separately. The author is asked to assess the proposed IT infrastructure model; see Section 4.3.1. This model is based on the IT infrastructure model described in his book.

The author had the following response:

When writing my book, I discovered that no adequate model was available for IT infrastructure. It took me quite some time to develop a model that was not only comprehensive, but also provided a framework for the structure of the book, resulting in a coherent narrative. The model has evolved through various book editions, and as I prepare for the fourth edition, I am revisiting the model. The upcoming edition of the book will include a greater focus on cloud-related information, and I am currently exploring the possibility of making changes to the existing model.

Your new model appears to be well-designed.

I do have a few points of attention:

- *In my current model, I was able to indicate that nonfunctionals should be described for each layer easily. However, this is less achievable in your new model.*
- *Although a cloud provider essentially has the same components as an on-prem infrastructure, the physical implementation is often different. I find it difficult to say precisely how an infrastructure of, for example, Google is built. Network components are partially solved in software and not with special hardware. This also applies to storage. Therefore, the model is somewhat challenging in terms of explaining each component.*
- *I believe you should merge the PaaS and Application Platform layers because I cannot clearly distinguish the difference unless you mean only Kubernetes⁵ as PaaS. However, a platform cannot function without a number of surrounding components, such as databases.*
- *I think you need to make a different layout for automation. Infra-automation should only apply to IaaS in your model because there is little to automate without virtualization. You may or may not include the PaaS layer here. I often see that the team that builds and automates Kubernetes differs from the team that builds networking⁶.*

⁵ Kubernetes is an open-source container orchestration platform that is widely used in cloud computing and enterprise applications.

⁶ Networking refers to the practice of connecting computer systems and devices together to share resources and communicate with each other. It encompasses various technologies and protocols that enable data

- *Infrastructure Platform Management is on the left side, which also applies to IaaS in your model. This sounds illogical. Perhaps it is a good idea to make automation part of the management blocks on the left to remove some complexity from your model.*

The suggestion of this explorative research regarding the reduce the complexity of the explanation of the model, the position of PaaS, and making automation part of the management block are adopted.

5.2.4 Refined IT Infrastructure Model

This section presents a refined IT infrastructure model developed with the analyzed survey results and input from an expert in the field. The expert's information was particularly valuable in refining the model's conceptual framework and coverage of emerging trends (the merge of PaaS towards the application layer) and cloud technologies. The same trend, the move from PaaS towards the application building block, is also noticed in the survey results.

The IT infrastructure, see Figure 53, has four main building blocks that aggregated a primary function. Changes compared to the previous version are greyed out. The functions are as follows.

- *Location* covers the different places where a physical infrastructure can be located. These locations are:
 - *Private* refers to cloud services and resources dedicated to a single organization and hosted on-premises or in a third-party data center.
 - *Hybrid* refers to a combination of both on-premises and cloud-based infrastructure.
 - *Public* refers to third-party service providers providing cloud services and resources over the Internet.
- *Physical Infrastructure* covers the three main physical building blocks of an IT infrastructure, namely:
 - *Networking* enables communication and data transfer between different components, such as servers, storage, and applications.
 - *Compute* refers to the processing power and resources required to run various workloads and applications.
 - *Storage* refers to the means to store and manage large volumes of data.
- *Virtual Infrastructure* covers the three main virtual building blocks of an IT infrastructure, namely:
 - *Virtual Networking* refers to an abstract pool of network resources to create logical networks that are isolated from each other, ensuring better security and resource utilization.
 - *Virtual Compute*, also known as virtual machines (VMs), refers to a virtualized environment of processing power and resources.
 - *Virtual Storage* is the type of storage in which logical storage is created by combining multiple physical storage devices.

exchange between systems, including local area networks (LANs), wide area networks (WANs), and the internet.

- *End-user devices* refer to hardware and software to interact with the IT infrastructure. These devices can range from traditional desktops and laptops to mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets.

Besides the four main building blocks, there is a change in the management blocks. The application, application platform, and infrastructure platform management buildings are aggregated in one building to manage all the applications, including SaaS and PaaS. The IT infrastructure remains one infrastructure building block.

An overview of changes between the initial IT infrastructure model (Laan, 2017) and the refined IT infrastructure model is presented in Table 23. This overview tells which building blocks are changed, added, or removed and the input sources.

Initial Model Building Blocks	Refined Model Building Blocks	Based on	Rationale
Datacenter	Location	Interview Survey Explorative study	IT infrastructures are available in different locations. Therefore, an overarching building block is added, which contains the three central areas where the IT infrastructure is located.
Networking Storage Compute	Physical Infrastructure	Interview Explorative study Survey	The technologies that construct a physical infrastructure are combined in an overarching building block.
	Virtual Infrastructure	Interview Survey	This building block is added to support the cloud infrastructure.
Operating Systems		Interview	Due to the introduction of virtualization and the incorporation of the operating systems in the virtualization environment, there is no need for this building block.
Application Management Platform Management	Application & Infrastructure Platform Management	Survey Explorative study	
	PaaS	Survey Explorative study	Automation and technology have changed the initial function of PaaS. PaaS is more of an abstraction layer on top of the virtualization building block that fully integrates with the application platform.

Table 23 Overview change between IT infrastructure models (created by the researcher)

One of the remarks and comments was that the definition of the platform is unclear. In their book 'Team Topologies,' Skelton et al. (Skelton et al., 2019) describe that a platform is necessary for a software development organization to support and enable application development. The IT infrastructure model contains two platforms, one to support and enable software development and the other to deliver the resources needed for the application to operate. However, there is a clear split between the capabilities and services provided by the IT infrastructure platform and the application platform.

Figure 53 The Infrastructure Model Version 2 (created by the researcher)

The book 'Team Topologies' (Skelton et al., 2019) defines a digital platform as follows:

A digital platform is a foundation of self-service APIs, tools, services, knowledge, and support which are arranged as a compelling internal product. A digital platform is a foundation of self-service APIs, tools, services, knowledge, and support which are arranged as a compelling internal product.

Definition 5-2 Digital platform (adapted from (Skelton et al., 2019))

This definition supports the platform approaches in the IT infrastructure model: the application platform and the infrastructure platform. The application platform and the infrastructure platform operate independently. The application platform contains the necessary functionality to build and deploy an application and uses resources from the infrastructure platform.

The infrastructure platform can be seen as one building block and has one management building block. In this way, there is an overarching management function to provision and operate all the building blocks of the infrastructure platform.

There is a change in the PaaS position within current infrastructure models (Dijk, 2017; Liu et al., 2011; Musse & Alamro, 2016). This model moves PaaS toward the application platform. The application platform offers a clear differentiation in functionality, making it suitable for software delivery and virtual resource allocation. In contrast, the infrastructure platform is responsible for providing a pool of resources. The expert panel and the expert also suggest the move of the PaaS building block toward the application platform.

5.3 Exploring the Definition of Automation for IT Infrastructure

The second part of the survey focused on automation. As described earlier in this research, automation is used for different purposes and in different layers of the IT infrastructure (Ghazizadeh et al., 2012; Penttinen et al., 2018). In Section 4.2.2, three types of automation are identified and proposed in the conceptual automation framework. The first type is the well-known automation for the application layer. The second type is automation for the virtual infrastructure, also known as Infrastructure as Code (Morris, 2020). The third type of automation is for the more physical IT infrastructure components.

The automation survey started with statements about the conceptual automation framework and types of automation. The responses of the expert panel are shown in Figure 54 Results of the survey on automation for the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher).

An observation is that multiple experts have commented on the purpose of automation. They asked the question, what are the goals of automation? Automation is at the core of anything we have been trying to achieve with IT since the beginning of IT. The goal is to eliminate human interference so that 'things' are consistent, have a greater speed of change, and have greater quality during change. That perspective explains the huge variance in response to the statements that automation is all about the deployment pipelines.

Most experts agree that there are three types of automation. This agreement is supported by the responses that many experts have a consensus that there is a difference between automation for applications, virtual infrastructure, and physical infrastructure.

Figure 54 Results of the survey on automation for the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher)

Another observation is that most experts agree that physical infrastructure automation is the domain of IT professionals. There is no consensus that type one and type two automation is more for users and developers. The variance in responses can be explained by the fact that it depends on the subject matter experts' point of view. It depends on whether an expert works in a more cloud-oriented economy or a more traditional one, such as the public sector.

The final part of the automation survey is about the combined delivery pipelines; see Section 4.4.2. These pipelines implement the types of automation of the conceptual framework for automation. The first delivery pipeline is the application pipeline, which is all about application deployment. The second is the virtual infrastructure pipeline, which is all about virtual infrastructure deployment. The latest is that the (physical) infrastructure pipeline is about (physical) infrastructure (compute, network, storage) deployment. Figure 55 Survey results on CI / CD statements Experts have a consensus that there are three pipelines of delivery. Based on the experts' responses, the conclusion can be drawn that every pipeline has its own speed of change.

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Figure 55 Survey results on CI / CD statements (created by the researcher)

The survey validates the proposed conceptual automation framework and shows that there are three types of automation. Simultaneously, the survey confirms the automation delivery model for the three types of automation. Based on this conclusion, no further refinement of the conceptual automation framework and the automation delivery model is needed.

5.3.1 Refined Conceptual Framework for Automation in the IT Infrastructure

The previous section ended with the conclusion that there is no refinement needed. But due to a change in the IT infrastructure model, the three types of automation must be reallocated. The model can also explicitly add the automation relation between the application and infrastructure platforms. This relation is known as infrastructure as code. The refined conceptual framework for automation in the IT infrastructure is presented in Figure 56 Conceptual framework for automation in the IT infrastructure version 2. Changes compared to the previous version are greyed out.

Figure 56 Conceptual framework for automation in the IT infrastructure version 2 (created by the researcher)

5.4 Exploring maturity model design

The third part of the survey focused on a maturity model for the automation of IT infrastructure. As highlighted in Chapter 2, a maturity model is a framework to assess an organization's current maturity level and identify the corresponding gap to reach the next maturity level (Becker et al., 2009). In the previous chapter, a preliminary maturity model was developed. The expert panel is asked to give its opinion on three aspects of this maturity model. The first question is about a suitable model for the maturity under investigation. The second question is about what would be the 'good' dimensions to represent an aspect of the desired maturity. Experts are asked to evaluate the preliminary maturity model in the third question. In the following sections, the responses for these aspects are worked out.

5.4.1 Exploring the Type of a Maturity Model

Maturity models can be categorized into two types, a staged maturity model or a continuous model (Serrano & Pereira, 2020). These types describe a different path to achieving a certain maturity level. In a staged model, to achieve a certain maturity level, it is required that the organization's capabilities are compliant with the dimensions of that level. In a continuous model, every capability is individually evaluated and improved, and each capability can be at a different maturity level, see Figure 57 Examples of a staged and continuous maturity mode.

To develop a maturity model, a choice for a model needs to be made. In the survey, experts are asked to respond to several statements about the development of capability in an organization. This development is relevant for the growth path in a maturity model and which model fits better for an automation maturity model for the IT infrastructure.

Figure 57 Examples of a staged and continuous maturity model (created by the researcher)

As can be seen in the survey results, Figure 58 Results of the survey on the types of maturity models The preferred model type for the experts is the continuous model. The experts agree that the organization's capability evolves individually and does not develop linearly. This consensus is supported by the agreement that not all capabilities of an organization need to be on the same maturity level. The comments of multiple experts also support this agreement.

Figure 58 Results of the survey on the types of maturity models (created by the researcher)

5.4.2 Exploring the Maturity Model Domains

The second aspect that is investigated is the dimensions of a maturity model. These dimensions represent a specific aspect of maturity for which a roadmap for improvement can be developed (Lasrado et al., 2015; Proença & Borbinha, 2016). Based on the cloud maturity model (Dijk, 2017), IT infrastructure model (Haris, 2010), and the results of the thematic analysis of the interviews in the first iteration, Section 4.5, initial dimensions are conceived. These two maturity models are chosen because they cover the whole aspect of an IT infrastructure, including the cloud. Table 24 Overview of possible dimensions for a maturity model contains the list of the dimensions and from which model it is derived.

Dimensions	Cloud Maturity Model (Dijk, 2017)	IT Infrastructure Maturity Model (Haris, 2010)	From the thematic analysis of interviews
Ability to change (Pace/Speed)			x
Actions are defined upfront.			x
Automation		x	x
Automation Architecture			x
Agility		x	
Business Process Management	x	x (business interface)	
Compliance	x		x
Documentation			x
Data Management	x		
Education			x
Ecosystem Relationship		x	
Financial	x	X (Pricing Scheme)	X (cost)

Dimensions	Cloud Maturity Model (Dijk, 2017)	IT Infrastructure Maturity Model (Haris, 2010)	From the thematic analysis of interviews
Governance	x		x
Knowledge		x	x
Infrastructure	x		
Infrastructure Configuration			x
Infrastructure Deployment			x
Infrastructure Management		x	
Infrastructure Provisioning		x	
IT Architecture	x		x
Operations	x		x
Repeatability			x
Process Management			x
Scalability			x
Standardization			x
Security	x		x
Service Management		x	
Self-Services			x
Skills			x
Software	x		
Software Development	x		
Solution Driver		x	
Status aware (Errors/Failures)			x
Tasks (manual – automated)			x
Infrastructure Utilization		x	
Vendor Management	x		x

Table 24 Overview of possible dimensions for a maturity model (created by the researcher)

The expert panel is asked to rate all dimensions. This approach aims to capture an expert's point of view and how they relate a dimension to automation. On purpose, the dimensions are not deliberately accompanied by explanations. The experts' responses are shown in Figure 59 Results of the survey on the dimensions of a maturity model (created by the researcher).

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Figure 59 Results of the survey on the dimensions of a maturity model (created by the researcher)

An analysis of the response shows that experts mostly agree that all dimensions are relevant for the maturity model. A top ten can be extracted with a deeper analysis of the statistic; see Appendix 13 for the statistic. Table 25 Top 10 dimensions based on statistical analysis, shows for which dimensions the total score is the highest and for which the variance is the lowest.

Top 10 Based Total Score	Top 10 Based on the lowest variance
Automation Architecture	Self-Service
Automation	Infrastructure Provisioning
Infrastructure Provisioning	Automation Architecture
Repeatability	Standardization
Standardization	Infrastructure Management
Infrastructure Deployment	Infrastructure Deployment
Self-Service	Scalability
Infrastructure Management	Knowledge
Tasks (manual - automated)	Solution Driver
Scalability	Infrastructure Configuration

Table 25 Top 10 dimensions based on statistical analysis (created by the researcher)

5.4.3 Exploring the Maturity Model Levels

The expert panel is asked to assess the preliminary maturity model in the last part of the survey. The first question is about the naming of the levels. Although the naming is not relevant to assess the maturity levels of an organization, a clear name helps in communication. The researcher proposed four naming schemes; see Table 26 Proposed naming schemes for maturity model.

Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Based on
Manual	Semi-automated	Automated	Service-based	Policy-based	Researchers' viewpoint
Not stable	Local stable	Partial stable	Passive stable	Active stable	Interviewee See Appendix 10.8
Basic	Controlled	Standardized	Optimized	Innovative	ITTI-MM (Haris, 2010)
Initial	Repeatable	Defined	Managed	Optimized	Becker (Becker et al., 2009)

Table 26 Proposed naming schemes for maturity model (created by the researcher)

Figure 60 Results of the survey on statements to describe the different maturity levels (created by the researcher)

Name schemes are derived from the literature, suggestions from an interviewee, and the researcher's viewpoint. These schemes fit the purpose of the maturity model, which is to define a roadmap. The experts scored the first naming scheme the highest; see Figure 60

Results of the survey on statements to describe the different maturity levels As a result, this naming scheme would be used in the final version of the maturity model.

The expert panel's opinion is asked about the preliminary maturity model; see Section 4.5.1. The main question is to provide the preliminary maturity model with a roadmap for growth in automation. Consequently, according to experts' opinions, there is a growth path. In addition, there is consensus about the number of levels. A maturity model with five levels is sufficient for a maturity model; see Figure 61 Results of the survey on the preliminary maturity model (created by the researcher).

Figure 61 Results of the survey on the preliminary maturity model (created by the researcher).

Based on the responses collected during the interviews, there are some statements about the day-n operations (Rami, 2015). For the maturity model to have more practical value, it would be nice if the model could support these day-n operations. All the responses to the day-n statements have a high variance, and most experts give a neutral response. Additionally, some experts commented that day-n operations are not part of the maturity model. Because, on every maturity level, the day-n operations are applicable. As a result, the final version of the maturity model should not incorporate the day-n operations paradigm. In Chapter 6, the survey results are used to develop the maturity model.

5.5 Summary

This chapter describes the second round of the design science research design cycle. This cycle's first result is a refined IT infrastructure model and a corresponding definition. The second result is a refined version of the framework for automation in the IT infrastructure. Lastly, a naming scheme for the five levels of the preliminary maturity model is defined. Also, suggestions are made for dimensions.

6 The IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model

In this chapter, the IT infrastructure automation maturity model is presented. First, the environment is defined as described by design science research. A new model and definition of the IT infrastructure are presented, followed by an explanation of the function and relationship of automation concerning the IT infrastructure. Secondly, the design criteria for a maturity model are defined. At the end of this chapter, the artifact (maturity model for IT infrastructure automation) is developed, and the IT infrastructure maturity model is described in detail.

6.1 Definition of IT infrastructure

The IT infrastructure has evolved over the last decade. The rise of the cloud landscape has changed the primary function of the IT infrastructure in the IT landscape. This change is described in Chapter 1, the theoretical framework in Chapter 2, and reconfirmed by subject matter experts in interviews (Section 4.3) and the digital survey (Section 5.2).

Combining the definition of IT infrastructure (Definition 5-1) with the conceptual framework for automation in the IT infrastructure version 2 (Section 5.3.1) led to the following new definition of IT infrastructure (Definition 6-1).

An IT infrastructure platform is a shared foundation for the application landscape, consisting of self-service APIs, tools, services, and knowledge. This foundation enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data. The platform comprises both virtual resources and supporting physical technology, which work together in an automated way to provide the necessary services and a managed environment.

Definition 6-1 IT Infrastructure (Final) (created by the researcher)

This definition covers both the traditional and cloud infrastructure. Since it also covers the virtual infrastructure, the hybrid IT infrastructure is implicitly incorporated due to the fact the virtual infrastructure is overarching to both infrastructure types. In addition, it bridges the automation gap between the IT infrastructure definitions from the theoretical framework by incorporating the platform approach. The definition positions the IT infrastructure as a platform that provides the necessary resources for the application platform. The platform also aligns with the IaaS definition from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (Liu et al., 2011).

This definition aligns with the IT infrastructure model version 2 of Section 5.2.4. However, two essential building blocks are missing in that IT infrastructure model. As described in the theoretical framework (Section 2.2) and confirmed by experts (Section 4.2 and Section 5.2.1), there is a need for business IT alignment. Although there are two building blocks for processes, a business building block refers to the organization's goals, strategies, and objectives. In contrast, processes refer to specific activities or steps to achieve those goals

and objectives. In other words, processes are the individual steps or actions that contribute to the overall functioning of the business.

Effective use of IT in business involves aligning IT resources with the organization's strategic goals and ensuring they are used to improve business processes and outcomes. To make that difference more evident in the model, the IT infrastructure model version 2 is expanded with two building blocks. The first is a building block for the business, representing the organization's different business processes and activities to achieve its goals and objectives. The second building block is business management, which involves the effective and efficient use of technology to support and improve business processes. The updated IT infrastructure model is shown in Figure 62. The added building blocks are colored gray.

Figure 62 The IT Infrastructure model version 3 (created by the researcher)

The IT infrastructure model defines that the IT infrastructure platform has four functions, namely:

1. *Locations* for IT infrastructure include data centers owned by the organization and third-party data centers or a combination of both.
2. The *physical infrastructure* of an IT infrastructure refers to the tangible components that make up the system, such as servers, storage devices, networking equipment, and cabling.
3. The *virtual infrastructure* uses virtualization technologies to create and manage virtual machines, networks, and storage resources. It allows for efficient resource utilization, flexibility, and scalability.
4. *End-user devices* are an essential component of IT infrastructure as they allow users to interact with the system. These devices can range from traditional desktop computers to mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets.

All these building blocks are managed from the infrastructure management building block.

The resulting IT infrastructure model provides a comprehensive and up-to-date view of the IT infrastructure. Overall, the model can be a valuable tool for IT professionals and researchers seeking to understand and analyze IT infrastructure in today's rapidly evolving digital landscape.

6.2 Definition of IT Infrastructure Automation

As mentioned in different places in this document, automation is a broad concept. The concept is overarching and all-inclusive. Subject matter experts and the theoretical framework confirm this view. After focusing on IT infrastructure automation, the concept becomes more specific. Based on this research, IT automation can be divided into three workflows. A workflow is a series of tasks or processes that are automated and executed in a specific sequence to achieve a desired outcome. This term is commonly used in the context of automation and can refer to the overall process of automating a particular task or set of functions. Another more technical term in automation for a "workflow" is a "pipeline." The three workflows are shown in Section 5.2.3, where the conceptual framework for automation in the IT infrastructure is presented.

The three workflows are:

1. Automated workflow for software development and deployment.
2. Automated workflow for provisioning and deployment of virtual IT infrastructure resources.
3. Automated workflow for provisioning, deploying, and operating physical IT infrastructure resources.

The first two workflows are more for the software developer, where the application code is written, built, tested, and deployed, together with the configuration of resources needed to run the application. The third workflow is about configuring the physical resources to provide the necessary resources to run the application. The three workflows and their relationship are depicted in Figure 63 Automation workflows in IT.

Figure 63 Automation workflows in IT (created by the researcher)

In the context of automation, the PDCA cycle can be applied to improve IT infrastructure management continuously (Nedzelskay et al., 2020). The PDCA cycle consists of four steps: Plan, Do, Check, and Act. This cycle is known as the Deming Cycle (Figure 64) and assures quality control.

Figure 64 Deming Cycle (adapted from (Nedzelskay et al., 2020))

The PDCA cycle can be related to the different workflows. They all have their own speed of change. Due to the automated interactive relation between the workflows, the quality of the combination is still ensured.

Figure 65 Conceptual Automation Framework in IT Infrastructure Version 3 visualizes the workflows on the IT infrastructure model. The numbers in the model refer to the three workflows.

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Figure 65 Conceptual Automation Framework in IT Infrastructure Version 3 (created by the researcher)

By combining the conceptual framework for automation in IT infrastructure, the updated IT infrastructure model, and the corresponding definition, a definition of automation can be established within the context of IT management. Specifically, automation refers to using software tools and technologies to automatically provision, configure, deploy, and manage physical and virtual resources within the IT infrastructure platform, including servers, storage, and networking resources. In this context, automation involves using automation tools, scripts, and workflows to perform tasks that would otherwise be carried out manually, such as provisioning, patching, and scaling. The purpose of automation in the IT infrastructure platform is to reduce the time and effort required to manage IT infrastructure, enhance consistency and reliability, and enable quicker response times to change business needs.

The following definition for automation in the IT infrastructure is formulated:

Automation of the IT infrastructure platform consists of the use of software tools and technologies to automatically provision, configure, deploy, and manage physical and virtual resources such as servers, storage, and networking. It involves using automation tools, scripts, and workflows to perform provisioning, patching, and scaling tasks.

Definition 6-2 Automation for the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher)

In conclusion, automation of the IT infrastructure platform involves using software tools, scripts, and workflows to automatically provision, deploy, and operate physical resources such as servers, storage, and networking. By automating these tasks, the IT team can reduce the time and effort required to manage physical and virtual infrastructure, improve

consistency and reliability, and respond more quickly to changing business needs. With a proper automation workflow, organizations can ensure that their physical and virtual IT infrastructures are always up-to-date, secure, and optimized for performance without the need for manual intervention.

6.3 Design of IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model

The design science research methodology highlights the importance of defining the environment for developing an artifact. As such, the previous sections have provided a clear understanding of the environment. This understanding is essential for the creation of the artifact of this research. In the final iteration of the design cycle, this artifact, which is a maturity model, will be created.

Maturity models provide a framework for measuring an organization's capabilities in a particular area over time. To ensure the accuracy of the model and to provide a clear path for improvement, the design of the maturity model must be carefully considered. The criteria for designing a maturity model can be divided into three categories. The first category is the general design, which encompasses a clearly defined structure for maturity, specific criteria and indicators for each level, a means of measuring progress or success, and a framework for assessing an organization's current state and identifying areas for improvement. The second category is the design of the levels of a maturity model. Each level represents the organization's progress in that area, with each level building on the previous one. Finally, the third category involves the design of dimensions for a maturity model, which are specific focus areas used to assess an organization's current state and advancement toward higher maturity levels. The design of these dimensions requires a thorough examination of the fundamental characteristics vital to the context of the organization or process under assessment. The following sections will describe the three design categories in more detail.

6.3.1 General Maturity Model Design Criteria

The purpose of a maturity model is to define a path to evolve over time. Lasrado et al. (Lasrado et al., 2015) describe a generic framework for constructing a maturity model. This framework considers the required path for growth. According to Lasrado et al., there are three essential components to describe a maturity model, they are:

1. *Levels*: a level of a maturity model represents a specific stage of development in an organization's capabilities or processes. Each level builds on the previous one and should have a set of distinct characteristics that are empirically testable.
2. *Dimensions*: a dimension is a specific focus area used to evaluate an organization's current state and progress toward higher maturity levels.
3. *Sub-dimensions*: refer to a more granular focus area used to evaluate an organization's current state and progress toward higher maturity levels.

The construction of this framework is visualized in Figure 66 General Structure of a Maturity Model based on

Figure 66 General Structure of a Maturity Model based on (Lasrado et al., 2015)

Various general components must be part of a maturity model (Haris, 2010; Kuriakose et al., 2011):

- A number of levels (typically three to six).
- A generic description or summary of the characteristics of each level as a whole number of dimensions.
- A description of each activity as it might be performed at each maturity level.
- The maturity model should be practically adaptable to any organization.
- It should be flexible enough for continual improvement to suit various changes in organizational environments.
- It should combine, if possible, the strength of existing models.

Based on the digital survey outcome, the model must be a continuous maturity model. This type of maturity model emphasizes continuous improvement and growth rather than discrete levels. It is a more fluid and flexible approach that allows organizations to continually adapt and evolve their processes and capabilities.

Design Criteria 1 The infrastructure automation maturity model must be a continuous model.

6.3.2 Design Criteria for Automation in the IT Infrastructure

IT infrastructure automation aims to streamline and simplify IT infrastructure management by automating routine tasks and processes (Advanced_Systems_Concepts, 2021; Bigelow, 2019; Maxima_Consulting, 2021; Redhat, 2019; VMWare, 2022). The scope for IT

infrastructure automation is described in the first two sections and covers IT infrastructure management. This scope provides a level playing field for developing a maturity model.

Design Criteria 2 The infrastructure automation maturity model covers the management of the IT infrastructure Platform

As seen in the IT infrastructure model (Figure 62), there is a decoupling between the physical IT infrastructure and the Virtual IT infrastructure. But there is a direct relation between both layers. Adding and removing physical and virtual components in the IT infrastructure platform must be easy to maintain, and both layers' constancy, quality, and stability must not be affected. This can be achieved when the defined automation workflows (Figure 63) are correctly implemented.

Infrastructure as code is an automation paradigm for providing virtual infrastructure resources. This paradigm covers the whole lifecycle management for virtual resources (Humble & Farley, 2011; Morris, 2020) and embraces the dynamic concepts of the cloud age. These concepts support making changes frequently and reliably. To guide the design and implementation of automation for the IT infrastructure to support these concepts, several principles are defined by Morris (Morris, 2020); see Table 27 Principles for implementing automation in the IT infrastructure.

Number	Principle
P1	Define everything as Code.
P2	Continuously test and deliver all work in progress.
P3	Build small, simple pieces that can be changed independently.
P4	The desired state of the infrastructure should be specified through version-controlled configuration.
P5	Infrastructure should be autonomic; that is, it should automatically correct itself to the desired state.
P6	The management environment should always know the actual state of the infrastructure through monitoring and analytics.
P7	Assume systems are unreliable.
P8	Make everything reproducible.
P9	Create disposable things.
P10	Minimize variation.
P11	Ensure that every process can be repeated.

Table 27 Principles for implementing automation in the IT infrastructure (adapted from (Morris, 2020))

Design Criteria 3 The infrastructure automation maturity model covers the principles for implementing automation for the IT infrastructure platform.

The principles from Table 27 give guidance for the maturity model. The level with the highest maturity must be able to comply with these principles. To comply, the highest level of automation must be entirely policy driven, which means that all automation processes are governed by predefined policies that dictate how automation should be performed. These policies typically define what tasks should be automated, how they should be

automated, and under what conditions automation should be triggered. The opposite is that the lowest level is ad-hoc and manual.

Design Criteria 4	The infrastructure automation maturity model provides a roadmap from no automation in the IT infrastructure platform to an entire policy-driven IT infrastructure platform.
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IT infrastructure management refers to the processes, practices, and services necessary to support and manage a platform. These operations are critical to ensure the availability, reliability, and security of IT services and assets (Dijk, 2017; Haris, 2010; Howell, 2022; Miranda et al., 2019; Pinto & Lacunza, 2021; Scott et al., 2007; Stephen, 2020). The following are some key management operations for an IT infrastructure platform:

1. *Infrastructure management*: Infrastructure management manages the physical infrastructure, including servers, storage, and networking equipment. This includes monitoring the hardware for faults, upgrading or replacing equipment when necessary, and ensuring the infrastructure is secure.
2. *Resource allocation and configuration*: Software developers can request and configure the required resources, including compute, storage, and network resources, based on their needs. The infrastructure management is responsible for allocating the resources and ensuring they are configured correctly.
3. *Security management*: The infrastructure management ensures that the infrastructure complies with the security policies, including protecting against cyber-attacks, data breaches, and other security threats. This includes implementing security controls and procedures.
4. *Performance monitoring and optimization*: The infrastructure management must monitor the performance of the infrastructure and optimize it to ensure that it meets the users' needs. This includes monitoring resource utilization, identifying bottlenecks, and adjusting to ensure optimal performance.

Design Criteria 5	The infrastructure automation maturity model provides a roadmap for an IT infrastructure platform's four key management operations.
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One of the other general design guidelines is to integrate the strength of other maturity models. Table 28 shows a list of the maturity model that influences the development of the maturity model, and the corresponding rationale. In the following sections, the influences of these models on the levels and dimensions are discussed.

Maturity Model	Number of Maturity Levels	The rationale for using this model as the base
ITTU-MM (Haris, 2010)	1 - 5	As derived from the IT infrastructure model, IT infrastructure is a diverse environment that is flexible in its virtual nature. This maturity model is designed to support a flexible IT infrastructure.
Maturity Model for IT Management (Becker et al., 2009)	0 - 5	The scope for the development of the maturity model is management. This maturity model proposes a procedure for designing a maturity model for IT management and then developing a maturity model for IT performance measures that incorporates automation.

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Maturity Model	Number of Maturity Levels	The rationale for using this model as the base
Gartner IT Infrastructure and Operations Maturity Model (Scott et al., 2007)	1 – 6	This maturity model evaluates the people, processes, and technology for operating an IT infrastructure. These three methodologies influence the behavior of the IT infrastructure. Therefore, they are essential to incorporate in the model.
The Gartner Infrastructure Maturity Model. (Hidas, 2006)	1 - 6	This maturity model from Gartner is a more detailed version. It describes people, processes, technology, and a more granular level of how an IT infrastructure can evolve.
Maturity Model for Implementing ITIL v3 (de Sousa Pereira & da Silva, 2010)	1 – 5	This maturity model provides a framework for Information Technology Infrastructure Library (ITIL), a best practice framework for managing IT. These management aspects are interesting only if they have the potential to be incorporated into the model.
Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model (Greene et al., 2017)	1 - 5	This maturity model describes a practical path for automation maturity in the network infrastructure and is one of the most practical maturity models found. It is this pragmatic approach that can be adapted to the model.
Cisco Network Automation Maturity (Pinto & Lacunza, 2021)	1 - 5	This maturity model describes a detailed roadmap for automation for a network and incorporates the day-n operations. This roadmap provides a path from automating a single device to a policy-driven approach and can be adapted to the model. The roadmap starts with a device-centric approach and moves toward a fully self-automated and policy-driven approach.
Cloud Maturity Model (Dijk, 2017)	1 – 5	This maturity model describes a roadmap for Cloud infrastructures. The model under development can benefit from this roadmap. An IT infrastructure incorporates the Cloud infrastructure and combines these with an on-premises IT infrastructure.
DevOps Maturity Model (Radstaak, 2019)	1 - 5	This maturity model describes a roadmap for DevOps in an organization. DevOps is a set of practices that emphasizes collaboration and communication for software development and delivery in an automated way. These practices can be interesting for the development of this model.
Open Group Service Integration Maturity Model (Group, 2009)	1 – 7	This maturity model describes the services integration for IT infrastructure and management. The IT infrastructure platform provides service to the application platform. From that perspective, it can be relevant to incorporate suggestions into the model.
Netbrain Network Automation Maturity Model (Netbrain, 2022)	0 - 4	This maturity model provides an automation roadmap from manual tasks to policy-driven tasks. This roadmap is of value for the development of the model.
Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (Quali, 2021)	1 – 5	This maturity model is a model from a company that describes a roadmap for infrastructure automation. The value of automation and the change drives to move to a higher maturity level are defined for every level. From that perspective, suggestions and approaches could be of value to incorporate into the model. From all the found models, this is the only model that comes close to the model under development.

Table 28 List of maturity models that influences the maturity model for automation of the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher)

Design Criteria 6 The infrastructure automation maturity model must incorporate the best strengths of the maturity model mentioned in Table 28

6.3.3 Design Criteria for Levels

The design of levels is a critical aspect of developing a maturity model. The levels within the maturity model represent the organization's progress in that area, with each level building on the previous one. The overall design criteria for levels of a maturity model are the following (Becker et al., 2009; Haris, 2010; Kuriakose et al., 2011):

1. Precise definitions of each level.
2. Specific goals and outcomes associated with each level.
3. A clear roadmap for organizations to progress from one level to the next.
4. Levels are sequentially ordered, from an initial level to a final level of perfection.

Applying the overall design criteria for levels with the outcome of the digital survey for the naming scheme and the design criteria four, the naming for the automation IT infrastructure maturity model can be defined. Design criteria seven describes the five levels.

Design Criteria 7	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
	Manual	Semi-automated	Automated	Service-based	Policy-based

Applying design criteria six with design criteria seven results in Table 29 Mapping the levels of different maturity models. This table shows the mapping of all the levels of the select maturity model to the defined maturity level of the model under development. Added to this table are the two scales for levels of automation. These scales describe the different stages from no automation and only human interaction to fully autonomous control.

Source	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Stages and Levels of Automation (Wickens et al., 2010)	Fully Manual Control.	The computer offers a complete set of decision/action alternatives.	The computer narrows the selection down to a few. The computer suggests one alternative. The computer executes that suggestion if the human approves.	The computer allows the human a restricted time to veto before automatic execution. The computer executes automatically, then necessarily informs the human.	The computer informs the human only if asked. The computer informs the human only if it decides to. Fully autonomous Control.
A literature review on the levels of automation during the years. What are the different taxonomies that have been proposed? (Vagia et al., 2016)	Manual Control.	Decision proposal stage. Human decision select stage.	Computer decision select stage. Computer execution and human information stage.	Computer execution and on call human information stage. Computer execution and voluntary information stage.	Autonomous Control Stage
ITU-MM (Haris, 2010)	Basic	Controlled	Standardized	Optimized	Innovative
Maturity Model for IT	Non-Existent Initial	Repeatable	Defined	Managed	Optimized

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Source	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Management (Becker et al., 2009)					
Gartner IT Infrastructure and Operations Maturity Model (Scott et al., 2007)	Survival Awareness	Committed	Proactive	Service-Aligned	Business Partnership
The Gartner Infrastructure Maturity Model. (Hidas, 2006)	Basic Centralized	Standardized	Rationalized	Virtualized Service-Based	Policy-Based
Maturity Model for Implementing ITIL v3 (de Sousa Pereira & da Silva, 2010)	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model (Greene et al., 2017)	Best effort Manual	Semi-Automated	Automated		Self-Driving
Cisco Network Automation Maturity (Pinto & Lacunza, 2021)	Manual Device Configuration	Basic Configuration	Controller-based per-domain automated provisioning	Controller-based network-wide automated provisioning	Automated provisioning of devices in a self-organized, self-diagnosing, and dynamically updated network
Cloud Maturity Model (Dijk, 2017)	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
DevOps Maturity Model (Radstaak, 2019)	Base	Beginner	Intermediate	Advanced	Expert/Extreme
Open Group Service Integration Maturity Model (Group, 2009)	Silo	Platform-specific	Common Reusable Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common SOA Environment • SOA Environment Sense and Respond 	Context-aware Event-based Sense and Respond
Netbrain Network Automation Maturity Model (Netbrain, 2022)	Manual	Interactive	Collaborative	Triggered	Preventative
Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (Quali, 2021)	Ad-hoc	Automated	Frictionless	Lifecycle	Self-Defining

Table 29 Mapping the levels of different maturity models (created by the researcher)

The definitions of each level with their specific goals and outcomes are described in Table 30 Description of the maturity levels (created by the researcher).

Level	Description
1	<p>Manual tasks characterize this level.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The components in the infrastructure are siloed, and there is a hardware/device-centric approach to infrastructure management. • Device configurations are performed manually at this level, and policies and access management are fragmented and managed locally. • Visibility into individual devices is limited, and each device is managed separately. • There is no documentation or centralized system to manage the infrastructure, and changes to the infrastructure can take weeks to months to complete. • Individuals or teams have little or no knowledge about automation and may be unaware of the need to acquire knowledge or have just started learning about it. • The culture is reactive and responds to situations as they arise. There is no incentive for automation. • Governance is ad hoc and reactive, with no formalized processes or procedures in place. • Compliance is handled on an individual basis. • SLAs are ad hoc and informal. They may not be documented or consistently applied.
2	<p>Semi-automated tasks characterize this level.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The components are operated by an end-to-end hardware/device-centric approach to infrastructure management. • There is basic automation for device configurations at this level, and policies and access management are decentralized. • Basic configurations can be made, and insights into the infrastructure are only alarm-triggered and device-level. • Scripts are in place for each component but are managed per device. • Documentation is available for each device. • Changes to the infrastructure can take days to weeks to complete. • Individuals or teams have some basic knowledge of automation but lack experience applying it. • The culture is more defined, and there are some basic expectations for implementing automation. • Basic governance processes are established and documented. There is some standardization in decision-making, and policies and procedures are developed and implemented. • Compliance is recognized as necessary, and policies and procedures are established to manage it. However, these policies and procedures may not be consistently followed, and there may be limited accountability. • SLAs are documented and consistently applied. There are some processes in place for tracking and reporting on SLA performance. • Although some automation is in place, this level is still considered relatively inefficient and prone to errors. However, it represents a more

Level	Description
	<p>systematic approach to managing the infrastructure and basic automation capabilities.</p>
<p>3</p>	<p>Automation characterized this level.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The components are operated by a mixed hardware-centric and software-centric approach to managing the infrastructure. • At this level, controller-based automation is implemented for multiple devices, and policies and access management are well-defined and centralized. Controller-based configurations are in place, providing information about the infrastructure in the technology domain. • Scripts are available for multiple components, and documentation is available per technology domain. • Changes to the infrastructure can take hours to days to complete. • Individuals or teams have developed a good understanding of automation. • The culture is proactive, and employees are actively encouraged to use automation. Employees are empowered to make decisions using automation in IT infrastructure management. • Governance processes are well-established, documented, and consistently followed. • SLAs are well-defined and aligned with business needs. Transparent processes are in place for tracking and reporting SLA performance, and SLA metrics are regularly reviewed and analyzed. • Compliance is consistently managed and enforced through formalized policies and procedures.
<p>4</p>	<p>Service-based characterize this level.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The components are operated by an end-to-end software-centric approach to managing the infrastructure. • At this level, automation is in place for each technology domain, and policies and access management are handled per technology domain. • Configuration is also managed per technology domain, with adaptive and preventive insight into the infrastructure. • Scripts are in place per technology and multiple components, and cross-technology domain documentation is available. Document management systems are in place, with version control. • Organizations at this level of maturity have achieved a high level of automation and efficiency, with the ability to quickly adapt to changes and prevent problems from occurring. • Changes to the infrastructure can be made in minutes to hours rather than days. • Individuals or teams deeply understand automation and can apply it in complex or challenging situations. They can adapt their knowledge and skills to new situations and often find innovative solutions. • The culture is highly collaborative, and employees work together to implement automation solutions. Employees are encouraged to share

Level	Description
	<p>knowledge and ideas about automation, and a culture of continuous learning and improvement exists.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance processes are fully integrated into the management of the IT infrastructure platform. Governance metrics are tracked and reported, and there is a high level of accountability for non-compliance. • Compliance policies and procedures are continually reviewed and refined, and compliance training is provided to all employees. • SLAs are actively managed to ensure service levels are consistently met. There are robust processes in place for monitoring, reporting, and analyzing SLA performance.
5	<p>Policy-drive characterize this level.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The components are operated by an integrated software-centric approach to managing the infrastructure. • At this level, there is comprehensive automation and integration across technology domains. • There is also automated and predictive insight into the infrastructure, with scripts in place that are cross-technology domain and cross-components. • Policies and access management are managed and integrated across technology domains, and configuration is managed across technology domains. • Documentation is generated automatically and cross-technology domain, making it easy to keep track of changes and maintain a comprehensive understanding of the infrastructure. • Changes to IT infrastructure can be made in seconds to minutes, allowing for rapid adaptation and response to changes. • There is a strong sense of creativity and a willingness to automate 'everything.' Individuals or teams have a mastery of automation and can apply it in various situations. The highly innovative culture encourages employees to think outside the box and take risks to drive innovation. • SLAs are integrated into all aspects of the operation of the IT infrastructure platform and are seen as a critical tool for managing customer expectations and driving performance. • Governance is a constantly evolving process integrated into all aspects of the operations of the IT infrastructure platform. • Compliance is a continually evolving process integrated into all aspects of the operations of the IT infrastructure platform. Compliance metrics are used for tenuous improvement, and compliance efforts are coordinated across all functions.

Table 30 Description of the maturity levels (created by the researcher).

6.3.4 Design Criteria for Dimensions

A well-designed set of dimensions can provide a clear roadmap for improving maturity and achieving desired outcomes. Therefore, the design of the dimensions requires careful consideration of the characteristics necessary for the particular context of the organization or process being evaluated. The dimensions should be clearly defined, measurable, and actionable, aligning with the organization's or process's overall goals and objectives. Design criteria for dimensions of a maturity model include:

1. **Relevance:** The dimensions should be relevant to the context and goals of the maturity model.
2. **Comprehensive:** The dimensions should cover all essential aspects of the context and goals of the maturity model.
3. **Clear definitions:** The dimensions should be clearly defined to avoid confusion and ensure consistency in understanding.
4. **Measurable:** The dimensions should be measurable so that progress and maturity levels can be tracked and evaluated.
5. **Scalable:** The dimensions should be able to scale across different levels and contexts.
6. **Mutually exclusive:** The dimensions should be mutually exclusive so there is no overlap or duplication between them.
7. **Consistent:** The dimensions should be consistent with the overall purpose and goals of the maturity model.

Design criteria two and four define that the maturity model covers IT infrastructure management. Therefore, all the dimensions should relate to managing and operating an IT infrastructure. The Gartner I&O maturity model (Scott et al., 2007) defines operating and maintaining three essential methodologies: people, processes, and technology. These methodologies also align with the conceptual model of this research; see Section 3.2.2. A Harvard report on IT complexity (Nallappan, 2022), concluded that managing complexity is not just a technology answer; companies must also consider processes and people. Based on these arguments, the main dimensions of this maturity model are people, processes, and technology.

Design Criteria 8	The infrastructure automation maturity model's main dimensions are people, processes, and technology.
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Combining design criteria two, four, and eight, the sub-dimensions can be selected from the list of dimensions, as presented during the digital survey (Section 5.4.2). The correct dimensions that fit the three methodologies and direct managing and operating an automated IT infrastructure platform can be chosen. To support the sub-dimension development, they must also be mentioned in the selected papers (Table 27) (Design Criteria 6). The chosen sub-dimensions are essential for automated IT infrastructure; they support the principles (Table 27) and are also based on the thematic analysis of the interviews. Table 31 presents the dimensions and sub-dimensions, where the column paper and survey explain on which rigor they are based.

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Dimensions	Sub-Dimensions	Papers	Survey
People	Knowledge and Skills	(Anwar & Masrek, 2014; Becker et al., 2009; Haris, 2010; Quali, 2021; Scott et al., 2007)	Education Knowledge Skills
	Culture	(Quali, 2021; Radstaak, 2019; Scott et al., 2007)	
Processes	Management	(Anwar & Masrek, 2014; Becker et al., 2009; Dijk, 2017; Haris, 2010)	Business Process Management Infrastructure Management Process Management Vendor Management
	Documentation	(Radstaak, 2019)	Documentation IT Architecture
	Governance	(Dijk, 2017)	Governance
	Compliance	(Dijk, 2017)	Compliance
	Policies	(Becker et al., 2009)	
	Monitoring	(Becker et al., 2009; Pinto & Lacunza, 2021; Radstaak, 2019)	Status aware Infrastructure Utilization
	Analysis	(Becker et al., 2009; Pinto & Lacunza, 2021; Radstaak, 2019)	Status aware
	Service Level Agreement	(Group, 2009; Haris, 2010)	
	Ability to change	(Haris, 2010; Hidas, 2006)	Scalability Infrastructure Utilization
	Technology	Deployment (Build and deploy)	(Pinto & Lacunza, 2021; Radstaak, 2019)
Provisioning		(Becker et al., 2009; Haris, 2010; Pinto & Lacunza, 2021; Radstaak, 2019)	Infrastructure Configuration Infrastructure Provisioning
Security		(Dijk, 2017 ; Pinto & Lacunza, 2021)	Security
Tasks (automation)		(Netbrain, 2022; Pinto & Lacunza, 2021; Quali, 2021; Radstaak, 2019)	Automation Automation Architecture Tasks (manual-automated) Software Software development

Table 31 Overview of dimensions and sub-dimensions (created by the researcher).

It's worth noting that these sub-dimensions are not mutually exclusive and can overlap. For example, developing and implementing skills development programs can fall under the People and Process dimensions. Similarly, security processes can involve both the Process and Technology dimensions. Overall, the key to effectively managing an IT infrastructure is to balance these activities across all three dimensions and continually monitor and improve them over time.

6.4 IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model

Combining the dimensions and sub-dimensions with the description of levels gives and complete maturity model for automation in the IT infrastructure. A high-level maturity model is presented, with the different levels and dimensions, in Figure 67 Maturity Model for Automation of the IT Infrastructure. The different improvement paths per dimension are described further in this section.

Figure 67 Maturity Model for Automation of the IT Infrastructure (created by the researcher)

The presented maturity model meets all design criteria described in this chapter. Table 32 gives an overview of all the design criteria formulated throughout this chapter.

Design Criteria 1	The infrastructure automation maturity model must be a continuous model.
Design Criteria 2	The infrastructure automation maturity model covers the management of the IT infrastructure Platform
Design Criteria 3	The infrastructure automation maturity model covers the principles for implementing automation for the IT infrastructure platform.
Design Criteria 4	The infrastructure automation maturity model provides a roadmap from no automation in the IT infrastructure platform to an entire policy-driven IT infrastructure platform.
Design Criteria 5	The infrastructure automation maturity model provides a roadmap for an IT infrastructure platform's four key management operations.
Design Criteria 6	The infrastructure automation maturity model must incorporate the best strengths of the maturity model mentioned in Table 28

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Design Criteria 7	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
	Manual	Semi-automated	Automated	Service-based	Policy-based
Design Criteria 8	The infrastructure automation maturity model's main dimensions are people, processes, and technology.				

Table 32 Overview of design criteria for infrastructure automation maturity model (created by the researcher)

Following the design criteria for dimensions, as presented at the beginning of Section 6.3.4, a more detailed maturity can be developed. The more detailed maturity model is shown in Table 33 Detailed Maturity Model for Automation in the IT Infrastructure. This model incorporates a more precise description of a level and a dimension. That description makes it possible to assess an organization for its maturity level for automation of the IT infrastructure.

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
	Manual	Semi-Automated	Automated	Service-Based	Policy-Based
People					
Knowledge and Skills	Individuals or teams have little or no knowledge of automation.	Individuals or teams have some basic knowledge of automation but lack experience applying it.	Individuals or teams have developed a good understanding of automation.	Individuals or teams deeply understand automation and can apply it in complex or challenging situations.	Individuals or teams have a mastery of automation and can apply it in various situations.
Culture	Culture is reactive and responds to situations as they arise.	Culture is more active, and there are some basic expectations for implementing automation.	Culture is proactive, and employees are actively encouraged to use automation.	Culture is highly collaborative, and employees work together to automate solutions.	Culture is highly innovative, and employees are encouraged to automate 'everything.'
Processes					
Management	Siloed management and hardware/device-centric.	End-to-End management of hardware/device-centric.	Mixed management for hardware-centric and software-centric components	End-to-End management and only software-centric	Integrated management and only software-centric
Documentation	There is no documentation.	Documentation is available for each device.	Documentation is available for every technology domain.	Documentation is available for every technology domain, and document management systems are in place.	Documentation is a constantly evolving process integrated into all aspects of the organization's operations.
Governance	Governance is ad hoc and reactive.	Basic governance processes are established and documented.	Governance processes are well-established, documented, and automated.	Governance processes are fully automated and integrated into the management of the IT infrastructure platform.	Governance is a constantly evolving process that is automated and integrated into all aspects of the operations of the IT infrastructure platform.
Compliance	Compliance is handled on an individual basis.	Compliance is recognized as important, and policies and	Compliance is consistently managed and	Compliance policies and procedures are automatically and	Compliance is a continually evolving process that is automated

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	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
		procedures are established to manage it.	automatically enforced	continually reviewed and refined.	and integrated into all aspects of the operations of the IT infrastructure platform.
Policies	Policies are ad hoc and unstructured	Basic decentralized policy management processes are established and documented.	Policy management processes are well-defined and centralized, and automatically enforced.	Policy management is actively managed, handled per technology domain, and automatically enforced.	Policy management is integrated, managed, handled in cross-technology domains, and automatically enforced.
Monitoring	Monitoring is ad hoc and reactive.	Basic monitoring processes are established and documented.	Monitoring processes are well-defined.	Monitoring is actively managed to ensure system performance is consistently optimized.	Monitoring is integrated into all aspects of the IT infrastructure platform.
Analysis	The analysis is ad hoc and unstructured	Basic analysis processes are established and documented.	The analysis processes are well-defined.	The analysis is actively managed to ensure adaptive and preventative insight	The analysis is integrated into all aspects and is automated, and provides predictive insight
SLA	SLAs are ad hoc and informal.	SLAs are documented and consistently applied.	SLAs are well-defined.	SLAs are actively managed to ensure service levels are consistently met.	SLAs are integrated into all aspects of the IT infrastructure platform.
Ability to change	Able to change in months to a week	Able to change in weeks	Able to change in weeks to days	Able to change in days to minutes	Able to change in minutes to seconds
Technology					
Deployment (Build and deploy)	Manual device configuration and deployment	Basic configuration and deployment in an automated way	Controller-based multiple devices configuration and deployment in an automated way	Per technology, domain configuration and deployment in an automated way	Cross-technology domain configuration and deployment in an automated way
Provisioning	Individual device-centric configuration	Basic configuration	Controller-based configuration	Per technology domain policy and access management	Cross-technology domain policy and access management
Security	Fragmented (local) policy and access management	Decentralized policy and access management	Centralized policy and access management, and automatically enforced.	Per technology domain policy and access management and automatically enforced.	Cross-technology domain policy and access management, and automatically enforced.
Tasks (automation)	Manual	Script per component	Scripted to multiple components	Scripted per technology and various components	Scripted cross-technology domain and cross components

Table 33 Detailed Maturity Model for Automation in the IT Infrastructure (created by the researcher)

6.5 Summary

In this chapter, the environment of the design science research is presented. This environment consists of an IT infrastructure model and a conceptual framework for the automation of the IT infrastructure. The IT infrastructure model is updated, and a new definition of the IT infrastructure is presented. This definition covers the physical and virtual infrastructure, locations, and end-user devices and positions the IT infrastructure as a platform that provides the necessary resources for the application platform.

Automation for the IT infrastructure consists of three workflows. There is one workflow for the application platform, one for the virtual infrastructure platform, and the last for the infrastructure platform. These three workflows are incorporated into the conceptual framework for automation in the IT infrastructure. Additionally, a definition for automation in the IT infrastructure is defined.

The defined environment provides a clear scope for a maturity model for the automation of the IT infrastructure. The developed maturity model consists of five levels, from manual to policy-based automation. The main dimensions of the maturity model are people, processes, and technology. The development maturity model provides a framework to assess an organization's maturity level for IT infrastructure automation.

7 Discussion

This chapter reflects and discusses the research process and the results. The chapter starts with a reflection on the research methodology, the design science research used in combination with the Delphi study used to create the artifact. A discussion on IT infrastructure and IT infrastructure automation follows this reflection. The followed by a discussion about the maturity model created for IT infrastructure automation.

7.1 Reflection on the Research Approach

Throughout this research study, the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology of Vom Brocke et al. (Vom Brocke et al., 2020) and the Delphi method (Turoff & Linstone, 2002) are used. The DSR methodology has been selected to ensure scientific rigor in developing the maturity model. During the maturity model development process, the DSR methodology was connected with the theoretical framework and the environment in an iterative way. The divergent and convergent methodology was added to this iterative approach. This methodology provides flexibility during the whole research period for publications to be found and added after filtering the theoretical framework. That way, publications immediately contribute to the development of the maturity model.

One of the challenges we had to overcome during this study was a lack of clarity in the scientific literature on the concepts that make up the environment of the artifact. For example, a clear and up-to-date definition of an IT infrastructure and automation in the context of an IT infrastructure was lacking. These challenges were alleviated by applying the DSR method, which allows an iterative approach to develop a clear and updated definition for IT infrastructure and IT infrastructure automation.

The Delphi method is used in the main research and is related to the development of the maturity model. The setup of the Delphi method allowed the use of different methods for collecting data and validating the first preliminary maturity model. The first method was a semi-structured interview. Collecting information from subject matter experts was very valuable and filled the gap between IT infrastructure in the iron age and today in the cloud age. The conducted interview approach allowed the researcher to introduce the research better and ask for more explanation when an answer was not clear. On the other hand, the results of the interviews provided unequivocal answers. The thematic analysis method was a perfect approach to structure these unstructured data.

The interviews are followed by a digital survey, another valuable method of collecting data and getting consensus. Due to the geographical spread of the experts, the Delphi method (Avella, 2016; Belton, MacDonald, Wright, & Hamlin, 2019; Turoff & Linstone, 2002) allowed the researcher to invite more experts. The main reason for inviting more experts was made clear by Okoli C et al. (Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004); one of the challenges for a research study is keeping experts involved during the investigation. The size of the expert panel is between fifteen to twenty participants (Alarabiat & Ramos, 2019; Avella, 2016; Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004; Toma & Piciooreanu, 2016). To be relevant for the digital survey, the number of respondents must also be between fifteen and twenty. To take into account a potential dropout of experts, a group of forty experts is invited. This invitation was a good decision;

some of the experts involved in the interviews could not attend the digital survey. Thanks to these extra invites, the criteria for a relevant number of participants are met.

Another challenge is the selection of appropriate experts, as pointed out by Okoli C et al. (Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004). The extensive professional network of the researcher was crucial to the success of this research and provided access to a large group of experts with relevant background knowledge and experience. All experts have worked for many years in information technology and different professions. Therefore, a great deal of practical knowledge was added to the research. This knowledge was valuable in understanding the IT infrastructure and automation correctly.

7.2 Reflection on Qualitative Semi-Structured Interviews

As a researcher, it is essential to note that the qualitative semi-structured interview has provided valuable insights into the opinions and practices of the subject matter experts. The positive response of subject matter experts to providing their own maturity models in Question Five highlights their willingness to share their knowledge and experience. Therefore, the preliminary maturity model cloud should be created based on the practical knowledge of the experts.

Subject matter experts found it challenging to answer interview questions six and seven about dimensions and attributes. They all had difficulty mentioning relevant dimensions and providing a roadmap for automation to grow with accurate attributes. A potential reason was the lack of not having a conceptual maturity model to discuss. Asking questions about a conceptual model should help to discuss dimensions and attributes. It is advisable to divide the interview into two parts, where the questions about dimensions and attributes are part of the second part. In the time between the interviews, a preliminary maturity model can be created and used as input for the second interview.

Not recording the interview but transcribing the notes by hand has worked well in capturing the insights. However, there is a drawback to this approach. It introduces a potential bias for the research because most of the transcribing was from the researcher's memory. It is usual to ask the interviewee to review the transcribe to mitigate this bias. For this research, the transcriptions are not sent to the interviewee to validate that their response was captured correctly. Interpretation errors without validation can potentially influence the results. Therefore, the limitation of not validating the transcribed notes with the interviewee should be addressed as a potential improvement area. The use of the digital survey mitigates the potential bias of the researcher.

7.3 Reflection and Discussion on the Digital Survey

The digital survey provided valuable information on IT infrastructure and IT infrastructure automation. The subject matter experts' opinions provide the necessary consensus to understand a modern IT infrastructure and how automation affects the management of that infrastructure. When this consensus was not reached, it was impossible to have an updated definition of IT infrastructure and IT infrastructure automation. Then, as a consequence, the creation of the maturity model was not possible.

Questions about the maturity model were more challenging. Although a preliminary maturity model was developed, asking questions about it was difficult. The reason for this was that the environment (context) of the research was not yet defined. As mentioned earlier, the environment (IT infrastructure and IT infrastructure automation) was part of the research. Therefore, it was impossible to establish a clear context to establish the automation landscape for the IT infrastructure. This limited the potential of the survey related to the question about the maturity model. This limitation was best expressed in the question of dimensions. The idea behind the question was to capture an expert's view on this subject. However, due to the lack of context, almost every subject matter expert found it challenging to answer this question. This resulted in an unusable response to the subsequent development of the maturity model.

7.4 Discussion on the IT Infrastructure

The discussion of the IT infrastructure in this thesis presents a complex and evolving landscape. The updated IT infrastructure model perfectly shows that it has become more complex in recent decades. Additionally, the updated IT infrastructure model and the definition of the IT infrastructure model contribute to the scientific body of knowledge. The shift towards a hybrid IT infrastructure and the disappearing line between the application platform and Platform as a Service created a transparent and easy-to-understand model for the IT infrastructure. This research also suggests that the IT infrastructure has four main functions: location, physical infrastructure, virtual infrastructure, and end-user devices. Additionally, the Platform as a Service is part of the application platform, which changes the traditional view of cloud delivery models and moves the Platform as a Service toward the application layers. This change introduces a different view of the platform as a service from the more commonly accepted definition of the platform as a service as proposed by NIST (Liu et al., 2011).

7.5 Discussion on IT Infrastructure Automation

The conceptual automation framework developed during this research, which supports the updated IT infrastructure model presented in the thesis, also shows that the IT landscape is more complex. This model also shows that there are three automation workflows. Two workflows are acknowledged in the scientific body of knowledge: Workflow 1 (Applications) and Workflow 2 (Infrastructure as code). Our research identified a third workflow that should be considered: the workflow for automation of the IT infrastructure.

The workflow of the IT infrastructure is, by definition, challenging. The IT infrastructure consists of a range of technologies delivered by different vendors. Therefore, interoperability for automation is challenging. This is mainly a challenge for practical implementation and is not part of this research. However, when somebody tries to implement automation, this is essential to understand. The subject matter experts interviewed confirmed this interoperability for the automation challenge and emerged during thematic analysis (Section 4.2.1 Implications for Automation).

In addition, the interoperability for the automation challenge is supported by the literature review. A report from consulting firm Forrester, “The Forrester Wave™: Infrastructure Automation Platforms, Q3 2019” (G. Chris, 2019), provides a list of the top infrastructure automation platforms. The consulting firm Gartner provides a representative list of vendors in their market guide for network automation and orchestration tools (Josh Chessman, 2020). Combining both lists gives the following leading vendors for infrastructure automation: Red Hat⁷, Microsoft⁸, VMWare⁹, BMC Software¹⁰, Cisco¹¹, and HashiCorp¹². Many others followed them.

Both observations provide insight into one of the main problems in adopting automation. Although some products have the potential to build a general orchestration environment, there is no interoperability between the different products. The main reason for missing interoperability is due to the lack of standardization. This sounds like an information asymmetry (Akerlof, 1970) between the on-site vendors and the customer who builds their automated infrastructure on the other site. Vendors have the knowledge and information to create a siloed closed ecosystem with their products for a specific technology. This asymmetry creates an imbalance, making it almost impossible to build an automated IT infrastructure above maturity level four. For maturity level five, IT infrastructure automation must be a cross-technology domain solution, and interoperability is essential.

7.6 Discussion on the maturity model

The maturity modality model developed for the automation of the IT infrastructure follows the five phases of control (Hancock, 2014). These five phases (see Figure 68) represent a generalized pattern for all forms of automation and the level of human control. Hancock's research shows that technology, especially automation, plays an essential role in how organizations and individuals do business. It is up to organizations to decide how much control they want over their IT infrastructure.

⁷ Red Hat top product for automation is ansible, which drive seamless orchestration, integration configuration management, and governance for multiple products.

⁸ Microsoft provides multiple tools for automating the infrastructure across environment, the main product is Azure automation.

⁹ VMware provides a menu of automation solutions, mainly to build PaaS and IaaS platforms.

¹⁰ BMC Software provides a solution for advance automation across myriad types of infrastructure, which is especially good at analytics, reporting and compliance.

¹¹ Cisco has solutions for Network Automation.

¹² HashiCorp provides solution for operating cloud-computing infrastructures.

Figure 68 A generalized growth pattern of automation and reduced manual contributions to all forms of human activity (adapted from (Hancock, 2014)).

The maturity model developed during this research allows organizations to assess their current automation maturity level to manage IT infrastructure and provide a roadmap for further growth.

The three dimensions influencing how an IT infrastructure is operated and maintained are well-known in scientific knowledge. It was challenging to find the right sub-dimensions. Because the digital survey did not bring the expected dimensions, a list of sub-dimensions was established after reinvestigating the result of the thematic analysis and a study of the related maturity model to IT infrastructure automation; see Section 2.4. The selected sub-dimensions align with the way of working for automated workflow. However, validating these sub-dimensions is out of this research scope and remains an open avenue for future investigation.

In conclusion, the maturity model developed supports the five phases of control. However, it is up to organizations to decide how mature their automation must be and how much control is in the hands of a human.

7.7 Summary

This thesis's discussion and reflection chapter highlights the value of combining design science research with the Delphi method. Additionally, the value of the Delphi method is highlighted, where two different methods are used, namely qualitative semi-structured interviews and digital surveys. The combination of all methods fully supported the development of the maturity model for IT infrastructure automation. The interviews and the digital survey provided valuable information on the opinions and practices of subject matter experts. However, the survey did not yield a consensus on the dimensions of a maturity model. The updated IT infrastructure model also provided information on the structure of a modern IT landscape and the corresponding functions. The lack of standardization for automation in the IT infrastructure makes it challenging to achieve a higher level of maturity for levels four and five. However, the maturity model developed supports the five phases of control. However, it is up to organizations to decide how mature their automation must be and how much control should remain in the hands of a human.

8 Conclusions

In the introduction of this research thesis, the impact on business performance due to the lack of automation in IT infrastructure management is explained. Because of this lack of automation, the IT infrastructure is not repeatable and has a low speed of change and high human interaction and errors. Automating IT infrastructure management can alleviate these problems and has the following advantage for an organization; It reduces human error, increases security, provides faster and more flexible services, allows the possibility of keeping up with the competition, and can reduce overall complexity. Implementing automation and bringing it to a certain maturity level takes time and is best achieved in incremental steps. To guide this implementation, a maturity model can provide a clearly defined roadmap by describing the necessary steps. A maturity model also defines which resources, such as skills, processes, and support technologies, are needed for a certain level. The scientific body of knowledge lacks a maturity model for IT infrastructure automation.

This research proposes a maturity model for IT infrastructure automation. The scope of the maturity model is on the automation of the management of the IT infrastructure and is one of the research results and will be further addressed in the section on research findings. The proposed maturity model combines different maturity models grounded in scientific research, vendor-specific models, and the practical knowledge of various subject matter experts. Based on the collected data, a maturity model of five levels is developed, providing a roadmap for automation.

The maturity model's first level refers to the IT infrastructure's manual management without any automation. At the next level, some of the management tasks are automated. At level three, automation is the cornerstone of infrastructure management. At level four, automation is widespread, and policies and access management are handled per technology domain. However, at level five, the highest maturity level, IT infrastructure management becomes entirely policy driven. This increase in automation maturity enhances quality and productivity, strengthens a company's competitive advantage, and reduces IT complexity (Atchison, 2022).

Furthermore, by fully implementing policy-driven automation management, organizations can improve operational efficiency, reduce costs, and minimize errors caused by human intervention. It also enables IT teams to focus on higher-value tasks that require human expertise while automating repetitive and routine tasks. In addition, it ensures that automation is controlled and secure, minimizing the risk of errors or security breaches (SOCRadar_Research, 2023).

This chapter will briefly answer the sub-questions of this research in the next section on research findings. After this, the main research question was answered, which is:

MRQ: What dimensions and attributes constitute an IT infrastructure automation maturity model?

The remaining parts of the chapter address some limitations with respect to this research. They are followed by recommendations on how to implement IT infrastructure automation

in an organization's operations. Finally, some suggestions are presented for further research.

8.1 Research Findings

This research proposes an "IT infrastructure automation maturity model" for practical implementation guidance to help organizations define their current automation level and suggest a path to grow to the next level. Before the developed maturity model is discussed, the defined research questions are revisited to see if the research approach provides information to answer them appropriately.

The first two sub-questions are about the scope of this research. The first question is about the definition of an IT infrastructure. The second question is about what Automation is in the context of the defined IT infrastructure. These two sub-questions also define the environment as defined by the design science research methodology. A well-defined environment specifies the ranges of the maturity model. To not reinvent the wheel, the third question consults existing scientific and industry literature to see if maturity models are already available. The last two sub-questions are about the development of the maturity model.

RQ01 What is an IT infrastructure?

To answer this question, a literature study was conducted first. The literature study included the scientific literature and industry practitioners' literature. The theoretical framework constructed during this research study (see Chapter 2) embraced a comprehensive IT infrastructure overview. Different definitions for an IT infrastructure were found, but all described an IT infrastructure from the iron age. In the definitions found, the change in the IT infrastructure due to the introduction of the Cloud was not reflected. Additionally, some models that describe an IT infrastructure were identified. However, these included the same omissions: a strong focus on only technology, developed for the iron age and no automation.

The second step in answering this question was to interview seventeen subject matter experts and ask them about their views on the IT infrastructure in the cloud age. Based on their responses, a new IT infrastructure model was developed. An explorative research study and a digital survey are performed in the following step. In the exploratory research study, the author of one of the found models was asked for his opinion. Parallel to the digital survey, the developed model is validated by twenty-five subject matter experts. A new and updated IT infrastructure model and definition are developed based on all the collected data.

There are two adaptations in the IT infrastructure model and definition compared to the definitions of the theoretical framework. The first one is the place of PaaS; in the updated model and definition, PaaS is placed within the application platform. Today, PaaS is all about direct resource allocation and is directly related to applications. The second is the IT infrastructure, which can be seen as a comprehensive platform that provides only the resources needed for applications to operate.

The answer to this sub-question, a new definition of IT infrastructure in the cloud age, can be defined as follows:

An IT infrastructure platform is a shared foundation consisting of self-service APIs, tools, services, and knowledge. This foundation enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data. The platform comprises both virtual resources and supporting physical technology, which work together in an automated way to provide the necessary services and management environment.

Definition 8-1 IT Infrastructure (Final) (created by the researcher)

The IT infrastructure model that supports this definition is shown in Figure 69 IT infrastructure model version 3.

Figure 69 IT infrastructure model version 3 (created by the researcher).

RQ02 What is IT infrastructure automation?

The steps for answering this sub-question are almost the same as for the first sub-question, except there was no exploratory research. From the literature study, we can derive that automation is a broad and overarching topic in the scientific body of knowledge and the practical industry. After focusing on automation for the IT infrastructure, no information was found in the scientific body. However, the practical industry provided relevant

publications. Some examples include publications from infrastructure vendors such as VMWARE¹³, RedHat¹⁴, and Cisco¹⁵ and content found in technology blogs.

After reviewing the literature and the results of the interviews, the first concept of automation in the IT infrastructure is proposed and validated by the digital survey. Based on the collected data, some important conclusions can be drawn:

1. The IT infrastructure model incorporates three different types of automation (see Section 6.2). These types are defined as workflows, or also known as CI/CD pipelines.
2. IT infrastructure automation is about managing the IT infrastructure platform.

These conclusions are translated into a definition of automation in the IT infrastructure; this definition is as follows:

The IT infrastructure platform's automation consists of using software tools and technologies to automatically provision, configure, deploy, and manage physical and virtual resources such as servers, storage, and networking. It involves using automation tools, scripts, and workflows to perform provisioning, patching, and scaling tasks.

Definition 6-2 Automation for the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher)

In addition to the definition of automation in the IT infrastructure, a conceptual model is proposed. This model fits the three-automation workflows and shows the relations between the different layers. The model is presented in Figure 70 Conceptual model for automation workflows in the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher). The combination of the definition and the model answers this question.

¹³ <https://www.vmware.com>

¹⁴ <https://www.redhat.com>

¹⁵ <https://www.cisco.com>

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Figure 70 Conceptual model for automation workflows in the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher).

RQ03 What models of IT infrastructure automation maturity are available in the current scientific literature?

To answer this question, a literature study was conducted. The literature study included both scientific literature and industry practitioners' literature. Although there is a significant amount of scientific material on maturity models (see Section 1.5.2), there is very limited scientific research on IT infrastructure in combination with automation. This limitation holds for the iron age as well as for the cloud age. Also, no maturity model for automation itself is found. The industry body of knowledge contains more information on IT infrastructure, automation, and combining both. In addition to the literature study, the seventeen subject matter experts are asked during their interview if they are familiar with the maturity model for automation of the IT infrastructure. Participants did not propose models, although few pointed out the existence of other adjacent maturity models.

In answering this sub-question, within the industry's body of knowledge, one whitepaper is found that contains a maturity model for the automation of the IT infrastructure. In addition to this paper, other papers had relevant knowledge used to develop the maturity model. An overview is presented in Table 34.

The scientific body of knowledge	The industry body of knowledge
IT Infrastructure Maturity Model (ITTU-MM) (Haris, 2010)	Gartner IT Infrastructure and Operations Maturity Model (Scott et al., 2007)
Maturity Model for IT Management (Becker et al., 2009)	The Gartner Infrastructure Maturity Model. (Hidas, 2006)
Maturity Model for Implementing ITIL v3 (de Sousa Pereira & da Silva, 2010)	Cisco Digital Network Readiness Model (Greene et al., 2017)
Cloud Maturity Model (Dijk, 2017)	Cisco Network Automation Maturity (Pinto & Lacunza, 2021)

The scientific body of knowledge	The industry body of knowledge
DevOps Maturity Model (Radstaak, 2019)	Open Group Service Integration Maturity Model (Group, 2009)
	Netbrain Network Automation Maturity Model (Netbrain, 2022)
	Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (Quali, 2021)

Table 34 Overview of the used maturity model (created by the researcher).

RQ04 What are useful dimensions along which the maturity of IT infrastructure can be assessed?

The starting point for answering the fourth sub-question was the interviews with the seventeen subject matter experts. Based on their response analysis, a potential list of dimensions was created. A new list with potential dimensions was composed with the dimension for the IT infrastructure model (Haris, 2010) and the Cloud maturity model (Dijk, 2017). This list was submitted as part of the survey to subject matter experts. After analyzing the corresponding results, it was hard to distinguish which dimension was relevant.

In answer to question RQ02, IT infrastructure automation is defined, and the corresponding conceptual model offers a solution for answering this question. The conceptual model shows that the IT infrastructure has its own automation workflow. The dimensions that influence the workflow for IT infrastructure automation are people, processes, and technology. Every dimension consists of several sub-dimensions. These sub-dimensions are derived from the different maturity models, which are part of the theoretical foundation (see Section 2.4).

In Table 35, the answer to this sub-question is presented.

Dimensions	Sub-Dimensions
People	Knowledge and Skills
	Culture
Processes	Management
	Documentation
	Governance
	Compliance
	Policies
	Monitoring
	Analysis
	Service Level Agreement
	Ability to change
Technology	Deployment (Build and deploy)
	Provisioning
	Security
	Tasks (automation)

Table 35 Overview of dimensions and subdimension for the maturity model (created by the researcher).

RQ05 What are the useful attributes for each of these dimensions?

The initial approach for answering this sub-question was asking the seventeen subject matter experts about the most useful attributes. However, almost all experts had difficulties answering this question. In the collection of data from the interviews, no responses were provided to answer this question. Therefore, the decision was made not to include questions about attributes in the digital survey.

The answer to RQ04 defines dimensions and sub-dimensions. Based on the selected sub-dimensions, a study of different maturity models (see Section 2.4) has yielded the desired result. The answer to this question can be found in Section 6.4, which contains a detailed maturity model, including attributes for sub-dimension and every maturity level.

8.2 Answering the Main Research Question

The answers to the sub-questions provide the required information for answering the main research question:

MRQ: *Which dimensions and attributes constitute an IT infrastructure automation maturity model?*

The proposed maturity model has five levels that allow the automation to evolve. The maturity model levels are designed so that IT infrastructure management can mature from a standalone technology to a fully integrated cross-technological domain environment. This maturity model combines different maturity models grounded in scientific research, vendor-specific models, and the opinions of various subject matter experts. The model describes an improvement path for automation to mature, allowing a business to improve quality and productivity and increase its competitive advantage.

The proposed maturity model answers the main research question by defining three main dimensions: People, Processes, and Technology. The people dimension addresses the knowledge and skill needed to understand and implement different levels of automation. The technology dimension covers the technical aspects needed to operate and maintain an automated IT infrastructure platform. The process dimension concerns the structured and documented workflows that guide IT infrastructure management.

This maturity model is also vendor and technology agnostic despite the use of knowledge and influences for vendor-specific information. As a side effect, the model can be used to audit an IT infrastructure's automation.

A detailed version of the maturity model can be found in Section 6.4. while Figure 1 presents a more high-level version of the maturity model for IT infrastructure automation, followed by a brief description of each maturity level.

Figure 71 High-level overview of the maturity model for the automation of the IT infrastructure (created by the researcher).

Level 1 - Manual

At this level, IT infrastructure management is characterized by manual tasks, siloed components, and a hardware/device-centric approach. Device configurations and access management are fragmented, while visibility and centralized documentation are limited. Governance, SLAs, and processes are ad hoc and informal, making this level prone to errors and inefficient. Infrastructure changes can take weeks to months, and culture is reactive with no incentive for automation. Despite this, it serves as an essential starting point for organizations beginning their automation journey and can be used as a baseline for improvement.

Level 2 – Semi-Automated

At this level, there is a mix of manual and automated infrastructure management tasks, focusing on end-to-end hardware and device operations. Automation is available for basic device configurations, but policies and access management remain decentralized. Although some basic automation is in place, insight into the infrastructure is limited to alarms triggered at the device level. Infrastructure changes can take several days to weeks to complete. Documentation is available for each device, and scripts are managed per device. Teams have some knowledge of automation but lack experience in applying it. Some basic automation expectations exist, and governance processes are established and documented. Compliance is recognized as necessary, but policies and procedures may not be followed consistently. Standardization is increasing in decision-making, and SLAs are documented and applied consistently. There are some processes in place to track and report on SLA performance. Although this level represents a more systematic approach to infrastructure management and basic automation capabilities, it is still considered relatively inefficient and prone to errors. Despite this, organizations at this level may be able to handle larger-scale operations and respond more quickly to changes in infrastructure. However, organizations may still struggle with scalability and overall efficiency.

Level 3 – Automated

At this level, automation is the cornerstone of infrastructure management. Infrastructure components are managed using a combination of hardware-centric and software-centric approaches. Automation controls multiple devices at this level; access policies and management are centralized and clearly defined. Controller-based configurations provide insight into the infrastructure across the technology domain. Scripts are available for multiple components, and documentation is available per technology domain. Infrastructure changes are completed in hours to days. Individuals or teams understand automation well, and the culture is proactive and encourages automation. Employees are empowered to make decisions using automation in IT infrastructure management. Governance processes are well-established, documented, and compliance is consistently managed and enforced through formalized policies and procedures that are always followed. SLAs are well-defined, transparently tracked, and regularly analyzed to ensure that they align with business needs.

Organizations at this level of maturity have achieved a high degree of automation and a more centralized approach to infrastructure management, resulting in improved responsiveness to changes and increased visibility. However, there may still be some manual processes in place.

Level 4 – Service-based

At this level, the IT infrastructure is service-based and is managed through a software-centric approach. Automation is highly prevalent, with policies and access management handled per technology domain. Configuration is also managed similarly, with documentation available through version control document management systems. Individuals and teams are highly skilled in automation and can adapt their knowledge and skills to new situations, encouraging a culture of collaboration and continuous learning. Governance processes are fully integrated into IT infrastructure management, with metrics tracked and reported to ensure accountability. SLAs are actively managed, with robust processes to monitor and report performance. Although there may be some manual processes in place, the organization has achieved a high level of automation and efficiency, with the ability to quickly adapt to changes and prevent problems from occurring.

Level 5 – Policy-based

At this level of maturity, the infrastructure is characterized by a policy-driven approach operated through an integrated software-centric system. The organization has achieved complete automation and integration in all technologies domains. Automated and predictive insight into the infrastructure is provided, and cross-technology domain scripts are available for all components. Policies and access management are integrated across all technology domains, and the configuration is managed similarly. Documentation is automatically generated and is in the cross-technology domain, providing an easy way to keep track of changes and maintain a comprehensive understanding of the infrastructure.

Changes to the IT infrastructure can be made in seconds to minutes, allowing for a rapid response to changes. The organization has a strong culture of innovation that encourages

employees to think creatively and automate everything. Individuals or teams have a mastery of automation and can apply it in various situations.

SLAs are integrated into all aspects of the IT infrastructure platform and are seen as a driver to manage customer expectations and drive performance. Governance is a constantly evolving process integrated into all aspects of the IT infrastructure platform's operations. Compliance is also a continually evolving process integrated into all aspects of the organization's operations. Compliance metrics are used for continuous improvement, and compliance efforts are coordinated across all functions.

Organizations at this level of maturity have achieved a high level of automation, integration, and efficiency. They are well-equipped to handle complex IT infrastructure and manage it effectively and streamlined.

By establishing an IT infrastructure automation maturity model, this research provides a framework for organizations to assess their current level of IT infrastructure automation and identify improvement areas, ultimately strengthening their digital transformation efforts and being prepared to adopt these trends.

8.3 Research Limitations

This research has some limitations that must be acknowledged. Firstly, the research only covers IT infrastructure automation's "what" aspect without exploring the "how" in detail. This might limit the practical applicability of the research findings, which are mainly descriptive. Secondly, the lack of practical evaluation limits the discussion of the results, as the effectiveness of the proposed approach in real-world scenarios remains untested. Additionally, another limitation of this research is traceable to the fact that the research mainly took place in one geographical area, namely Europe, and with a bias of subject matter experts from a limited number of economies. This could limit the usefulness of the artifact developed. However, the researcher believes this impact is low since the different technologies used in IT infrastructures are standardized and used worldwide.

Furthermore, the limited accessibility of internal publications from vendors (such as Cisco, IBM¹⁶, and Microsoft¹⁷) and consulting firms (Forrester¹⁸ and Gartner¹⁹) and the lack of rigor in the field of automation and IT infrastructure management pose additional limitations.

In addition, this thesis only investigates the influence of automation on the maturity of the IT infrastructure. This influence is drawn in the conceptual model (Fig. 36). The model shows only the relationship between automation and the maturity of the IT infrastructure. In this research, other areas or topics that can potentially influence the maturity of an IT infrastructure are ignored. Therefore, the results may not be fully generalizable to the maturity of other parts of the IT landscape (see Figure 69) and only to the IT infrastructure.

¹⁶ <https://www.ibm.com>

¹⁷ <https://www.microsoft.com>

¹⁸ <https://www.forrester.com>

¹⁹ <https://www.gartner.com>

Finally, the factor of time is another limitation of this research. This research is carried out as part of a Master of Science dissertation and must be completed within a specific time frame. Due to this time constraint, the researcher could not perform practical artifact validation. When there was more time, the potential geographical bias and that of the subject matter experts could have been reduced by conducting a broader survey, which could have enhanced the credibility and generalizability of the findings.

8.4 Recommendations

As discussed in the previous sections, adopting an IT infrastructure automation maturity model can significantly benefit organizations' digital transformation initiatives. This section will provide recommendations for organizations that implement IT infrastructure automation in their operations. These recommendations are based on the findings of this research and consider both the practical use and scientific rigor of the proposed maturity model. Following these recommendations, organizations can improve the quality and efficiency of their IT infrastructure services, enabling them to stay competitive with the pace of automation trends and remain competitive in their respective industries.

The recommendations are as follows.

- Use the maturity model developed in this research as a framework to determine the current automation maturity level for the organization's IT infrastructure. Start with a comprehensive assessment of the organization's current IT infrastructure and identify areas that can be automated.
- Develop a roadmap for automation implementation in the IT infrastructure, considering the organization's priorities and available resources. Use the maturity model to determine the desired automation maturity level and identify the necessary steps to reach that level.
- Invest in training and development of the IT workforce to develop the skills and knowledge needed to implement and manage IT infrastructure automation.
- Implement automation in a phased approach, starting with low-risk and high-impact areas to build momentum and demonstrate the benefits of automation to the business.
- Continuously monitor and assess the effectiveness of automation initiatives, using the maturity model to track progress and identify areas for improvement.

8.5 Future Work

The current IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model research has established a foundation for future studies that can build on its findings. The following areas are suggested for future research:

Firstly, further development and validation of the IT infrastructure model should focus on exploring the "how" aspect of automation and conducting practical validation of the proposed artifact. This will help better understand how automation can be applied in different scenarios and identify potential issues that may arise during implementation.

Second, future research on the IT infrastructure model is required to adapt to the modern complex IT landscape. In a modern IT landscape, Platform as a Service may shift towards the Application Platform. There should also be further research on the position of PaaS to determine whether it still belongs to the IT infrastructure or is now part of the application platform.

Third, the different workflows of automation (CI/CD) should be further explored and validated, as it is essential to understand the impact of automation on different aspects of IT infrastructure management and within the IT landscape.

Fourth, further validation of the maturity model is needed to ensure its effectiveness and identify potential areas for improvement. This can involve testing the model in different contexts and industries to assess its applicability and usefulness.

Fifth, future research could also explore whether it is possible to reach level five of the maturity model and what challenges organizations can face in doing so.

Lastly, a broader survey could be conducted to reduce geographical and subject matter expert bias, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the maturity model's applicability in different contexts.

In conclusion, further research on the IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model can provide valuable insight for organizations to enhance their automation maturity levels and streamline their IT Infrastructure Management processes.

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10 Appendix – Transcripts of Interviews

10.1 Transcript 01

Date : October 3, 2022
Function : Enterprise Architect
Sector : Public Sector
Country : The Netherlands

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- The IT infrastructure is error sensitive.
- A lot of manual configuration work is involved.
- Not efficient because of a lot of manual work.
- Not agile.
- No knowledge of the current status of the IT infrastructure, automation provides you with that knowledge.
- Configuration parameters (attributes but also policies) are chosen upfront and can be enforced.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- For everything that has no knowledge and functionality of the company.
- It is generic and about technology.
- Everything that is physical hardware and/or logical hardware.
- IT infrastructure can be defined as Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), known from cloud technology.
- The IT landscape can be divided into two parts, where the dividing line is the operating system. Everything that is 'beneath' the operating system is the IT infrastructure, and above is part of the application landscape.

3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for IT infrastructure?*

- That every action is defined up-front, which means that it is known in advance how one will react to a certain circumstance, this all is scripted.

4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*

- In essence, there is no difference, but the physical hardware environment (IT infrastructure) is harder to script than the application environment.

- The philosophy of CI/CD (continuous integration/continuous deployment) from the application environment can be used in the IT infrastructure because the mechanism of unity testing can be very valuable.
 - Also, methodologies from the software world can be used in the IT infrastructure, but with a different use.
 - All knowledge (also known as policies) is only available in one place. There is one central truth.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? Do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
- a) The axis of functional richness, with five levels:
1. *Initial* - Ad-hoc, reactive, Unimaginable
 2. *Repeatable* – Project management, reactive
 3. *Defined* – Processes are defined, anticipated, and proactive.
 4. *Quality managed* – Processes are measured and controlled.
 5. *Optimized* - Focus on process improvement.
- b) *No*
6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*
- See the answer to question 4 and question 7.
7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

Level 0: Create a script and deploy it to 1 component/device.

Level 1: Create a script and deploy it to multiple components/devices.

Level 2: create a script that can be deployed to multiple technologies and multiple components/devices.

Level 3: central policy and deployment to the full IT infrastructure.

Level 4: Actions are predefined and central policy.

Level 5: Self-learning response for action and automatic adjustments.

10.2 Transcript 02

Date : October 5, 2022

Function : IT Manager

Sector : Public Sector

Country : The Netherlands

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- The IT infrastructure is error sensitive.
 - The change process takes a long time.
 - Lack of standardization, with too many technical depts.
 - Lack of assurance of IT continuity/disaster recovery
 - Not scalable.
 - Lack of noticeable compliance. There is no guarantee that the settings are set as intended.
2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*
- Within the Dutch government, we use a technical reference model. The lower layers of this model describe the IT infrastructure for me. They are the physical building layer, the network layer, the platform layer, and the middleware layer. But also, a small part of the application layer is the collaboration and messaging applications, which for me, are also part of the IT infrastructure.
 - Collaboration and messaging are part of the IT infrastructure mainly through the way the organization is constructed, and they are treated differently from a DevOps perspective.
3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*
- I see this from the perspective of a user/software developer and an IaaS/PaaS view. That is different from my answer to question 3.
 - Fully self-service for consumers of the IT infrastructure -> Software developers
 - API service for a 100% full self-service deployment cycle (CI/CD) of new and existing services.
 - Configuration of IT infrastructure capabilities based on standard templates and parameterized deployment scripts.
 - From an operational perspective, you can say that the IT infrastructure is fully aware of its status and can heal itself. Also known as pro-active health monitoring & self-remediation. As an example, automated triggers signal that there is a physical error of a component towards service engineers.
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
- There are four main differences:
 - *'Vertical dependencies'*
Application services are self-sustaining and use APIs from the environment for 'horizontal' dependencies. The infrastructure creates the condition for the application services, with the result that one configuration error can negatively hit all application services.
 - *Infra = cost driver, application services = business value*
Investments in the IT infrastructure have no direct business value. Application services deliver business value.

- *Bits versus atoms*
The financial impact of IT infrastructure hardware investments is huge and often has a value in the millions with a long depreciation period. Within the software culture, however, we see a throw-a-way approach.
 - *CI/CD for software developed with OTAP versus OTAP for hardware*
With software development, there often is an O (development), T (test), A (acceptance), and P (production) development used for the application development and deployment within the same IT infrastructure. But in almost all cases, there is no OTAP environment for the supporting IT infrastructure.
 - Both worlds are fundamentally different:
 - The software is infinitely scaled.
 - Software is dispensable.
 - Hardware cannot scale infinitely and is limited.
 - Hardware investments are expensive and have a long depreciation period.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
- A maturity model provides guidelines to assess your current status of maturity within the axis/dimensions of the model.
 - A maturity model defines maturity levels on multiple different dimensions. There are not all considered at the technology dimensions but also at the personal, organizational, process, and cultural dimensions.
 - A maturity model provides for every dimension of the model a description of the different maturity levels.
 - It may be handy for an IT infrastructure maturity model to provide a maturity per abstract building block (for TOAGF definition) of a technology layer. This way, an estimate can be made where investment is needed for automation. Also, which building block remains behind and is the first to be picked for improvement to make the next step in maturity?
 - A maturity model has five levels.
 - The maturity model should be built-up from a self-service point of view. How can you go from 100% to 0%.
6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*
- Proposal:
 - Level 1: Defined – There is a PDC of IT infrastructure services.
 - Level 2: IaaS – Basic Level
 - Level 3: IaaS – Advanced Level
 - Level 4: ??? - Reporting
 - Level 5: ??? – Self Healing

- Levels 1 – 3 are primary for delivering services to the end-user/developer
- Levels 4 – 5 are more for operating the IT infrastructure
- Technical aspect per capability (Architecture building block)
 - Level 1: extent to which the infra capability is described in an infra catalog
 - Level 1: the extent of standardization based on templates
 - Level 2: extend the scripted deployment
 - Level 3: the extent of self-service via APIs for DevOps
 - Level 4: extend billing and reporting for customers
 - Level 5: extend monitoring and self-healing
- Process/People/Culture
 - ITIL-processes -> extend processes manual or automated.
 - Skill and education level of people

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- Most important is that the topics are generic for every dimension, which makes scoring easier.

10.3 Transcript 03

Date : October 5, 2022
Function : IT Management
Sector : Information Technology
Country : United States of America

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- When there is no automation, “there is no hope!” Today, IT is too complex nowadays, and troubleshooting is almost impossible.
- You do not get consistent results; as a result, the IT landscape is unmaintainable.
- It is also very inefficient.
- You get different statuses in your IT landscape.
- Lower productivity.
- There are also security concerns, due to different patch levels.
- The greatest impact for the largest user group
 - Try to avoid errors and troubleshooting costs. Because there are not enough resources to solve the problem in an environment of more than 100 machines.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- That is every component necessary for people to do their job.

- Which is all the hardware, mobiles, and laptops.
 - But applications are also part of this.
 - It is all about the user(s); they are coming to you for a working environment.
3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*
- It is about producing a reproducible environment.
 - Where self-service is the seamless deployment of necessary applications.
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
- From the perspective that the IT Infrastructure also contains applications, then there is no difference.
 - It is an integrated environment.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
- You will never get there -> however, it is the ultimate goal.
 - It is about working towards a goal.
 - It is also more of a measurement tool.
 - It is about:
 - Skill level of people
 - Stages
 - There is no current model available.
6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

This answer is more about levels/stages.

- a. Level – Manual Stage
 - i. It is about unboxing and manual deployment.
- b. Level – Automate the process to deploy a component.
 - i. That is, installing the system software and applications. But there is no integration.
- c. Level – Automate the integration between the system software and the applications.
- d. Level – Everything is updated automatically.
- e. Level – Self-running/healing.

Levels 1 – 3 are about Day 1 operations.

Levels 4 – 5 are about Day 2 operations.

About the dimensions:

- Skill
- How invisible are you as an IT department?
- What it takes to deploy.
 - How much is needed to achieve this so that there is no follow-up?
 - This is so because there is a failure.
 - In level 5, there are no follow-ups.

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- Measure the compliance.

10.4 Transcript 04

Date : October 10, 2022
Function : IT Management
Sector : Information Technology
Country : France

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- IT has become more complicated/complex over the last (decade) years. For proper management, automation is needed.
- Also, the IT environment needs to be consistent.
- On the other hand, smart people always script everything. This has to do with the mindset of people.
- Without automation, it is hard to secure knowledge. If someone leaves, the company knowledge is still available.
- You need to build your IT environment from scratch when a major disaster occurs. That is not possible when there is no automation.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- The IT infrastructure is the skeleton (body) of the IT landscape and must support all the other layers that construct this landscape.
- Said differently, IT is the body, and the infrastructure is the bones.
- The IT infrastructure is everything that supports the business. That is the purpose of the IT infrastructure.
- The operating system is part of the IT infrastructure.

3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*

- It is about knowing (mastering) the status of your environment in a reproducible way.
 - It is about deploying, maintaining, and evolving your IT.
 - Automation is also about bringing all processes together.
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
- The IT infrastructure is about building the technical foundation for the applications.
 - The applications are an additional layer for a good user experience.
 - And are deployed with a CI/CD pipeline.
 - Also, the applications are about business value, where the IT infrastructure is there to support and serve the application.
 - When you look at the IT infrastructure and CI/CD that is all about patching.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
- Maturity scale
 - Worst situation:
 - Documentation lacks
 - Manually
 - No scripts.
 - No list of assets.
 - No CMDB
 - Best situation:
 - Every component is in exactly the required state.
 - There is a difference between cloud and on-premises:
 - With the cloud, everything is code; even the IT infrastructure is code.
 - With on-premises, you need local 'hands-on' and all else is code.
 - Intermediate states:
 - Scripted
 - Installation and configuration of OS
 - Scripting
 - Adding policy's
 - Security
 - Compliance
 - Maintenance
 - Collecting state and logging
 - Monitoring
 - But not more than five levels.
 - Automating to evolve must also be a part of the model.

- That can be translated to upgrade newer versions automatically, but also validate if an upgrade is allowed at that moment in time for that component, and even inform the correct people.

6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

- Operating Automation
- Configuration Automation
- Policy Automation
- Monitoring Automation
- Security Automation

- But most important is the mindset, it is all about the people. Smart people automate their work, especially when there are repetitive tasks.
- Automation is not a one-shot approach, and it is a continuous driver. The states need to be checked continuously.

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- There are no topics explicitly mentioned. But see the answers to Questions 5 & 6.

10.5 Transcript 05

Date : October 12, 2022
Function : Enterprise Architect
Sector : Public Sector
Country : The Netherlands

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- Indeed, there is a problem. The biggest problem is there is no knowledge and the labor market.
- When the IT infrastructure is not automated, and the rest of the IT landscape is, then a bottleneck will arise. The whole IT landscape is a chain.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- It is the foundation of your information provision.
- The data and the applications live here and are available for the end user.
- Consists of:
 - Physical hardware
 - Virtual Hardware

- Operating system
 - Also, monitoring and security are part of the IT infrastructure.
 - The operating system for the IT infrastructure also includes DNS and directory services.
3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*
- The real question is, to what extent can we automate activities?
There are two functional characteristics:
 1. Repeating activities
 2. Predictable Activities
 - The IT infrastructure must be offered as a service towards the other part of the IT landscape.
 - Automation is also about knowing the state and having predefined actions for that state.
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
- The application layer is about:
 - Low code, which is program automation.
 - Continuous integration/continuous deployment.
 - There is also a relationship between the IT infrastructure and the components. It is a Chain.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
- There are different maturity models:
 1. Decide where you are.
 2. Prescriptive
 3. Benchmark ModelsThe combination of numbers 1 & 2 is mainly seen in maturity models.
 - The model also needs to be flexible.
Thus, it is possible to adapt it to an organization.
Matrix-based models are very static. Even when a part has a more mature level, the whole is examined on a lower level.
Developing a model based on a spider diagram is nicer to overcome this inflexibility, where each part can be rated independently.
 - Also, look at the ESSA strategy:
 - Eliminate
 - Simplify
 - Standardize
 - Automated

- To the best of his knowledge, there are no maturity models available for the automation of the IT infrastructure.
- The interviewee has also written a master thesis on the maturity model, 'A multi-criteria decision-making model for EA maturity models in the context of Industry 4.0' (Haaster, 2020).
Available at: <https://theses.liacs.nl/1753>
- Five levels would be excellent.
- And ask the question do you need to be at the maximum maturity level?

6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

- Interesting dimensions are:
 - Technology
 - Processes
 - People
 - Context

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- An interesting topic is:
 - Repeatability

10.6 Transcript 06

Date : October 12, 2022
Function : IT Infrastructure Architect
Sector : Information Technology
Country : United States of America

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- If you do not have automation, it takes time to perform a task.
 - This is all about labor costs.
- Also, human error is a cost factor. When there is no automation, the cost of correcting errors can be high.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- The IT infrastructure is everything people need to have access to.
 - It is about physical hardware, servers, desktop, laptop, etc.
 - But also about collaborating tools and, on the other hand, connectivity to a service provider.

- It is a combination of services.
 - It is an environment where people/users are involved. When there is a problem in the IT infrastructure, all people/users are most directly affected. That is different by applications, there are mostly partial people/users affected.
3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*
- It's replaced manual work.
 - There is only one place to touch for doing the 'work'.
 - It is all about the state. In a prescriptive way, you can define the state, and via monitoring, you can determine if the IT infrastructure is in the correct state. If not, you can define how to react.
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
- Application automation is easier, and it is software talking to software.
 - IT infrastructure automation is harder, and it is software talking to hardware.
 - You also need to involve an employee so that automation can take place.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
- Worst mature level:
 - Manual work/tasks
 - Reactive
 - You don't know the state of the IT infrastructure.
 - Most mature level:
 - No manual work/tasks
 - Proactive
 - You know the exact state of the IT infrastructure.
 - An important indicator here is the state.
 - Is it effective and cost-effective to automate tasks that can be easily conducted manually? There needs to be a balance. There must also be a balance between the time you want to spend automating the task and the benefit you get from it.
6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*
- Monitoring:
 - How reliable is your IT infrastructure?
 - Culture:
 - If 'its breaks', you need to be motivated to improve the environment at once so that it does not happen again.

- Also, the mindset to automate repeating tasks.
- Security:
 - Code review
- Standardization

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- One of the attributes or topics is the number of errors that occur and cause problems for people.
- The number of standards.

10.7 Transcripts 07 and 08

Date : October 14, 2022
Function : IT Infrastructure Architect
Sector : Information Technology
Country : The Netherlands

Date : October 14, 2022
Function : IT Management
Sector : Information Technology
Country : The Netherlands

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- Looking from IT to Business, the IT landscape has been parceled out or is isolated (siloeed). There is no collaboration between the different components.
- When you go from business to IT, it is about requesting services. A self-service approach.
- The main problem is that there is no standardization. You need to standardize if you want automation.
- In the upper layers of the IT landscape, the speed of change is high, and when you do not have automation in the lower layers of the IT landscape, there is no ability to adapt at the same speed. The changes are then very slow and do not support the rapidly changing environment of the upper layers.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- The IT infrastructure is Hybrid. A combination of local on-premises IT infrastructure and cloud IT infrastructure can be seen as the lowest layer inside of the IT landscape. The application layer and the information layer. This is depicted below.

- The move from the 'old' IT infrastructure to the Hybrid IT infrastructure

- The collaboration tool is part of the application layer and is placed on top of the IT infrastructure layer.
- A modern workspace is in the end part of the application layer. Because it consists of collaboration tools and office applications, it is also a business need.

3. From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?

- Technology automation is about simplifying technology and defining how technology works.
- Process automation is about the reduction of manual operations.
- Automation is about performing repeating tasks in a systematic and fast way. This approach helps to standardize.
- Automation is also about documentation and sharing knowledge.
- With automation, you have more control of operational IT infrastructure, and it is easier to monitor the state during a change and deployment of new components.
- Provides a single source of truth.

4. Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?

- There is a difference in the characteristic between the automation for the application environment and the IT infrastructure environment.
- The purpose is the same, but how it is executed is different.
- There is a clear relationship between both. In modern solutions, the automation of the application environment triggers the automation of the IT infrastructure environment. For example, when an application needs more resources, it asks the infrastructure to scale up the necessary resources.

5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*

- Preferable between 3 to 5 levels.
- Level 1 – Everything is manually configured and operated.
- Level 2 – Everything is standardized but still manually configured and operated.
- Level 3 – Everything is standardized but automated, configured, and operated.
- Level 4 – Everything is standardized but policy-based controlled, configured, and operated.
- Level 5 – Everything is autonomously configured and operated.

6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

- Dimensions are:
 - Governance
 - How good are you in requirement engineering?
 - Operation
 - Processes
 - State of technology

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- It is about KPI's but is hard to answer currently.

10.8 Transcript 09

Date : October 20, 2022
Function : IT Infrastructure Architect
Sector : Research and development
Country : The Netherlands

Response to the following questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- The biggest problem with automation is time. That can be seen from two perspectives. First, you need time to implement automation. This is not an easy task, and often it is a reactive response (after there is an implementation). If automation is implemented, then there is the benefit of having more time. The second perspective, there is the mindset, you need to have the mindset and the ability to think abstractly.
- New technologies nowadays come with automation included. But it is the automation of a single product(line) and not based on standards. This prevents automation integration between products from a single vendor and between products from different vendors. All the automation solutions are still pointing solutions.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- The IT infrastructure is the basis, the fundament, and the lowest layer.
- It is hardware but includes the system's software, which is necessary for operation.
- Also, it includes the IT department applications, supporting applications such as helpdesk software, and the software necessary for packaging and distributing other business applications.

3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*

- "Everything you must do more than once, you must automate". This is true on a component level, multi-component, and also multi-technology.
- There is one source of information for configuring the entire IT infrastructure.

4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*

- With IT Infrastructure Automation, there is an interaction between the system software and the hardware.
- Application automation has no direct interaction with hardware.

5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*

- There are two main states:
 - Not Passive Stable
The 'system' (in this case, the IT infrastructure) does not know how to react and handle all statuses.

- Passive Stable
The 'system' (in this case, the IT Infrastructure) does know by itself how to react and handle all statuses.
 - And there are one or more states in between where the 'system' knows how to react and handle a number of all statuses.
 - Ideally, there are 4 to 6 levels of maturity.
 - Level 1: Not passively stable
 - Level 2: Local Passive Stable
 - Level 3: Partial Passive Stable
 - Level 4: Passive stable
6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*
- The following dimensions can be defined:
 - Controllable
 - As an example: OpenStack
 - Easy deployment
 - As an example: Apple's total integration of software and hardware.
 - Automatability
 - As an example: APIs and documentation
 - Integrability with the environment
 - Examples: APIs, LDAP, etc.
 - Scalability
 - As an example: OpenStack
 - And systems are built modular.
 - Supplier reliability
 - agreements are fulfilled
 - flexible within the maintenance contract;
 - Vendor Reliability
 - Quick Support
 - Possibility to run the system on premises v.s. cloud
 - Migration possibility
 - Examples: APIs, LDAP, etc.
 - Exportability
 - As an example: APIs, open data model
7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*
- See answers to question 6

10.9 Transcript 10

Date : October 21, 2022
Function : IT Network Architect
Sector : Public
Country : The Netherlands

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- The Dutch government uses an architecture reference framework called NORA (https://www.noraonline.nl/wiki/NORA_online). This framework consists of 5 layers.
- To have a consistent execution of the business demands (the upper layer) towards the technology (the lower layer), you need an automated way of working. Manual execution introduces errors and is not consistent.
- Another problem is that there is no standardization for the automation integration of different technologies.
- Also, with processes, there is a difference between what is asked and what is delivered. Automation helps to define and structure the implementation and overcomes semantic problems.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- The NORA framework consists of 5 layers; the lowest layer is the Technology layer. The IT infrastructure is placed within this layer.
- But the difference between the application layer (number 4) and the technology layer is not a hard line. This distinction has diminished in recent years.

3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*

- Automation is all actions executed after a manual action and without manual intervention.
- Every action that can be performed manually or semi-manually needs to be automated.
- Every variable and parameter must be unique.
- And it is more an application/software 'thing' than a hardware 'thing'.

4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*

- For me, there is no difference.

5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the*

assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?

- There are three levels:
 - Level 1: Manual-state infrastructure
 - Needs a lot of coordination (Response and action) between the different parts and technologies of the infrastructure.
 - Level 2: Normalized Infrastructure
 - The interaction between different parts and technologies of the infrastructure is standardized.
 - Level 3: Fully automated infrastructure
 - The infrastructure acts as one 'system'. Coordination (Response and action) between the different parts and technologies is clearly defined.

6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

- Dimensions are:
 - Governance
 - Actions:
 - How many manual actions are there?
 - What is the reason behind these manual actions?
 - Consistency vs. Compliance
 - How many deviations are there concerning the preferred state?
 - Robustness
 - Failure rate
 - Resiliency

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- See the answer to Question 6.

10.10 Transcript 11

Date : October 21, 2022
Function : Enterprise Architect
Sector : Utility
Country : Belgium

Response to the following questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- Many manual procedures are expensive. In this way, deployments are expensive.
- There is no consistency in the deployment.
- There is almost no maintenance of documentation.

- The quality must be lower because there is no unambiguous way of working.
- Also, the IT landscape's complexity is increasing, making it impossible to properly manage and expand the landscape manually.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- Use the definition from the book of Sjaak Laan, "IT Infrastructure Architecture - Infrastructure Building Blocks and Concepts Third Edition" (Laan, 2017). Where he writes that depends on your point of view.

A more detailed description of the IT infrastructure from his book is shown below.

- Also, see my research paper 'Applying Generalized Normalized Systems Theory to Engie' IT Reference Architecture Library' (Haerens, 2016), where it is defined as 'IT Infrastructure = Physical Infrastructure + Software Infrastructure'
- The IT landscape can also be divided into three main parts, namely:
 - SAAS (Software as a Service)
 - Applications, but also mail and SharePoint.
 - PAAS (Platform as a Service)

- Are different services, like web services and database services
 - IAAS (Infrastructure as a Service)
 - Are hardware and operating software?
 - There is a dividing line between SAAS and PAAS where PAAS and IAAS constitute the IT infrastructure.
 - Applications (SAAS) are related to the business. The IT infrastructure is what is necessary to run that business.
3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for the 'IT infrastructure'?*
- Automation is something you see in the deployment part of the IT Infrastructure. This part of the IT infrastructure is also known by the term 'Control Plane.
 - The 'control plane' is the 'place' where 'everything' must be automated.
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
- Automation for the applications is managed and developed by different teams with different knowledge than IT infrastructure.
 - Applications are, in essence, the 'tools' to deliver business value and, from this perspective, are almost part of the business.
 - When there is a failure in an application, then just adjusting the (source) code is enough to overcome it.
 - Furthermore, the application only 'lives' in the 'data plane' of the IT infrastructure.
 - At the IT infrastructure level, when a failure is uncovered during a deployment, the deployment needs to be rerolled and again deployed.
 - Also, it is very hard to do unit testing in the IT infrastructure, which is very common in applications.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
- Preferable between 3 to 5 levels.
 - A maturity model has a few conditions which, after assessment, you can use to determine the right level, and it describes what is necessary to grow to the next level.
 - When you move to the next level, 'everything' becomes easier.
 - To the best of our knowledge, there is currently no available maturity model for the automation of the IT infrastructure.
 - The levels can be:
 - Level 0 – Everything is deployed manually, and there is no documentation.
 - Level 1 – There are deployment procedures.

- Level 2 – There are deployment procedures and scripts to automate some deployment steps.
- Level 3 – There are deployment procedures and scripts to automate the deployment steps, and there is documentation.
- Level 4 – Zero-touch deployment (incl. procedures and documentation)

6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

- Dimensions are as follows:
 - Deployment
 - Monitoring
 - Knowledge, especially product knowledge.
 - Programming Knowledge

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- Currently, there is no idea, and it depends on the outcome of this research...

10.11 Transcript 12

Date: October 16, 2022

Function: IT Cyber Security

Sector: Public Sector

Country: The Netherlands

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

Indeed, there are problems:

- When there is no automation, all components have no homogeneous behavior. This can cause surprises during maintenance.
- From a cyber-security point of view, the configuration of your components could violate the applicable guidelines.
- Manual configuration is costly and leads to sloppiness.
- Your IT environment is not reproducible. This can have a severe impact when trying to recover from an incident.
- When an organization is not investing or already has automation, it tells you something about the maturity of the organization.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- *Interaction of different IT components that facilitate IT processes.*

- *The IT components are:*
 - *All hardware and corresponding software, such as operating systems and supporting applications.*
 - *Depending on your point of view, you can see that there is layering. The interaction between these layers is the IT infrastructure.*
 - *The IT infrastructure does not have a direct relationship with the business. We can say that the infrastructure has no business context. It facilitates and supports applications related to business and the supporting processes.*
3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*
- Automation needs to support the lifecycle of an IT component, which contains three stages:
 1. Deployment
 - Easy and (almost) zero-touch configurations
 2. Operations
 - Validate if the configuration does not violate the compliance and security rules.
 3. Decommissioning
 - Properly deletion of the configuration
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
- The application layer is dependent on the IT infrastructure layer. As a result, there are two different automation environments.
 - In the application layer, the changes are fast and volatile; it is a very dynamic environment.
 - In the infrastructure layer, changes are slow and planned; it is a very static environment.
 - Due to these distinctive characteristics, both layers have other deployment mechanisms and, as a result, separate ways of automation.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
- An interesting question here is how much knowledge a software developer needs for the IT infrastructure before they can deploy their applications.
 - As you mature, you need less knowledge of the IT infrastructure to deploy the application. Because the more mature you are, the more automation takes care of.
 - Let us say there are three maturity levels:
 - Level 0 - Manually
 - The application developer needs a professional level of knowledge of the IT infrastructure.
 - Level 1 - Coordination

- The application developer needs partial knowledge of the IT infrastructure and coordinates the deployment with the IT infrastructure.
 - Level 2 – Automatic
 - The application developer does not need knowledge of the IT infrastructure. Some services can be used to automate the deployment fully.
6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

1. Knowledge of the stakeholder
 - (Business) Users
 - Developers
2. Functional automation
 - Day-2-day operations
 - Zero-trust
3. Non-functional automation
 - Logging
 - Monitoring
 - security
4. Robustness
 - Recovery without lost data lost.
 - Speed of recovery – 1 day/week/month

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- See the answer to question 6.

10.12 Transcript 13

Date: October 27, 2022

Function: IT Cloud Architect

Sector: Utility

Country: Belgium

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- That depends on the size and business of the organization(enterprise):
 - At small organizations, you do not spend much time on automation.
 - At large organizations, you do spend time on automation.
 - When an organization has a data center, you spend a lot of time automating because automating bare metals is hard.
 - Cloud companies spend a lot of time in automation because it is easier, and it is their business.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*
 - The IT infrastructure is the most technologically advanced part of the IT landscape. It has all the hardware, servers, storage, and network and supports business applications. Currently primarily known as IaaS and PaaS, the (empty) databases are also part of the IT infrastructure.
 - Applications have a direct relationship with the business and use SaaS.
3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*
 - Automation is, in an automated way, provisioning and deployment of configurations to the different components.
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
 - It starts with IT infrastructure and ends with applications.
 - There is no difference in automation on many levels, and it depends on the technologies you are using.
 - In automation, you make use of a pipeline, the well-known CI/CD principle. The software can confirm your configuration, for example, to check compliance. This is not common in the IT infrastructure.
 - When using cloud technology, there is a difference; with cloud technology, everything is provisioned and deployed with the use of automation, the (virtual) IT infrastructure, and the application. The IT infrastructure is mostly not provided with automation if you have one data center.
 - There is a genuine shift from left to right for security. When using a pipeline, the checks are mainly at the end, just before deployment. When integrating the IT infrastructure into the pipeline (or combining the two), security checks can be done earlier in the process, and that is what the change means. However, this is currently a best practice, and it can be of interest to integrate this into a maturity model.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? Do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
 - For me, a maturity model is to assess the current state based on KPIs. This can help to see if there is room for improvement in the next step of the model.
 - You can easily switch your cloud IT infrastructure to another provider if you are mature enough. This only works in a native cloud IT landscape.
 - The high level of maturity is when the systems in the IT infrastructure can heal themselves. That detects and responds to states.

6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

- An essential dimension is 'Documentation'; even when everything is 'running' without problems, but you don't have any documentation, you have nothing.
- Other dimensions are:
 - Knowledge
 - Compliance
 - People
 - Skill Level

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- These can also be seen as KPIs.
- One KPI can be the number of deployments:
 - How small are the deployments? The more mature the number of deployments in a shorter timeframe, the more mature.
 -
 - Deployment Speed:
 - The more traditional the IT infrastructure, the slower the pace.
 - And they have primarily big changes at once.
- Number of the failed test (see as an example infrastructure as code)
- The organization of the team
- How easily can knowledge be transferred to new team members?

10.13 [Transcript 14](#)

Date: October 27, 2022

Function: Enterprise Architect

Sector: Information Technology

Country: The Netherlands

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- An issue is that there is no uniformity and, as a result, no consistency.
- Manual 'work' also introduces many errors; automation can prevent this.
- On the other hand, manual 'work' also costs a lot of time.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- The IT infrastructure is something, from my point of view, that must be there. Let us say it is a utility that must be there based on standard products and working according to standards.

- It is also very technological.
 - It is the primary layer on which the applications run.
 - From a self-service point of view, it is (as a whole) a platform.
3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*
- With automation, the pace of change can be increased; if you compare this with applications, modification can be added very quickly due to automation. Although the IT infrastructure is very static, automation can increase the speed of changes due to its nature.
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
- These are two different fields of work.
 - From my point of view, the IT infrastructure is delivered by a provider.
 - Applications must be able to use the services of the IT infrastructure.
 - The IT infrastructure does not have a direct business context and supports the application, which is business context aware.
 - As pointed out in question 3, the IT infrastructure and application layers have their own heartbeat.
5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*
- A maturity model defines where you are, how you can grow, and what steps you need to take.
 - You can also see this as a reference framework for growth/evolution.
 - If you develop a maturity model, it must be practical and give you helpful guidance.
 - A model with a granularity of 5 levels will suit this best.
6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*
- Connectivity
 - Interaction with others, not only from a technological perspective.
 - Security
 - It must have a place early in the model.
 - Collaboration with partners/vendors with the same maturity level.
 - Level 0: Chaos
 - Development and maintenance are based on craftsmanship.
 - Level 1:
 - There are standard solutions.

- Level 2:
 - There are standards.
- Level 3:
 - Solutions are based on standards.
- Level 4:
 - Everything is standardized.
- Level 5:
 - Automation is a business spearhead.
 - You are growing along with the standards.

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- Cost factor
 - If you are more mature, you need to ask yourself, how much may it (automation) cost for you as a business?

10.14 [Transcript 15](#)

Date: October 27, 2022

Function: IT Infrastructure Architect

Sector: Information Technology

Country: The Netherlands

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- The most significant lack is that there is no standardization of automation, which prevents interoperability between different vendors' solutions.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- The IT infrastructure provides multiple consumers, incl. Humans and automated systems, with generic IT services without business context.

3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*

- Automation automates routine actions to monitor and maintain the IT infrastructure.

4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*

- As answered in question 3, the same can be said for the automation of the application environment.

5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*

- There are different maturity frameworks, and two are mentioned in TOGAF 9.2 (<https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/togaf91-doc/arch/chap51.html>):
 - CMMI & ACMM
 - See also;
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Capability_Maturity_Model_Integration

Characteristics of the Maturity levels

- - Maturity is the degree to which the required actions are predictable and effective. A level tells which is the case for different components.
 - A maturity model helps make choices about the level of ambition and priorities.
 - You can use a maturity model to compare departments or companies.
 - A maturity model must have enough granularity and has mostly 4 – 7 levels.

6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

- Dimensions are:
 1. The Architecture of the Automation (itself)
 2. Security
 3. Governance
 4. Documentation
 5. Predictability
 6. Traceability

7. Adaptability -> Easy to Adjust
8. Robustness -> systems keep operating even when there is an error.

- There are two forms:
 1. Matrix, assessing all dimensions to define the level of maturity.
 2. Superdiagram, assessing per dimension the level of maturity.

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- See Question 6.

10.15 Transcript 16

Date: November 4, 2022

Function: Enterprise Architect

Sector: Information Technology

Country: The Netherlands

Response to the following questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- The IT landscape is too different.
 - That is the reason why you can get a grip on it.
 - For many parts of the IT landscape, there is no standard.
 - Every part has its own standard.
 - Parametrizing is due to that reason not standardized.
 - This is also valid for the cloud.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- There is currently almost no difference between the IT infrastructure and the other part of the IT Landscape.
- You can see the IT infrastructure layer and the application layer.
- The IT infrastructure (layer) does not perform functions directly for the business; the application layer does this.

3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*

- This must provide self-service; in the background, everything is arranged.
- The cloud principles can explain the latest:
 - Broad-network
 - Elasticity
 - Measured Service

- On-demand Self-Service
 - Resource Pooling
 - => <https://onacloudoftheirown.wordpress.com/2016/01/29/cloud-computing-as-easy-as-5-4-3/>
 - Or the Seven Principles of Cloud-Native Architecture
 - Service-Oriented Design
 - Elasticity
 - Observability
 - Resilience
 - Automation of All Procedures
 - Zero Trust
 - Continuous Evolution of Architecture
 - => https://www.alibabacloud.com/blog/seven-principles-of-cloud-native-architecture_598431
4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*
- The characteristics of both are different.
 - Automated configuration in the IT infrastructure is mainly done via API's.
 - Automation for applications is more about building the application and not configuring it.
5. *What is a maturity model for you? Do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use? This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model.*
- Preferable three levels;
 - First level – Manual parameterization of components
 - Second level – Automated parameterization of components
 - Third level – Patron recognition based on AI and automated adjusting and parameterization of components
 - See <https://www.ccoverheid.nl/documenten/synalysekernmodel.pdf> for inspiration on maturity models and levels.
 - The Kruchten architecture model contains five levels for applications:
 - <https://medium.com/globant/kruchten-architecture-model-2f95d0da1c7>
6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*
- Look also at the Open Infrastructure Architecture Repository for dimensions ideas:
 - https://www.infra-repository.org/oiar/index.php/Main_Page
7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*
- See <https://patterns.arcitura.com/devops-metrics-mechanisms-tools>

- [Active Nodes](#)
- [Blocks Per Hour, Blocks Per Day](#)
- [Total Node/Partial Node Ratio](#)
- [Transaction Latency](#)
- [Transactions Per Second](#)
- [Transaction Throughput](#)
- [Unique App Downloads](#)

10.16 Transcript 17

Date: November 11, 2022

Function: IT Cloud Architect

Sector: Utility

Country: Belgium

Response to questions:

1. *What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?*

- The goal must be compliance by design.
 - Key areas are configuration and security.
- There is no manual configuration, so there is more time for development and innovation.
- The intention must be to automate everything, but that is probably impossible.
- It is also a culture, say, a way of thinking. The antithesis is DevOps.
- The move to the cloud accelerates automation. It is in the DNA of the cloud.
- One of the challenges is the processes. When processes are not adapted to the automated way of working, the automation does not work as expected. This is mainly the case when human approval is needed somewhere in the process.

2. *Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?*

- Around ten years ago, the IT infrastructure was built from different systems, servers, storage, and networks. But nowadays, it can be seen as one system with these integrated functions of servers, storage, and networks.
- IT infrastructure is hardware and software that runs directly on that hardware.

3. *From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?*

- Automation allows you to sleep at night, lets you go on vacation, and gives you time to think.
- Automation delivers the expected result in a repeatable way.
- Automation also reduces manpower but does not replace it.

4. *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*

- In the goal, there is no difference (time and repeatability)
- The difference is in the implementation; you must adapt to the context.
- The speed of deployment in the on-premises world is different from that in the cloud. The cloud application and IT infrastructure are seen and handled the same. The IT infrastructure is seen as code (also known as Infrastructure as Code), and the application is also code.

5. *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*

- The pillars of a maturity model could be:
 - People know how to automate.
 - Culture is the mindset of how to automate and do it each time.
- Also, there is a paradigm shift from DevOps to NoOps (<https://news.beta80group.it/en/noops-what-it-is-and-how-it-will-change-it-operation-in-the-next-future>)
 - NoOps refers to a situation where an IT environment becomes so automated from the underlying infrastructure using technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, data analytics, and effective disaster recovery that there is no need for a dedicated team to manage software in-house. (https://www.alibabacloud.com/blog/noops-the-reason-for-a-paradigm-shift-in-it-operations_597389)
- A mature department can identify what is needed to automate and what is done by a human. But over time, the human part is reduced in iterative processes.
- A more mature IT infrastructure can check if it complies with company policies. The next step can be to have the automation fix errors.

6. *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

- Measuring
- Empowerment/leadership to enforce automation.
- Culture
- Knowledge
- Every automation must be bulletproof.
 - The KPI can be the failure rate or the test coverage.
- Observability
 - Getting insight into the system because not monitoring is old school.

7. *From your point of view, what are the attributes or topics of each dimension?*

- See Question 6

11 Appendix – Thematic Analysis of Interviews

11.1 Thematic Analysis for Interview Question 1

Interview question 1: What do you think is the problem with the lack of automation in the IT infrastructure?

Answers	Theme
<p>A lot of manual configuration work is involved.</p> <p>Many manual procedures are expensive. In this way, deployments are expensive.</p> <p>The quality must be lower because there is no unambiguous way of working.</p> <p>Manual configuration is costly and leads to sloppiness.</p> <p>Manual 'work' also introduces many errors; automation can prevent this.</p> <p>There is no manual configuration, so there is more time for development and innovation.</p>	Manual Work
<p>The IT infrastructure is error sensitive. (2x)</p> <p>Try to avoid errors and troubleshooting costs.</p>	Error sensitive
<p>No knowledge of the current status of the IT infrastructure, automation provides you with that knowledge.</p> <p>When there is no automation, all components have no homogeneous behaviour. This can cause surprises during maintenance.</p> <p>You get different statuses in your IT landscape.</p>	State of the system (where system is the IT infrastructure)
<p>Configuration parameters (attributes but also policies) are chosen upfront and can be enforced.</p>	Configuration
<p>The change process takes a long time.</p> <p>In the upper layers of the IT landscape, the speed of change is high, when you do not have automation in the lower layers of the IT landscape, there is no on-time ability to adapt. The changes are then very slow and do not support the rapidly changing environment of the upper layers.</p> <p>When an organization has a data centre, you spend a lot of time automating because automating bare metals is hard.</p> <p>Cloud companies spend a lot of time in automation because it is easier, and it is their business.</p>	Low pace / Low speed of change

<p>Lack of standardization, with too many technical depts.</p> <p>The main problem is that there is no standardization. You need to standardize if you want automation.</p> <p>New technologies nowadays come with automation included. But it is the automation of a single product(line) and not based on standards. This prevents automation integration between products from a single vendor and between products from different vendors. All the automation solutions are still pointing solutions.</p> <p>Another problem is that there is no standardization for the automation integration of different technologies.</p> <p>An issue is that there is no uniformity and, as a result, no consistency</p> <p>The most significant lack is that there is no standardization of automation, which prevents interoperability between different vendors' solutions.</p> <p>For many parts of the IT landscape, there is no standard.</p> <p>Every part has its own standard.</p> <p>Parametrizing is due to that reason not standardized. This is also valid for the cloud.</p>	<p>No Standardization</p>
<p>You do not get consistent results; as a result, the IT landscape is unmaintainable.</p> <p>You get different statuses in your IT landscape.</p> <p>Environment needs to be consistent.</p> <p>There is no consistency in the deployment.</p>	<p>Consistency</p>
<p>Lack of noticeable compliance. There is no guarantee that the settings are set as intended.</p> <p>There are also security concerns, due to different patch levels.</p> <p>From a cyber-security point of view, the configuration of your components could violate the applicable guidelines.</p> <p>The goal must be compliance by design; o Key areas are configuration and security.</p>	<p>Compliance</p>
<p>When there is no automation, “there is no hope!” Today, IT is too complex nowadays, and troubleshooting is almost impossible. IT has become more complicated/complex over the last (decade) years.</p>	<p>IT infrastructure is nowadays to complex</p>

Also, the complexity of the IT landscape is increasing, and this makes it impossible for it to properly manage and expand the landscape manually.

Around ten years ago, the IT infrastructure was built from different systems, servers, storage, and networks. But nowadays, it can be seen as one system with these integrated functions of servers, storage, and networks.

The IT landscape is too different.

When an organization is not investing or already has automation, it tells you something about the maturity of the organization.

The intention must be to automate everything, but that is probably impossible.

It is also a culture, say, a way of thinking. The antithesis is DevOps.

Without automation, it is hard to secure knowledge. If someone leaves, the company knowledge is still available.

Certainly, there is a problem. The biggest problem is, there is no knowledge and the labour market.

There is almost no maintenance of documentation.

On the other hand, smart people always script everything. This has to do with the mindset of people.

If you do not have automation, it takes time to perform a task.

The biggest problem with automation is time. That can be seen from two perspectives. First, you need time to implement automation. This is not an easy task, and often it is a reactive response (after there is an implementation). If automation is implemented, then there is the benefit of having more time. The second perspective, there is the mindset, you need to have the mindset and the ability to think abstractly.

At small organizations, you do not spend much time on automation.

At large organizations, you do spend time on automation.

Organization Culture

Skills / Knowledge

Time

Manual 'work' also costs a lot of time.	
<p>Manual 'work' also costs a lot of time.</p> <p>Also, human error is a cost factor. When there is no automation, the cost for correcting errors can be high.</p> <p>This is all about labor cost.</p> <p>Manual configuration is costly and leads to sloppiness.</p>	Cost
<p>Looking from IT to Business, the IT landscape has been parcelled out or is isolated (siloes). There is no collaboration between the different components.</p> <p>Also, with processes, there is a difference between what is asked and what is delivered. Automation helps to define and structure the implementation and overcomes semantic problems.</p>	IT -> Business
<p>When you go from business to IT, it is about requesting services. A self-service approach.</p> <p>To have a consistent execution of the business demands (the upper layer) towards the technology (the lower layer), you need an automated way of working. Manual execution introduces errors and is not consistent.</p>	Business -> IT
<p>Your IT environment is not reproducible. This can have a severe impact when trying to recover from an incident.</p> <p>Lack of assurance of IT continuity/disaster recovery.</p> <p>When there is a major disaster, you need to build your IT environment from scratch. That is not possible when there is no automation.</p> <p>When the IT infrastructure is not automated and the rest of the IT landscape is, then a bottleneck will raise. The whole IT landscape is a chain.</p>	Reproducible
<p>One of the challenges is the processes. When processes are not adapted to the automated way of working, the automation does not work as expected. This is mainly the case when human approval is needed somewhere in the process.</p>	Processes

11.2 Thematic Analysis for Interview Question 2

Interview Question 2: Can you describe what an IT infrastructure is for you and where it can be placed within the IT landscape?

Answers	Theme
<p>For everything that has no knowledge and functionality of the company</p> <p>The IT infrastructure is everything that supports the business. That is the purpose of the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>Applications (SAAS) are related to the business. The IT infrastructure is what is necessary to run that business.</p> <p>The IT infrastructure does not have a direct relationship with the business. We can say that the infrastructure has no business context. It facilitates and supports applications related to business and the supporting processes.</p> <p>Applications have a direct relationship with the business and use SaaS.</p> <p>The IT infrastructure does not have a direct business context and supports the application, which is business context aware.</p> <p>The IT infrastructure (layer) does not perform functions directly for the business; the application layer does this.</p>	<p>No Business Context</p>
<p>Is generic and about technology</p> <p>Within the Dutch government, we use a technical reference model. The lower layers of this model describe the IT infrastructure for me. They are the physical building layer, the network layer, the platform layer, and the middleware layer. But also, a small part of the application layer is the collaboration and messaging applications, which for me are also part of the IT infrastructure</p> <p>The NORA framework consists of 5 layers, and the lowest layer is the Technology layer. The IT infrastructure is placed within this layer.</p> <p>But the difference between the application layer (number 4) and the technology layer is not a hard line. This distinction has diminished in recent years.</p> <p>Also, see my research paper 'Applying Generalized Normalized Systems Theory to Engie' IT Reference Architecture Library' [2], where it is defined as 'IT Infrastructure = Physical Infrastructure + Software Infrastructure'.</p>	<p>Technology Layer</p>

<p>Depending on your point of view, you can see that there is layering. The interaction between these layers is the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>The IT infrastructure is the most technologically advanced part of the IT landscape. It has all the hardware, servers, storage, and network, and it supports business applications. Currently primarily known as IaaS and PaaS, the (empty) databases are also part of the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>It is also very technological.</p> <p>It is the primary layer on which the applications run.</p> <p>You can see the IT infrastructure layer and the application layer.</p>	
<p>Everything that is physical hardware and/or logical hardware.</p> <p>Consists of: o Physical hardware o Virtual Hardware o Operating system.</p> <p>It is about physical hardware, servers, desktop, laptop, etc.</p> <p>It is hardware but includes the software of the system which is necessary for operation.</p> <p>The IT components are: o All hardware and corresponding software, such as operating systems and supporting applications.</p> <p>IT infrastructure is hardware and software that runs directly on that hardware.</p>	Physical IT infrastructure
<p>IT infrastructure can be defined as Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), known from cloud technology.</p> <p>I see this from the perspective of a user/software developer and an IaaS/PaaS view.</p> <p>The IT landscape can also be divided into three main parts, namely: o SAAS (Software as a Service) § Applications, but also mail and SharePoint. o PAAS (Platform as a Service) § Are different services, like web services and database services o IAAS (Infrastructure as a Service) § Are hardware and operating software?</p> <p>There is a dividing line between SAAS and PAAS. where PAAS and IAAS constitute the IT infrastructure.</p>	Virtual IT infrastructure
<p>The IT landscape can be divided into two parts, where the dividing line is the operating system. Everything that is 'beneath' the operating system is the IT infrastructure and above is part of the application landscape</p>	Two parts; the dividing line is the OS.

<p>The operating system is part of the IT infrastructure</p> <p>The operating system for the IT infrastructure also includes DNS and directory services.</p> <p>Als monitoring and security are part of the IT infrastructure</p>	
<p>It is all about the user(s), they are coming to you for a working environment.</p> <p>That is every component necessary for people to do their job.</p> <p>The data and the applications live here, and they are available for the end-user.</p> <p>The IT infrastructure is everything people need to have access to.</p> <p>It is an environment where people/users are involved. When there is a problem in the IT infrastructure, all people/users are mostly directly affected. That is different by applications, there are mostly a partial people/user affected.</p> <p>A modern workspace is in the end part of the application layer. Because it consists of collaboration tools and office applications. Also it is also a business need.</p>	<p>It is all about users</p>
<p>The IT infrastructure is the skeleton (body) of the IT landscape and must support all the other layers that construct this landscape.</p> <p>Said in a different way, IT is the body, and the infrastructure are the bones.</p> <p>The IT infrastructure is the basis, the fundament, and the lowest layer.</p> <p>Around ten years ago, the IT infrastructure was built from different systems, servers, storage, and networks. But nowadays, it can be seen as one system with these integrated functions of servers, storage, and networks.</p> <p>Error! Reference source not found.</p>	<p>Skeleton / Body of the It Landscape</p>

<p>The IT infrastructure is Hybrid. A combination of local on-premises IT infrastructure and cloud IT infrastructure can be seen as the lowest layer inside of the IT landscape. The application layer and the information layer</p> <p>The diagram shows a layered architecture. At the top is the 'Informatielaag' (Information Layer) in light blue. Below it is the 'Applicatielaag' (Application Layer) in light orange. The 'Hybrid IT Infrastructure' is shown in a grey box containing: 'CyberSecurity' (orange bar), 'Collaboration' (teal box), 'Virtualisatie' (teal box), 'Hybrid Cloud' (teal box), 'Secure Enterprise Connectivity' (purple box), 'Compute & Storage' (teal box), and 'Secure Cloud Connectivity' (purple bar).</p>	<p>Hybrid</p>
<p>But also, about collaborating tools and, on the other hand, connectivity to a service provider</p> <p>The collaboration tool is part of the application layer and is placed on top of the IT infrastructure layer</p> <p>Also, it includes the IT department applications, supporting applications such as helpdesk software, and the software necessary for the packaging and distribution of other business applications</p>	<p>Collaboration /Support Applications</p>
<p>The diagram shows a stack of layers on the left: Business Process, Information, Application, Server, Buidling, and Electricity Provider. To the right, three vertical double-headed arrows represent different levels of infrastructure: 'Infrastructure for business analyst' (spanning Application, Information, and Business Process), 'Infrastructure for application user' (spanning Application and Information), and 'Infrastructure for systems manager' (spanning Application and Server).</p> <p>The IT infrastructure is something, from my point of view, that must be there. Let us say it is a utility that must be there based on standard products and working according to standards</p> <p>From a self-service point of view, it is (as a whole) a platform</p> <p>There is currently almost no difference between the IT infrastructure and the other part of the IT Landscape.</p>	<p>Depends on your view</p>

11.3 Thematic Analysis for Interview Question 3

Interview Question 3: From your point of view, can you describe what 'Automation' is for 'IT infrastructure'?

Answers	Theme
<p>0</p> <p>That every action is defined up-front, which means that it is known in advance how one will react to a certain circumstance. This all is scripted</p> <p>There are two active characteristics: 1. Repeating activities 2. Predictable Activities</p> <p>Every action that can be performed manually or semi-manually needs to be automated</p> <p>Automation delivers the expected result in a repeatable way</p> <p>Automation is all actions that are executed after a manual action and without manual intervention</p>	<p>Actions are defined up-front</p>
<p>Configuration of IT infrastructure capabilities based on standard templates and parameterized deployment scripts</p> <p>It is about deploying, maintaining and evolving your IT</p> <p>It's replaced manual work.</p> <p>Automation is about performing repeating tasks in a systematic and fast way. This approach helps to standardize. However, automation is different from a savings measure</p> <p>Every variable and parameter must be unique</p> <p>Automation is, in an automated way, provisioning and deployment of configurations to the different components.</p> <p>With automation, the pace of change can be increased; if you compare this with applications, modification can be added very quickly due to automation. Although the IT infrastructure is very static, automation can increase the speed of changes due to its nature</p> <p>Automation needs to support the lifecycle of an IT component, which contains three stages</p>	<p>Standard way of configuring (Deployment is part of it)</p>
<p>All knowledge (also known as policies) is only available in one place. There is one central truth</p>	<p>One Central Truth</p>

<p>There is only one place to touch for doing the 'work'</p> <p>Provides a single source of truth.</p> <p>There is one source of information for the configuration of the total IT infrastructure</p>	
<p>Automation is also about documentation</p>	<p>A standard way of documentation</p>
<p>sharing knowledge</p>	<p>Sharing Knowledge</p>
<p>In essence, there is no difference, but the physical hardware environment (IT infrastructure) is harder to script than the application environment.</p>	<p>Physical HW is harder to automate</p>
<p>The philosophy of CI/CD (continuous integration/continuous deployment) from the application environment can be used in the IT infrastructure. Because the mechanism of unity testing can be very valuable</p>	<p>CI/CD philosophy</p>
<p>Fully self-service for consumers of the IT infrastructure -> Software developers</p> <p>API service for a 100% full self-service deployment cycle (CI/CD) of new and existing services.</p> <p>where self-service is the seamless deployment of necessary applications</p> <p>This must provide self-service; in the background, everything is arranged</p> <p>The IT infrastructure must be offered as a service towards the others part of the IT landscape</p>	<p>Self Service</p>
<p>From an operational perspective, you can say that the IT infrastructure is fully aware of its status and can heal itself. Also known as pro-active health monitoring & selfremediation. As an example, automated triggers signal that there is a physical error of a component towards service engineers</p> <p>It is about knowing the (mastering) the status of your environment in a reproducible way.</p> <p>Automation is also about knowing the state and having predefined action for that state.</p> <p>It is all about the state. In a prescriptive way you can define the state and via monitoring you can find out if the IT infrastructure is in the correct state. If not, you can define how to react</p> <p>With automation you have more control of an IT infrastructure which is operational, it is easier to monitor the state during a change and deployment of new components.</p>	<p>Status aware</p>

<p>It is about producing a reproducible environment</p> <p>“Everything you have to do more than once, you have to automate”. This is true on a component level, multi-component, and also multi-technology</p>	<p>A reproducible environment</p>
<p>Automation is something you see in the deployment part of the IT Infrastructure. This part of the IT infrastructure is also known by the term 'Control Plane</p> <p>Furthermore, the application only 'lives' in the 'data plane' of the IT infrastructure</p>	<p>Development part of the IT Infrastructure</p>
<p>The cloud principles can explain the latest: o Broad-network o Elasticity o Measured Service o On-demand Self-Service o Resource Pooling</p> <p>Or the Seven Principles of Cloud-Native Architecture o Service-Oriented Desing o Elasticity o Observability o Resilience o Automation of All Procedures o Zero Trust</p> <p>Continuous Evolution of Architecture</p>	<p>Based on Cloud principles</p>

11.4 Thematic Analysis for Interview Question 4

Research Question 4: *Is there a difference between 'Automation' for an 'IT infrastructure' and 'Automation in the application environment'? If so, can you describe the difference?*

Answers	Theme
<p>The software is infinitely scaled.</p> <p>Software is dispensable.</p> <p>Hardware cannot scale infinitely and is limited.</p> <p>Hardware investments are expensive and have a long depreciation period.</p> <p>Infra = cost driver, application services = business value.</p> <p>There is a difference in the characteristic between the automation for the application environment and the IT infrastructure environment.</p> <p>The purpose is the same, but how it is executed is different.</p> <p>Due to these distinctive characteristics, both layers have other deployment mechanisms and, as a result, separate ways of automation.</p> <p>It starts with IT infrastructure and ends with applications.</p> <p>These are two different fields of work.</p> <p>the IT infrastructure and application layers have their own heartbeat.</p> <p>The characteristics of both are different.</p> <p>Automation for the applications is managed and developed by totally different teams, with different knowledge than for the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>CI/CD for software developed with OTAP versus OTAP for hardware.</p> <p>Application automation has no direct interaction with hardware.</p> <p>In automation, you make use of a pipeline, the well-known CI/CD principle. The software can confirm your configuration, for example, to check compliance. This is not common in the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>At the IT infrastructure level, when a failure is uncovered during a deployment, the deployment needs to be rerolled and again deployed.</p>	<p>Fundamentally different</p>

<p>In the infrastructure layer, changes are slow and planned; it is a very static environment.</p> <p>From my point of view, the IT infrastructure is delivered by a provider.</p> <p>You also need to involve an employee for that automation can 'take place' in the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>Automation for the applications is managed and developed by totally different teams, with different knowledge than for the IT infrastructure.</p>	
<p>From the perspective that the IT Infrastructure also contains applications, then there is no difference.</p> <p>It is an integrated environment.</p> <p>For me, there is no difference.</p> <p>There is no difference in automation on many levels, and it depends on the technologies you are using.</p>	<p>No difference</p>
<p>Also, the applications are about business value, where the IT-infrastructure is there to support and serve the application.</p> <p>Applications are in essence the 'tools' to deliver business value and from this perspective are almost part of the business.</p> <p>When there is a failure in an application, then just adjusting the (source) code is enough to overcome it.</p>	<p>Applications deliver Business value</p>
<p>There is a clear relationship between both. In modern solutions, the automation of the application environment triggers the automation of the IT infrastructure environment. As an example, when an application needs more resources, it asks the infrastructure to scale up the necessary resources.</p> <p>With IT Infrastructure Automation, there is an interaction between the system software and the hardware.</p> <p>Vertical dependencies it is depends on the layer (IT infra) below.</p> <p>There is also a relationship with the IT infrastructure and the components. It is a Chain.</p> <p>The application layer is dependent on the IT infrastructure layer. As a result, there are two different automation environments</p>	<p>Relation</p>
<p>The application layer is about: Low code which is program automation. Continues integration/continues deployment.</p>	<p>Automation in the Application Layer</p>

<p>The applications are an additional layer for a proper user experience and are deployed with an CI/CD pipeline.</p> <p>Application automation is easier, it is software talking to software.</p> <p>In the application layer, the changes are fast and volatile; it is a very dynamic environment.</p> <p>Applications must be able to use the services of the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>Automation for applications is more about building the application and not configuring it.</p>	
<p>IT infrastructure automation is harder, it is software talking to hardware.</p> <p>When you look at the IT-infrastructure and CI/CD that is all about patching.</p> <p>Also, it is very hard to do unit testing in the IT infrastructure, which is very common in applications.</p> <p>When using cloud technology, there is a difference; with cloud technology, everything is provisioned and deployed with the use of automation, the (virtual) IT infrastructure, and the application. If you have one data centre, the IT infrastructure is mostly not provided with automation.</p> <p>Automation automates routine actions to monitor and maintain the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>Automated configuration in the IT infrastructure is mainly done via API's.</p> <p>There is a genuine shift from <i>left to right</i> for security. When using a pipeline, the checks are mainly at the end, just before deployment. When integrating the IT infrastructure into the pipeline (or combining the two), security checks can be done earlier in the process, and that is what the change means. However, this is currently a best practice, and it can be of interest to integrate this into a maturity model.</p>	<p>Automation in the Infrastructure Layer</p>

11.5 Thematic Analysis for Interview Question 5

Interview Question 5: *This research aims to explore the feasibility of a maturity model. What is a maturity model for you? And do you know of a maturity model that fits or comes close to the assessment of the maturity level of IT infrastructure automation? If so, what kind of maturity model would you like to use?*

Answers	Theme
<p>If you are mature enough, you can easily switch your cloud IT infrastructure to another provider. This only works in a native cloud IT landscape.</p> <p>A mature department can identify what is needed to automate and what is done by a human. But over time, the human part is reduced in iterative processes.</p> <p>A more mature IT infrastructure can check if it complies with company policies. The next step can be to have the automation fix errors.</p> <p>As you mature, you need less knowledge of the IT infrastructure to deploy the application. Because the more mature you are, the more automation takes care of.</p> <p>Also, there is a paradigm shift from DevOps to NoOps. NoOps refers to a situation where an IT environment becomes so automated from the underlying infrastructure using technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, data analytics, and effective disaster recovery that there is no need for a dedicated team to manage software inhouse.</p> <p>Levels 1 – 3 are primary for delivering services to the end-user/developer.</p> <p>Levels 4 – 5 are more for operating the IT infrastructure.</p>	<p>Generic guidance about developing a Maturity Model for an IT infrastructure</p>
<p>Level 0: Create a script and deploy it to 1 component/device.</p> <p>Worst situation: Documentation lacks Manually No scripts. No list of assets. No CMDB</p> <p>Worst mature level: Manual work/tasks Reactive You don't know the state of the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>Level 0 – Everything is deployed manually and there is no documentation.</p> <p>Level 0 - Manually - The application developer needs a professional level of knowledge of the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>An interesting question here is how much knowledge a software developer needs for the IT infrastructure before they can deploy their applications.</p>	<p>Level 0</p>

<p>Level 0: Chaos - Development and maintenance are based on craftsmanship.</p>	
<p>Level 1: Create a script and deploy it to multiple components/devices.</p> <p>Level 1: Defined – There is a PDC of IT infrastructure services.</p> <p>Level 1: extent to which the infra capability is described in an infra catalogue.</p> <p>Level 1: the extent of standardization based on templates.</p> <p>Level 1– Manual Stage i. It is about unboxing and manual deployment.</p> <p>Level 1 – Everything is manually configured and operated.</p> <p>Level 1: Not passively stable</p> <p>Level 1: Manual-state infrastructure - Needs a lot of coordination (Response and action) between the different parts and technologies of the infrastructure.</p> <p>Level 1: There are deployment procedures.</p> <p>Level 1: Coordination § The application developer needs partial knowledge of the IT infrastructure and coordinates the deployment with the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>Level 1: There are standard solutions.</p> <p>Level 1: Manual parameterization of components</p>	<p>Level 1</p>
<p>Level 2: create a script that can be deployed to multiple technologies and multiple components/devices.</p> <p>Level 2: IaaS – Basic Level.</p> <p>Level 2: extend the scripted deployment.</p> <p>Level 2: Automate the process to deploy a component. That is, installing the system software and applications. But there is no integration.</p> <p>Level 2: Everything is standardized but still manually configured and operated.</p> <p>Level 2: Local Passive Stable.</p>	<p>Level 2</p>

<p>Level 2: Normalized Infrastructure § The interaction between different parts and technologies of the infrastructure is standardized.</p> <p>Level 2: There are deployment procedures and scripts to automate some deployment steps.</p> <p>Level 2: Automatic § The application developer does not need knowledge of the IT infrastructure. Some services can be used to automate the deployment fully.</p> <p>Level 2: There are standards.</p> <p>Level 2: Automated parameterization of components.</p>	
<p>Level 3: central policy and deployment to the full IT infrastructure.</p> <p>Level 3: IaaS – Advanced Level.</p> <p>Level 3: the extent of self-service via APIs for DevOps.</p> <p>Level 3: Automate the integration between the system software and the applications.</p> <p>Intermediate states: Scripted Installation and configuration of OS Scripting Adding policy's Security Compliance Maintenance Collecting state and logging Monitoring</p> <p>Level 3: Everything is standardized but automated configured and operated.</p> <p>Level 3: Partial Passive Stable.</p> <p>Level 3: Fully automated infrastructure. The infrastructure acts as one 'system'. Coordination (Response and action) between the different parts and technologies is clearly defined.</p> <p>Level 3: There are deployment procedures and scripts to automate the deployment steps and there is documentation.</p> <p>Level 3: Solutions are based on standards.</p>	<p>Level 3</p>

<p>Level 3: Patron recognition based on AI and automated adjusting and parameterization of components.</p>	
<p>Level 4: Actions are predefined and central policy. Level 4 – Everything is standardized but policy-based controlled, configured, and operated.</p> <p>Level 4: Reporting.</p> <p>Level 4: Extend billing and reporting for customers.</p> <p>Level 4: Everything is updated automatically.</p> <p>Level 4: Everything is standardized but policy-based controlled, configured, and operated.</p> <p>Level 4: Passive stable.</p> <p>Level 4: Zero-touch deployment (incl. procedures and documentation).</p> <p>Level 4: Everything is standardized.</p>	<p>Level 4</p>
<p>Level 5: Self-learning response for action and automatic adjustments.</p> <p>Level 5: Self running/healing.</p> <p>Level 5: extend monitoring and self-healing.</p> <p>Best situation: Every component is in exactly the required state. There is a difference between cloud and on-premises: With cloud everything is code, even the IT infrastructure is code. With on-premises, you need local 'hands-on' and all else is code.</p> <p>Most mature level: No manual work/tasks Proactive You know the exact state of the IT infrastructure.</p> <p>Level 5: Everything is autonomously configured and operated.</p> <p>The high level of maturity is when the systems in the IT infrastructure can heal themselves. That detects and responds to states.</p> <p>Level 5: Automation is a business spearhead. You are growing along with the standards.</p>	<p>Level 5</p>

11.6 Thematic Analysis for Interview Question 6

Interview Question 6: *From your point of view, how many dimensions should a maturity model consist of? What are the names/labels of these dimensions?*

Answers	Dimension
Empowerment/leadership to enforce automation	Empowerments
Technology	Technology
State of technology	
Processes (2x)	Processes
But most important is the mindset, it is all about the people. Smart people automate their work, especially when there are repetitive tasks.	People / Mindset
People (2x)	
Culture: If 'its breaks' you need to be motivated to improve the environment at once, so that it does not happen again. Also, the mindset to automate repeating tasks.	Culture
Culture	
Skill level of people	Skill / Knowledge
Knowledge, especially product knowledge	
Programming Knowledge	
Knowledge of the stakeholder: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Business) Users • Developers 	
How easily can knowledge be transferred to new team members?	
Skill Level	
Knowledge (2x)	
What it takes to deploy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much is needed to achieve this so that there is no follow up. • This is so because there is a failure. • In level 5 there is no follow ups 	Deployment
Easy deployment § As an example: Apple, total integration of software and hardware.	

Master Thesis - IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM)

How small are the deployments? The more mature the number of deployments in a shorter timeframe, the more mature	
Configuration Automation Operating Automation Policy Automation	Configuration
Measure the compliance. Security: Code review Consistency vs. Compliance § How many deviations are there concerning the preferred state. Compliance	Compliance
Automation is not a one-shot approach; it is a continuous driver. The states need to be checked continuously. Monitoring Automation Monitoring: How reliable is your IT infrastructure? One of the attributes or topics is the number of errors that occur and cause problems for people. Monitoring Observability - Getting insight into the system because not monitoring is old school. Every automation must be bulletproof. The KPI can be the failure rate or the test coverage. Predictability Robustness, Failure rate, Resiliency	State (Errors /Failures)
Security Automation Functional automation o Day-2-day operations o Zero-trust Security (2x) Security o It must have a place early in the model.	Security
Standardization	Standardization

Master Thesis - IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM)

The number of standards	
Governance - How good are you in requirement engineering? Governance (2x) Traceability	Governance
Operations	Operations
Automatability § As an example: APIs and documentation	Automatability
Integrability with the environment, Examples: APIs, LDAP, etc. Connectivity o Interaction with others, not only from a technological perspective.	Integrability
Possibility to run the system on premises vs. cloud	Hybrid (On-premises & Cloud)
An essential dimension is 'Documentation'; even when everything is 'running' without problems, but you don't have any documentation, you have nothing. Documentation	Documentation
Collaboration with partners/vendors with the same maturity level. Supplier reliability, agreements are fulfilled & flexible within the maintenance contract. Vendor Reliability & Quick Support	Suppliers/Vendors/Partners
Cost factor - If you are more mature, you need to ask yourself, how much may it (automation) cost for you as a business?	Cost
The Architecture of the Automation (itself)	Architecture of Automation
Deployment Speed: The more traditional the IT infrastructure, the slower the pace. And they have primarily big changes at once.	Speed

12 Appendix – Digital Survey

12.1 Invitation through Email

Subject: Survey for Master Thesis - IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model

Email Boddy:

Dear (vEAP member) / (Expert panel member),

As part of the master study on Enterprise IT Architecture from the Antwerp Management School, I am doing a master thesis to explore and design a prototype for an **IT infrastructure automation maturity model**. This survey is part of that research.

In the past period, I have researched the topics of IT infrastructure, automation, and maturity models based on various interviews and literature studies. This survey presents the first results of this research. The purpose of this survey is to validate these results.

May I kindly ask if you would like to complete this survey?

The survey can be completed until 3 March at noon.

Follow this link to the survey:

<link>

Or copy and paste the URL below into your internet browser:

<link>

Thanks in advance for filling in.

Warm regards,

ing. Henk-Jan Hopman BSc

Follow the link to opt out of future emails:

<link>

12.2 Invitation through Signal

May I kindly ask if you would like to complete the following survey? Which presents the first results of my research. The survey can be completed until 3 March at noon. Thanks in advance for filling in.

https://uamangementschool.eu.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_56HZD1BKb30HV5k

12.3 Survey

Survey Maturity Model for automation of the IT Infrastructure

Start of Block: Introduction

Q1.1 This survey is part of my research for my master thesis to explore and design a prototype for an IT infrastructure automation maturity model.

The questionnaire consists of three parts:

- The *IT infrastructure*, where the questions are related to exploring a new definition and model of the IT infrastructure.
- *Automation* concerning the IT infrastructure, to explore what automation is for the IT infrastructure.
- An *IT infrastructure Automation Maturity Model*, where the questions are about the possible levels and dimensions.

The results of this survey will be treated anonymously.

If anything needs to be clarified, don't hesitate to get in touch with me at xxxxx@xxx.xxx.

Best regards,

Henk-Jan Hopman

End of Block: Introduction

Start of Block: IT Infrastructure

Q2.1 There are different models to model the IT infrastructure. For my research the base model for an IT infrastructure is depicted below, which is adopted from Sjaak Laan's Books "IT Infrastructure Architecture - Infrastructure Building Blocks and Concepts".

Page Break

Q2.2 Besides modeling an IT Infrastructure model, there are many ways to express it. In preparing this questionnaire, I asked different experts what they perceive as IT infrastructure. This resulted in a couple of different terminologies. Provide per terminologies if you strongly disagree or strongly agree or somewhere in between, to what extent this corresponds to your image of an IT infrastructure.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Has business context.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Has NO business context.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is a Technology layer according to different reference architectures, such as for example explained in the technology reference model of TOGAF (version 9.2).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is physical hardware	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is only virtual hardware	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is a combination of physical and virtual hardware	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Contains IaaS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Contains PaaS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Contains SaaS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
An IT infrastructure is all about the users.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is the skeleton or body of the IT landscape	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Contains also the collaboration and support applications (i.e. mail or ticketing systems)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provides services to Applications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is the base fundament for users to get access to their applications and data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The 'place' where data and applications 'live'.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q2.3 Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Q2.4 If you are missing one or more terminologies, would you please add these with a brief explanation?

Q2.5 Which of the following definitions best describes today's IT infrastructure?

Provide per definition if this is an extremely inadequate or extremely adequate or somewhere in between definition of the IT infrastructure.

	Extremely inadequate	Moderately inadequate	Slightly inadequate	Neither adequate nor inadequate	Slightly adequate	Moderately adequate	Extremely adequate
IT infrastructure is the overall shared and common foundation of virtual resources and services, which has no direct business context and enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IT infrastructure is a shared platform with no direct business context, which supports and enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data. This platform consists of a virtual and supporting physical technology layer. Both layers consist of complex hard- and software components and communication technology.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IT infrastructure is a shared platform that provides a common foundation with virtual resources and service components, which has no direct business context, to support and enable organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IT infrastructure is a shared platform that provides a common foundation with virtual hardware and supporting software to provide resources and service components, which has no direct business context, to support and enable organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q2.6 Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Q2.7 If you are missing 'something' in the definition, would you please add these with a brief explanation?

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Q2.8 When researching a model for IT infrastructure, it became clear that almost no model is available in the scientific literature that defines an IT infrastructure. The following IT infrastructure model is developed as part of this research: it is a combination of available models from the industry and a book on IT infrastructure architecture.

Q2.9 The following statements are about this proposed model for the IT infrastructure.

Provide per statement if you strongly disagree or strongly agree or somewhere in between.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
This model represent as much as possible the current general view on an IT landscape.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A modern IT infrastructure can be seen as one platform.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The IT infrastructure platform management only manage IaaS & PaaS.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The infrastructure platform's management can be divided into two separate management entities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The infrastructure of a cloud provider must be part of this proposed model.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The on-premise infrastructure must be part of this proposed model.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The IT infrastructure consists only of the on-premise and cloud provides blocks.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The IT infrastructure (On-premise and Cloud provider) has a separate Infrastructure management.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is a clear difference between the application platform and the infrastructure platform.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is a clear difference between PaaS and the application platform.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
End User Devices are part of the Infrastructure platform.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q2.10 Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Q2.11 If you have any comments or additions to this model, please describe them.

End of Block: IT Infrastructure

Start of Block: Automation

Q3.2 Automation is a broad topic, especially within IT. During the research, I noticed that there are three parts of automation in the IT landscape. As visualized in the following figure:

1. The first part is the well-known automation for the application layer.
2. The second part is automation for the virtual infrastructure, also known as Infrastructure as Code.
3. The third part is automation for the more physical components of the IT infrastructure.

Where the first and second parts of automation are facing towards users and developers, and their purpose is to create business value. The third part is facing towards IT professionals and has indirect business value.

Q3.3 The following statements are about automation for the IT infrastructure and based on the previous model. Provide per statement if you strongly disagree or strongly agree or somewhere in between.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Automation is all about making pipelines and CI/CD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Automation for applications is different then for virtual infrastructures.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Automation for the virtual infrastructure is different then for the (physical) infrastructure.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is no difference in automation for the virtual infrastructure then physical infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is one automation for the infrastructure platform.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Physical Infrastructure automation is for IT professionals.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There are three 'types' of automation in the IT landscape.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Application automation and virtual infrastructure automation is more for the users and developers.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q3.4 Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Q3.5 If you have any comments or additions to this automation model, please describe them.

Q3.6 The following diagram can be made by combining the insights about the tree automation types with knowledge about automation pipelines. The pipelines are:

1. Application pipeline. This pipeline is all about application deployment.
2. The virtual infrastructure pipeline. This pipeline is all about virtual infrastructure deployment.
3. The (physical) infrastructure pipeline. This pipeline is about (physical) infrastructure (compute, network, storage) deployment.

There is an explicit dependency between the application automation pipeline and the virtual infrastructure automation. The infrastructure automation has its cadence and pace and supports the other automation pipelines.

Q3.7 The previous diagram shows three CI/CD pipeline. The next statements are about these pipelines. Provide per statement if you strongly disagree or strongly agree or somewhere in between.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
There are three CI/CD pipelines in the IT landscape.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The application pipeline (1) depends on the virtual infrastructure pipeline.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The application pipeline (1) and virtual infrastructure pipeline (2) has (almost) the same deployment pace/speed.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The infrastructure pipeline (3) has his own deployment pace/speed.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The infrastructure pipeline (3) consist of the physical components for network, compute and storage.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q3.8 Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Q3.9 If you have any comments or additions to this three automation pipelines, please describe them.

End of Block: Automation

Start of Block: Maturity Model

Q4.1 The following questions are about the development of the maturity model. A maturity model is a 'tool' to assess the current level of maturity and provides a path to the next level. It is built up of stages and dimensions. The following figure visualizes a generic maturity model.

Q4.2

There are two types of maturity models, a staged maturity model of a continuous model. A produced model helps an organization to improve its capabilities "as a whole."

To achieve a certain maturity level, it is required that the organization's capabilities are compliant with the characteristics of that level. In a continuous model, every capability is evaluated and improved individually, and each capability can be at a different maturity level. The following figure visualizes the two models.

To develop a maturity model, a choice for a model needs to be made. The response to the following statement helps in choosing the model type. Provide per statement if you strongly disagree or strongly agree or somewhere in between.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The capabilities of an organization develop linear.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Organizations need to have a predefined and proven improvement path.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Every capability can improve individually.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
An organization develops there maturity step by step. Therefor all capabilities needed to be on the same maturity level.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To have a good overview of the maturity levels, the best representation is as a matrix diagram.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To have a good overview of the maturity levels, the best representation is as a spider diagram.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q4.3 Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Q4.4 If you have any comments or additions to this model, please describe them.

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Q4.5 Maturity models consist of levels also of dimensions. Provide per dimension if you strongly disagree or strongly agree or somewhere in between that these dimensions must be part of this maturity model for **AUTOMATION**.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Actions are defined up-front	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Automation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Automation Architecture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Business Process Management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Compliance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Documentation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data Management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Education	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ecosystem relationship	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Financial	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Governance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure Configuration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure Deployment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure Management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure Provisioning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IT Architecture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Operations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Operations	<input type="radio"/>						
One Central truth	<input type="radio"/>						
Repeatability	<input type="radio"/>						
Process Management	<input type="radio"/>						
Scalability	<input type="radio"/>						
Standardization	<input type="radio"/>						
Security	<input type="radio"/>						
Service Management	<input type="radio"/>						
Self-Service	<input type="radio"/>						
Skills	<input type="radio"/>						
Software	<input type="radio"/>						
Software Development	<input type="radio"/>						
Solution Driver	<input type="radio"/>						
Status Aware (Errors/Failures)	<input type="radio"/>						
Tasks (manual - automated)	<input type="radio"/>						
Infrastructure Utilization	<input type="radio"/>						
Vendor Management	<input type="radio"/>						

Q4.6 Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Q4.7 If you have any comments or additions to these dimensions, please describe them.

End of Block: Maturity Model

Start of Block: Draft maturity model

Q5.1 A first draft of a maturity model for IT infrastructure automation is shown below. The IT infrastructure's scope is the infrastructure proposed in the IT infrastructure model (number 3).

Dimension	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Technology	Silo'd, Hardware/device-centric	End-to-End hardware/devic-centric	Mixed hardware-centric and software-centric	End-to-End software-centric	Integrated software-centric
Automation	Manual device configuration	Basic configuration automation	Controller-based multiple devices Automation	Per technology domain automation	Cross technology domain automation
Security	Fragement (local) policy and access management	Decentralized policy and access management	Centralized policy and access management	Per technology domain policy and access management	Cross technology domain policy and access management
Provisioning	Individual device-centric configuration	Basic configuration	Controller based configuration	Per technology domain based configuration	Cross technology domain-based configuration
Analytics	Individual device visibility	Alarm-triggered and device level insight	Technology domain wide insight	Adaptive and preventative insight	Automated and predictive insight
Tasks	Manual	Script per component	Scripted to multiple components	Scripted per technology and multiple component	Scripted cross technology domain and cross components
Documentation	No documentation	Per device documentation	Per technology domain documentation	Cross technology domain documentation	Documentation is generated automatically and cross technology domain
Ability to change	Weeks to Months	Days to weeks	Hours to days	Minutes to Hours	Seconds to Minutes

Q5.2 The following statements describe the different maturity levels. Provide per statement if you strongly disagree or strongly agree or somewhere in between that this statement best describes the different levels of a maturity model for IT infrastructure automation.

Q5.3 Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Q5.4 If you have any comments or additions to these descriptions, please describe them.

Q5.5 This question is about some generic statements about the first draft of this maturity model. Provide per statement if you strongly disagree or strongly agree or somewhere in between with this statement.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
This model provides a path to grow in automation maturity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
With five levels you can properly define a maturity model for automation.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Five levels are too many to define an automation maturity model.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Level 1 to level 3 are more about day-0 and day-1 operations.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Level 4 and level 5 are more about day-2 operations.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Level 1 to level 3 are primary for delivering service.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Level 4 and level 5 are primary for operating the IT infrastructure (update, life cycle management, etc).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q5.6 Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Q5.7 If you have any comments or additions to these generic statements, please describe them.

End of Block: Draft maturity model

Start of Block: Research

Q6.1 You are almost at the end of this survey. To substantiate this scientific research project. The distribution of expertise (knowledge) and the sector of economy in which you work is needed.

Q6.2 What is your job description?

Q6.3 In which sector of economy are you working?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Manufacturing | <input type="radio"/> Hospitality and Leisure |
| <input type="radio"/> Utilities - electricity, gas | <input type="radio"/> Real Estate |
| <input type="radio"/> Construction | <input type="radio"/> Information Technology |
| <input type="radio"/> Retail | <input type="radio"/> Education |
| <input type="radio"/> Financial Services | <input type="radio"/> Public Sector |
| <input type="radio"/> Communication | <input type="radio"/> Research and Development |

End of Block: Research

Start of Block: End

Q7.1 Are there any additional comments or suggestions?

End of Block: End

13 Appendix - Analysis of Digital Survey

Survey results

Q2.2 - Besides modeling an IT Infrastructure model, there are many ways to express...

Field	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Has business context.	1	2	2	1	8	7	4
Has NO business context.	8	8	3	1	2	2	1
Is a Technology layer according to different reference architectures, such as for example explained in the technology reference model of TOGAF (version 9.2).	0	0	2	3	5	11	4
Is physical hardware	3	1	1	3	2	12	3
Is only virtual hardware	11	10	2	1	1	0	0
Is a combination of physical and virtual hardware	0	2	0	1	2	7	13
Contains IaaS	0	0	0	0	3	8	14
Contains PaaS	0	0	0	0	3	15	7
Contains SaaS	3	5	1	2	6	5	3
An IT infrastructure is all about the users.	1	10	5	2	4	1	2
Is the skeleton or body of the IT landscape	0	3	2	0	3	12	5
Contains also the collaboration and support applications (i.e. mail or ticketing systems)	1	5	3	1	6	5	4
Provides services to Applications	0	0	0	0	3	12	10
Is the base fundament for users to get access to their applications and data	0	1	1	1	2	10	10
The 'place' where data and applications 'live'.	0	0	0	1	3	11	10

Q2.2 - Besides modeling an IT Infrastructure model, there are many ways to express...

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses	Sum
Has business context.	23.00	29.00	27.00	1.62	2.64	25	675.00
Has NO business context.	23.00	29.00	24.64	1.79	3.19	25	616.00
Is a Technology layer according to different reference architectures, such as for example explained in the technology reference model of TOGAF (version 9.2).	25.00	29.00	27.48	1.14	1.29	25	687.00
Is physical hardware	23.00	29.00	26.92	1.87	3.51	25	673.00
Is only virtual hardware	23.00	27.00	23.84	1.01	1.01	25	596.00
Is a combination of physical and virtual hardware	24.00	29.00	28.04	1.43	2.04	25	701.00
Contains IaaS	27.00	29.00	28.44	0.70	0.49	25	711.00
Contains PaaS	27.00	29.00	28.16	0.61	0.37	25	704.00
Contains SaaS	23.00	29.00	26.20	2.00	4.00	25	655.00
An IT infrastructure is all about the users.	23.00	29.00	25.36	1.67	2.79	25	634.00
Is the skeleton or body of the IT landscape	24.00	29.00	27.36	1.60	2.55	25	684.00
Contains also the collaboration and support applications (i.e. mail or ticketing systems)	23.00	29.00	26.48	1.88	3.53	25	662.00
Provides services to Applications	27.00	29.00	28.28	0.66	0.44	25	707.00
Is the base fundament for users to get access to their applications and data	24.00	29.00	27.96	1.28	1.64	25	699.00
The 'place' where data and applications 'live'.	26.00	29.00	28.20	0.80	0.64	25	705.00

Q2.3 - Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Business context is about the size of the business. Small Business needs IT infrastructure. 100% complete but as a compact and basic version. So there is a business context.

1: Has business context is incorrect phrasing. Should more be like: IT Infrastructure should reflect the needs from the business context.

Terminologies 4 - 6 are to strict using "is".

IT Infrastructure has a more specific meaning within the IT domain compared to the outside world. For my wife as a communication professional, applications and data in the applications are also part of the IT infrastructure. So the definition of IT Infrastructure depends on the context. My answers are given from the IT domain perspective.

Infrastructure is interchangeable, strongly agree

I consider container orchestration platforms part of the IT infrastructure, e.g. Kubernetes. I should provide abstractions to tenant applications, so the complexity of managing infrastructure is hidden from the application developers and users.

Different segments of the IT infrastructure can have different or no business contexts. For example, Compute/storage is nowadays so general that most business contexts can use the same/universal IT infrastructure.

The business influences the contents of the IT infrastructure layer strongly.

no

collaboration and support is very wide, like workspace functionality but also ITOM en ITSM. The last two are very close to IT infrastructure because without it, it wouldnt be complete.

Q2.4 - If you are missing one or more terminologies, would you please add these with a brief explanation?

If you are missing one or more terminologies, would you please add these with a brief explanation?

Maybe about geography? Is IT infrastructure always geographical independent? For instance, when almost everything is virtual, like the cloud, how do you place geographical separated aspects.

Infrastructure is interchangeable, strongly agree

Infrastructure is serving business purposes, not a goal in itself

I'm missing security in the context of infrastructure, cloud-native infrastructure, policies as code

It provide basic security pre-conditions for applications, interms of availability (failover, etc.) as well as identification, authentication, access-path and monitoring services

1) Provides the basic components to communicate with other infrastructures

2) translates the physical world into the digital world

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Maybe you could have asked whether or not Security Services are an integral part (subsystem) of IT-infrastructure or not...

Provides its services to other applications, and/or to many/all end users, in a generic way

An unexpected error has occurred

Q2.5 - Which of the following definitions best describes today's IT infrastructure...

Field	Extremely inadequate	Moderately inadequate	Slightly inadequate	Neither adequate nor inadequate	Slightly adequate	Moderately adequate	Extremely adequate
IT infrastructure is the overall shared and common foundation of virtual resources and services, which has no direct business context and enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data.	0	7	2	0	10	4	2

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IT infrastructure is a shared platform with no direct business context, which supports and enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data. This platform consists of a virtual and supporting physical technology layer. Both layers consist of complex hard- and software components and communication technology.

0 3 3 1 5 7 6

IT infrastructure is a shared platform that provides a common foundation with virtual resources and service components, which has no direct business context, to support and enable organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications.

0 4 5 1 8 7 0

7

IT infrastructure is a shared platform that provides a common foundation with virtual hardware and supporting software to provide resources and service components, which has no direct business context, to support and enable organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications.

0 5 7 1 7 5 0

Q2.5 - Which of the following definitions best describes today's IT infrastructure...

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses	Sum
IT infrastructure is the overall shared and common foundation of virtual resources and services, which has no direct business context and enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data.	102.00	107.00	104.32	1.69	2.86	25	2608.00

Master Thesis - IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM)

IT infrastructure is a shared platform with no direct business context, which supports and enables organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications and data. This platform consists of a virtual and supporting physical technology layer. Both layers consist of complex hard- and software components and communication technology.

102.00	107.00	105.12	1.68	2.83	25	2628.00
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IT infrastructure is a shared platform that provides a common foundation with virtual resources and service components, which has no direct business context, to support and enable organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications.

102.00	106.00	104.36	1.47	2.15	25	2609.00
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IT infrastructure is a shared platform that provides a common foundation with virtual hardware and supporting software to provide resources and service components, which has no direct business context, to support and enable organizations to develop and implement present and future business applications.

102.00	106.00	104.00	1.47	2.16	25	2600.00
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Q2.6 - Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

iT infrastructure includes the physical layer

For Definition 1, I don't like developing and implement (...) data. Other verbs are required for data. Again, I don't like the specifics

For Definition 2, I like the first sentence, but don't agree with the specifics in the next sentences.

For definition 4, I don't like the virtual hardware. That suggest PaaS.

I don't like that business context is excluded, i think business conext determines the requirements with regard to infrastructure

I do consider platform engineering as a valuable practice delivering value to both developers and business, but it's not covering the whole infrastructure in a hybrid, multi-cloud context

it's both physical and virtual hardware, and both shared and dedicated. It depends also on the level of control one has.

In all phrases you mention that there is no direct business context. This is adequate if you split the functionality and technology of IT Infrastructure on an architectural level. But several functionalities that are provided by the IT Infrastructure actually do have business context (that is that it is used for business processes). The answers are based on the assumption that you have splitted technology and functionality.

As soon as it is limited to virtual resources the statement becomes more inaccurate for me

no

I think you should include "common foundation of physical and virtual components, including supporting software to provie resource and services" there is ALWAYS a physical component, even if it is just the box connecting a company to the Internet and from there on to virtual cloud services

I'm kind of stuck because all the answers say 'no direct business context'. I believe that infrastructure is useless if you don't know the business goals and deliverables. Or, I have a other interpretation of Business context..

I don't agree with any of these definitions. All state that there is no direct business context. Three definitions only mention virtual resources but no physical resources. And the one definition that does mention physical resources (definition #2) includes communication technology.

Q2.7 - If you are missing 'something' in the defintion, would you please add these with a brief explanation?

If you are missing 'something' in the defintion, would you please add these with a brief explanation?

a definition should be "fit for purpose", what is the purpose and usage of this definition, only than you can determine whether something is missing

Master Thesis - IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM)

First definition: IT infrastructure provides the foundation for cloud-native platforms, which deliver golden paths and self-service capabilities to tenants of the platform.

- both virtual AND physical devices / services
 - services like security- and operational monitoring: should they be in the IT infrastructure? The definition do not address this.

All definitions contain good element, but not one covers all aspects. A combination of all the definitions might result in a adequate definition.

Q2.9 - The following statements are about this proposed model for the IT infrastru...

Field	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
This model represent as much as possible the current general view on an IT landscape.	1	0	6	1	4	11	2
A modern IT infrastructure can be seen as one platform.	1	7	1	1	6	7	2
The IT infrastructure platform management only manage laas & PaaS.	1	6	6	0	6	5	1
The infrastructure platform's management can be divided into two separate management entities.	1	4	6	9	4	1	0
The infrastructure of a cloud provider must be part of this proposed model.	0	3	2	2	2	10	6
The on-premise infrastructure must be part of this proposed model.	0	1	0	1	2	12	9
The IT infrastructure consists only of the on-premise and cloud provides blocks.	2	10	3	3	3	2	2

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The IT infrastructure (On-premise and Cloud provider) has a separate Infrastructure management.	1	4	7	2	4	5	2
There is a clear difference between the application platform and the infrastructure platform.	0	3	2	2	2	13	3
There is a clear difference between PaaS and the application platform.	2	4	5	1	2	9	2
End User Devices are part of the Infrastructure platform.	1	3	3	1	2	7	8

Q2.9 - The following statements are about this proposed model for the IT infrastru...

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses	Sum
This model represent as much as possible the current general view on an IT landscape.	13.00	19.00	16.92	1.55	2.39	25	423.00
A modern IT infrastructure can be seen as one platform.	13.00	19.00	16.32	1.87	3.50	25	408.00
The IT infrastructure platform management only manage IaaS & PaaS.	13.00	19.00	15.92	1.72	2.95	25	398.00
The infrastructure platform's management can be divided into two separate management entities.	13.00	18.00	15.56	1.17	1.37	25	389.00
The infrastructure of a cloud provider must be part of this proposed model.	14.00	19.00	17.28	1.66	2.76	25	432.00
The on-premise infrastructure must be part of this proposed model.	14.00	19.00	18.04	1.11	1.24	25	451.00
The IT infrastructure consists only of the on-premise and cloud provides blocks.	13.00	19.00	15.36	1.79	3.19	25	384.00

Master Thesis - IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM)

The IT infrastructure (On-premise and Cloud provider) has a separate Infrastructure management.	13.00	19.00	16.08	1.72	2.95	25	402.00
There is a clear difference between the application platform and the infrastructure platform.	14.00	19.00	17.16	1.57	2.45	25	429.00
There is a clear difference between PaaS and the application platform.	13.00	19.00	16.28	1.93	3.72	25	407.00
End User Devices are part of the Infrastructure platform.	13.00	19.00	17.12	1.95	3.79	25	428.00

Q2.10 - Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Application platform is part of the IT platform.
Application platform runs on/as a PaaS

Line 4: This question makes no sense to me. The text refers to the diagram on the previous page, but contradicts with the diagram

Choices are easy to make, but hard to explain because of the lack of industry definitions of infrastructure, platforms

in my opinion the application platform and PaaS are equal.
For the application layer, there should be no difference between an application being on premise or in (public or private) clouds. The Infrastructure management must be able to service both.

I think there are more models than just on premise or cloud - it is simply a delivery model. Therefore, I am hesitant to strongly agree on the definition with just these two. I would opt for a phrase like "should contain all infrastructure delivery models"

no

on-premise and cloud provider --> is it better to use private and public? Because Cloud is a delivery-model which can be used onpremise as well.. SAAS can also be part of IT infrastructure, if those are SAAS-services of the (cloud)provider. SAAS services can also be created by the (end)consumer which make it nog part of the providers-IT-infrastructure, however build with same IT-resources from the (Cloud) provider

Q2.11 - If you have any comments or additions to this model, please describe them.

If you have any comments or additions to this model, please describe them.

Mobile devices such has smartphone or PDA in logistics are part of the infrastructure

13

Master Thesis - IT Infrastructure Automation Maturity Model (ITIAMM)

I am missing Edge compute in this model

There's no scientific definition of infrastructure, certainly not for IaaS, PaaS, SaaS.
Many questions are ambiguous and hard to answer without extensive explanation

A infrastructure model needs to be clear to non technical personnel. If the model is too complex or difficult to understand it had no purpose within the organisation.

Lacking in the model : end-user devices like mobile, laptop, end-user computing. The difference between "an IT infrastructure" (specific) and "IT infrastructure".

As per your model the infrastructure is only provided for datacenter services. The End User Devices also need a communication infrastructure, whether these are on premise or in external locations (@home, road warriors, partner locations, etc.).

I like the view of Arcitura CCP, where all the infrastructure assets are IT-resources which can be combined to Services and when exposed outside 'cloud Services'. Your model misses a place for containers (example also on baremetal possible) and serverless. On premise can nowadays also be delivered by an external provider. I do more like the layers of business values/processes, information, data and then application. 'Application platform' in the picture is difficult, because there are enough applications on middleware which deliver an application (runtime) platform on PaaS. There are a lot of examples where application-data (ex java) of application-COTS is placed/installed on PaaS, without being it an application platform for a (cloud)provider. Maybe in terms of a consumer, it would be their platform, but more like their own created (Cloud)Services. Performance and availability are characteristics of a technical deployment. I see more value for logging, monitoring, auditing, ITSM on the right columns. PaaS is not always on top of IaaS, so there are some Storage Services which can be provided to (end)consumers without a PaaS services. Is there a place for self-service portal, orchestration, automation of applications on IaaS/PaaS AND automation of the infrastructure Services?

In the IaaS/PaaS column you include the physical datacenter at the bottom row of the model. In the end user devices column you don't include the physical campus at the bottom row of the model. That appears to be inconsistent.

Q3.3 - The following statements are about automation for the IT infrastructure and...

Field	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Automation is all about making pipelines and CI/CD.	3	7	3	0	7	3	2
Automation for applications is different then for virtual infrastructures.	2	3	4	1	5	8	2
Automation for the virtual infrastructure is different then for the (physical) infrastructure.	3	1	5	1	4	7	4
There is no difference in automation for the virtual infrastructure then physical infrastructure	3	8	8	0	1	1	4
There is one automation for the infrastructure platform.	3	8	4	4	3	3	0
Physical Infrastructure automation is for IT professionals.	1	1	1	2	5	13	2
There are three 'types' of automation in the IT landscape.	0	3	3	3	8	8	0
Application automation and virtual infrastructure automation is more for the users and developers.	1	4	6	2	7	5	0

Q3.3 - The following statements are about automation for the IT infrastructure and...

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses	Sum
Automation is all about making pipelines and CI/CD.	9.00	15.00	11.72	1.93	3.72	25	293.00
Automation for applications is different then for virtual infrastructures.	9.00	15.00	12.44	1.83	3.37	25	311.00
Automation for the virtual infrastructure is different then for the (physical) infrastructure.	9.00	15.00	12.56	1.96	3.85	25	314.00
There is no difference in automation for the virtual infrastructure then physical infrastructure	9.00	15.00	11.28	1.95	3.80	25	282.00
There is one automation for the infrastructure platform.	9.00	14.00	11.20	1.57	2.48	25	280.00
Physical Infrastructure automation is for IT professionals.	9.00	15.00	13.24	1.42	2.02	25	331.00
There are three 'types' of automation in the IT landscape.	10.00	14.00	12.60	1.36	1.84	25	315.00
Application automation and virtual infrastructure automation is more for the users and developers.	9.00	14.00	12.00	1.52	2.32	25	300.00

Q3.4 - Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Statement 1: pipelines and CI/CD concepts are also applicable to infrastructure

Same story, ambiguous questions due to lack of clear definitions

Application and virtual infrastructure development with a orchestration tool needs solid understanding of the function of different components within the tool.

Automation is in my opinion not a 'thing'. You want to achieve something (that is make things easy/fast/flawless/etc. by eliminating human interference. So are there different types of automation, not really. There are though different areas in which you want to automate the technology or processes. To be able to do this, there are several tools or ways to support that.

How about RPA? I can't say that fits within the three types of automation.
Physical infrastructure automation is also relevant for Real Estate and Facility Management.

no

automation of core-infrastructure IT resources is different on stacked, converged and hyperconverged infrastructure. Some models and hardware have their own tooling and standards for automation. Ideally all automation can be centralized and uniformed as code. Physical infrastructure can also be delivered to end-consumers outside the cloud-provider. Again the Arictura CCP gives a clear separation of it. A end-consumer can be a IT-professional but also a good devops-team with wide knowledge.

There are countless types of automation in the IT landscape. Automation is in essence at the core of anything we are trying to achieve with IT since the beginning of IT

Q3.5 - If you have any comments or additions to this automation model, please describe them.

If you have any comments or additions to this automation model, please describe them.

In a software driven world, anything as code is driving modern cloud-native application development. DevOps practices evolve, such as GitOps for infrastructure, container platforms and application workloads. Again lack of standardization results in many solutions, however CSI,CRI, CNI in the Kubernetes spaces is addressing some of these challenges

What are the goals of automation: I think: consistency (hence policies), speed of change, quality of change.

I miss context, at which types of companies are you aiming? I can imagine different choices and outcomes for IT suppliers for example.

I like the three layers you define, because I think there are distinct differences between them.

Q3.7 - The previous diagram shows three CI/CD pipeline. The next statements are ab...

Field	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
There are three CI/CD pipelines in the IT landscape.	0	5	3	3	5	8	1
The application pipeline (1) depends on the virtual infrastructure pipeline.	0	1	3	0	6	13	2
The application pipeline (1) and virtual infrastructure pipeline (2) has (almost) the same deployment pace/speed.	0	6	8	3	4	4	0
The infrastructure pipeline (3) has his own deployment pace/speed.	0	0	4	1	3	12	5
The infrastructure pipeline (3) consist of the physical components for network, compute and storage.	0	4	2	1	1	13	4

Q3.7 - The previous diagram shows three CI/CD pipeline. The next statements are ab...

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses	Sum
There are three CI/CD pipelines in the IT landscape.	11.00	16.00	13.44	1.60	2.57	25	336.00
The application pipeline (1) depends on the virtual infrastructure pipeline.	11.00	16.00	14.32	1.26	1.58	25	358.00
The application pipeline (1) and virtual infrastructure pipeline (2) has (almost) the same deployment pace/speed.	11.00	15.00	12.68	1.41	1.98	25	317.00
The infrastructure pipeline (3) has his own deployment pace/speed.	12.00	16.00	14.52	1.30	1.69	25	363.00
The infrastructure pipeline (3) consist of the physical components for network, compute and storage.	11.00	16.00	14.16	1.71	2.93	25	354.00

Q3.8 - Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Wat about the management and control component for the physical layer when integrating automation?

Pipelines shouldn't be limited. Every group of IT admins or developers should be able to create a pipeline that connects to (supplements) the three basic/foundational pipelines you propose.

There is a difference between network, compute and storage pipelines that needs further explanation. The goal of a pipeline needs to be clearly defined and based open standards.

The questions are (off course) biased as this is the way you have done your research. The answers are based on that thought and not always in line with my thoughts on the different streams.

no

on the three pipelines, maybe it can be one or two with good delegation and integration on each other. So maybe logically or functionally there are two.

The pace of change in the application pipeline is much higher than the pace of change in the virtual infra pipeline. In the virtual infra pipeline I don't think scaling up resources or scaling down resources counts as "change". Scaling up and down resources based upon templates is just automated operations. This is not the same as "change".

Q3.9 - If you have any comments or additions to this three automation pipelines, please describe them.

If you have any comments or additions to this three automation pipelines, please describe them.

Virtual network is part of it especially with CI/CD that may require specific layer of security. Thinking also about IAM that is part of security of infrastructure

I don't agree with the full incorporation of pipeline 2 into pipeline 1. My gut feeling is that there is an intermediate level between them where both pipelines meet, 2 as a provider and 1 as a user.

What about policies as code, e.g. Open Policy agent framework which also have a pipeline of developing, deploying and managing policies across the layers you've mentioned.

CI/CD for physical components seems an awkward idea: these things have to be bought, inspected and installed.

To start off, you need to have a business requirement. This can come from high level business requirements or from within the IT organization.

I think the application pipeline is interacting with the operate phase of the virtual infra pipeline. The dependencies as they are drawn in the current picture don't feel correct to me.

Q4.2 - There are two types of maturity models, a staged maturity model of a contin...

Field	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The capabilities of an organization develop linear.	9	6	5	5	0	0	0
Organizations need to have a predefined and proven improvement path.	1	8	4	1	9	2	0
Every capability can improve individually.	0	1	4	3	5	12	0
An organization develops there maturity step by step. Therefor all capabilities needed to be on the same maturity level.	2	10	8	1	4	0	0
To have a good overview of the maturity levels, the best representation is as a matrix diagram.	0	5	5	6	6	3	0
To have a good overview of the maturity levels, the best representation is as a spider diagram.	0	0	5	5	8	6	1

Q4.2 - There are two types of maturity models, a staged maturity model of a contin...

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses	Sum
The capabilities of an organization develop linear.	13.00	16.00	14.24	1.14	1.30	25	356.00
Organizations need to have a predefined and proven improvement path.	13.00	18.00	15.60	1.52	2.32	25	390.00
Every capability can improve individually.	14.00	18.00	16.92	1.26	1.59	25	423.00
An organization develops there maturity step by step. Therefor all capabilities needed to be on the same maturity level.	13.00	17.00	14.80	1.17	1.36	25	370.00
To have a good overview of the maturity levels, the best representation is as a matrix diagram.	14.00	18.00	15.88	1.31	1.71	25	397.00
To have a good overview of the maturity levels, the best representation is as a spider diagram.	15.00	19.00	16.72	1.15	1.32	25	418.00

Q4.3 - Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

as a start a matrix model is easier to communicate, later refinement to a continuous model can be done when more experience has been obtained

Like CMM, the levels between capabilities should be too far apart. For example, CMM dictates that communication between CMM levels with more than 1 level of difference is problematic.

The spider diagram needs a solid description and every year it needs to be updated to provide insights in improvement.

The representation probably depends on the viewers. The maturity should be able to be representated in both (or even more) ways.

I think development of maturity levels should take place in unison, but the start may not be the same level. Some characteristics will always be better developed. It is key to not let them get ahead too much, but develop the others to a more or less matching level

no

the models are too small, make them clickable for bigger resolution. I skip these answers for now because of my time and the 'fear' if I don't complete it that my former answers are lost...

Both the matrix diagram, and the spider diagram can prove valuable as a means to provide overview.

Q4.4 - If you have any comments or additions to this model, please describe them.

If you have any comments or additions to this model, please describe them.

The dependencies are not linear, but much more complex. The dependencies give hard and soft limits. Soft limits impact efficiency (improvement is possible but more effort is required.)

There's a graph representation of capabilities which should cover the time aspect, because capabilities evolve over time (e.g. Wardley maps)

Weakest link argument - being super mature in one aspect will be brought down by other aspects that are low

Q4.5 - Maturity models consist of levels also of dimensions. Provide per dimension...

Field	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Actions are defined up-front	1	2	4	2	5	10	1
Automation	1	0	0	2	1	9	12
Automation Architecture	0	0	1	3	0	10	11
Agility	1	1	1	4	6	8	4
Business Process Management	1	3	4	6	4	5	2
Compliance	2	1	0	3	3	11	5
Documentation	0	1	2	2	4	12	4
Data Management	0	1	3	4	1	10	6
Education	0	3	2	6	4	6	4
Ecosystem relationship	0	4	3	9	2	4	3
Financial	1	7	4	6	0	6	1
Governance	1	2	1	1	5	9	6
Knowledge	0	1	1	1	6	10	6
Infrastructure	0	1	4	4	5	8	3
Infrastructure Configuration	0	0	3	2	1	13	6
Infrastructure Deployment	0	0	2	2	0	14	7
Infrastructure Management	0	0	2	2	1	14	6
Infrastructure Provisioning	0	0	2	1	0	14	8
IT Architecture	0	2	3	2	4	6	8
Operations	1	0	1	2	3	15	3

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One Central truth	1	2	1	5	2	7	7
Repeatability	1	1	0	1	0	12	10
Process Management	1	1	4	5	7	6	1
Scalability	0	1	0	3	4	11	6
Standardization	0	1	0	2	1	14	7
Security	1	1	1	3	0	9	10
Service Management	1	1	4	5	3	11	0
Self-Service	0	0	0	3	2	16	4
Skills	0	2	2	3	3	12	3
Software	1	3	2	5	5	8	1
Software Development	1	2	1	5	3	8	5
Solution Driver	1	1	5	12	1	5	0
Status Aware (Errors/Failures)	0	2	0	2	6	12	3
Tasks (manual - automated)	0	1	1	2	2	12	7
Infrastructure Utilization	0	2	2	1	4	13	3
Vendor Management	0	3	3	4	6	4	5

Q4.5 - Maturity models consist of levels also of dimensions. Provide per dimension...

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses	Sum
Actions are defined up-front	33.00	39.00	36.68	1.59	2.54	25	917.00
Automation	33.00	39.00	38.08	1.35	1.83	25	952.00
Automation Architecture	35.00	39.00	38.08	1.13	1.27	25	952.00
Agility	33.00	39.00	37.12	1.51	2.27	25	928.00
Business Process Management	33.00	39.00	36.28	1.61	2.60	25	907.00
Compliance	33.00	39.00	37.28	1.71	2.92	25	932.00
Documentation	34.00	39.00	37.44	1.30	1.69	25	936.00
Data Management	34.00	39.00	37.36	1.49	2.23	25	934.00
Education	34.00	39.00	36.80	1.57	2.48	25	920.00
Ecosystem relationship	34.00	39.00	36.32	1.57	2.46	25	908.00
Financial	33.00	39.00	35.76	1.70	2.90	25	894.00
Governance	33.00	39.00	37.32	1.67	2.78	25	933.00
Knowledge	34.00	39.00	37.64	1.23	1.51	25	941.00
Infrastructure	34.00	39.00	36.96	1.40	1.96	25	924.00
Infrastructure Configuration	35.00	39.00	37.68	1.26	1.58	25	942.00
Infrastructure Deployment	35.00	39.00	37.88	1.14	1.31	25	947.00
Infrastructure Management	35.00	39.00	37.80	1.13	1.28	25	945.00
Infrastructure Provisioning	35.00	39.00	38.00	1.10	1.20	25	950.00
IT Architecture	34.00	39.00	37.32	1.64	2.70	25	933.00
Operations	33.00	39.00	37.52	1.30	1.69	25	938.00
One Central truth	33.00	39.00	37.16	1.76	3.09	25	929.00
Repeatability	33.00	39.00	37.96	1.48	2.20	25	949.00
Process Management	33.00	39.00	36.52	1.42	2.01	25	913.00

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Scalability	34.00	39.00	37.68	1.19	1.42	25	942.00
Standardization	34.00	39.00	37.92	1.13	1.27	25	948.00
Security	33.00	39.00	37.68	1.67	2.78	25	942.00
Service Management	33.00	38.00	36.64	1.47	2.15	25	916.00
Self-Service	36.00	39.00	37.84	0.83	0.69	25	946.00
Skills	34.00	39.00	37.20	1.44	2.08	25	930.00
Software	33.00	39.00	36.52	1.58	2.49	25	913.00
Software Development	33.00	39.00	37.04	1.68	2.84	25	926.00
Solution Driver	33.00	38.00	36.04	1.25	1.56	25	901.00
Status Aware (Errors/Failures)	34.00	39.00	37.40	1.26	1.60	25	935.00
Tasks (manual - automated)	34.00	39.00	37.76	1.27	1.62	25	944.00
Infrastructure Utilization	34.00	39.00	37.32	1.41	1.98	25	933.00
Vendor Management	34.00	39.00	36.80	1.62	2.64	25	920.00

Q4.6 - Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

"actions are defined upfront" is mostly true, but when AI comes into play, the goals are defined upfront.

no

I skip these answers for now because of my time and the 'fear' if I don't complete it that my former answers are lost...

Q4.7 - If you have any comments or additions to these dimensions, please describe them.

If you have any comments or additions to these dimensions, please describe them.

Neutral means: are in some form part of maturity, but not in this wording

automation (2nd bullet) cannot be part of automation.

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I have rated the dimensions not lower than neutral since each dimension needs explanation on what you mean by it. As an example, it is unclear what your definition of Vendor Management is. Do you mean the element managers provided by a vendor, the support relationship to a vendor, the involvement of the vendor in solution designs, or any other definition.

I feel there is a mix between traditional quality dimensions (iso 25001) and maturity dimensions. Maturity for me is more about the organisation's capabilities, quality is more about the product's aspects

It's hard to fill in, because you don't provide definitions and/or context.

Related to "status aware (errors/failures)" you could mention "self healing / self remediation"

Q5.2 - The following statements describe the different maturity levels. Provide pe...

Field	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Manual Semi-automated Automated Service-Based Policy-Based	0	0	2	2	7	12	2
Not Stable Local Stable Partial Stable Passive Stable Active Stable	6	5	3	4	5	2	0
Basic Controlled Standarized Optimized Innovative	0	3	1	3	7	7	4
Initial Repeatable Defined Managed Optimized	0	1	3	3	5	8	5

Q5.2 - The following statements describe the different maturity levels. Provide pe...

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses	Sum
Manual Semi-automated Automated Service-Based Policy-Based	14.00	18.00	16.40	1.02	1.04	25	410.00
Not Stable Local Stable Partial Stable Passive Stable Active Stable	12.00	17.00	14.12	1.68	2.83	25	353.00
Basic Controlled Standarized Optimized Innovative	13.00	18.00	16.04	1.51	2.28	25	401.00
Initial Repeatable Defined Managed Optimized	13.00	18.00	16.24	1.42	2.02	25	406.00

Q5.3 - Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Level 5 traditionally is always about self-correction. The terms should reflect this (as some do)

no

I skipped these because of my time, and I'm not sure if my previous answers are lost if I continue later on the day.

I don't understand what you want the word "stable" to mean here

Q5.4 - If you have any comments or additions to these descriptions, please describe them.

If you have any comments or additions to these descriptions, please describe them.

I don't like Basic or initial in a maturity model.

Basic is part of basic, medium, good, expert... provides no useful reference.

Initial implies that all organizations start in the model on initial status, which neglects existing maturity levels

Neither one actually makes the maturity level clear for me. Maybe it is wise to have different maturity levels on Operational management, Implementation, Infrastructure capabilities, Levels of standardized services, Automation agility, End-user experience, or other 'soft' terms.

Maybe a level scale referring to the effort involved? From highly manual to fully self correcting

Q5.5 - This question is about some generic statements about the first draft of thi...

Field	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
This model provides a path to grow in automation maturity.	0	1	0	2	8	10	4
With five levels you can properly define a maturity model for automation.	0	0	0	1	6	13	5
Five levels are too many to define an automation maturity model.	5	12	7	1	0	0	0
Level 1 to level 3 are more about day-0 and day-1 operations.	0	1	3	13	6	2	0
Level 4 and level 5 are more about day-2 operations.	0	1	3	13	6	2	0
Level 1 to level 3 are primary for delivering service.	1	1	4	8	6	5	0
Level 4 and level 5 are primary for operating the IT infrastructure (update, life cycle management, etc).	1	2	4	10	5	3	0

Q5.6 - Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Are there one or more choices you would like to explain?

Question 4 and 5 are not clear to me. I think every level developments has all 3 day-phases

i don't understand last 4 statements (day-2?)

unclear question.

Day-0, day-1 and day-2 operations are not part of the maturity level. In each of these you can be on level 1 or up to level 5.

The maturity table gives insight in the current situation, but does not provide a path. This could be an additional guide that describes high level actions to get to the next level. This actually also depends on the technology part that you are dealing with.

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no

I skipped these because of my time, and I'm not sure if my previous answers are lost if I continue later on the day.

I am not comfortable with the first draft of the maturity model. The dimensions that are mentioned, should in my opinion be aspects for determining the level, rather than dimensions themselves.

Q5.7 - If you have any comments or additions to these generic statements, please describe them.

If you have any comments or additions to these generic statements, please describe them.

Technology: I don't like software centric, I would prefer service-centric

Automation and provisioning feel overlapping

Automation: Basic configuration automation is using a controller-based multiple device automation, so level 2 and 3 not clear distinguishable.

Analytics: Preventative seems more mature dan predictive

Automation and Tasks feels overlapping with Automation. Is scripting a way to automate tasks?

Documentation has nice levels

Ability to change: I prefers simpler: months - days - hours - minutes - seconds

I think I would be more comfortable with a model in which infrastructure building blocks are dimensions.

I don't know what day-X operations are

Q6.2 - What is your job description?

Q6.2 - What is your job description?

What is your job description?

IT Services Director

Solution Architect

Data network/transport Infrastructure engineer

IT Architect

Enterprise Architect

enterprise architect

Teamlead

Architecture

Principal Technologist

IT Architect

IT Infrastructure engineer

it architect

Network Architect

Enterprise Architect

Architect

Technical Architect

Head of Enterprise Architecture

Enterprise architect

Technical Architect

Enterprise Architect

Q6.3 - In which sector of economy are you working?

Q6.3 - In which sector of economy are you working?

Q7.1 - Are there any additional comments or suggestions?

Are there any additional comments or suggestions?

Not for now.

In topics that are more difficult, the non-native expressions make things harder to understand and therefore harder to answer correctly.

(By all means - I am no native speaker as well, but much more proficient in reading)

success with processing the answers !!

success!

Good and solid survey. Interested if there is within the academic world a broad based model that has a broad adaptation with the community.

keep up the good work!

Automation is a term that spans from low-level scripts to intent-driven cross-technology orchestration tools that serve the whole IT stack. It can be plotted on technology but also on processes. The implementation of an automated process also means looking at the lifecycle of this piece of automation. What is the agility to change or even remove an automated process. And is there insight in the impact of an action within the IT Infrastructure (manual or automated).

And when it comes to maturity, who (or which group of people) is owner and/or is responsible of a piece of automation.

Please keep me informed on the results. It will be very useful for daily application!

I skipped these because of my time, and I'm not sure if my previous answers are lost if I continue later on the day. Contact me if I can edit the results later on for which I didn't have the time for.

Fijn weekend en tot maandag!

